

**Teaching from the heart: crossing the
research/teaching/public engagement nexus.**

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Abstract

This study contributes the understanding of the triple nexus of research, teaching and public engagement (R/T/Pe) in STEM. Specifically, the research explores the perceptions and experiences of Scottish lecturers teaching undergraduate STEM cohorts within disciplines defined by the research excellence framework (REF) as STEM Panel B. Panel B disciplines include engineering; chemistry; computer science; mathematics; physics; earth and environmental sciences.

As Higher Education funding is increasingly explicitly linked to measurements of impact, this builds on the notion of Von Humboldt's teaching/research nexus to explore the role of lecturers in supporting students to integrate R/T/Pe. Notably, STEM panel B disciplines are reportedly the least likely to report on impact case studies within REF which infers that these disciplines are less likely to integrate aspects of public engagement alongside their teaching and research.

A qualitative design using an interpretative phenomenological methodology was used to collect interviews from lecturers alongside novel data collection methods and autoethnography to reflect on interviews findings with participants. Overall, participants found that developing research-readiness in undergraduate cohorts is challenging as undergraduates work towards becoming research-ready, and often public engagement projects can help to overcome these barriers.

For lecturers there are structural barriers that can hinder their ability to develop links between R/T/Pe and this is harder still for those teaching in post-92 universities. Boundary blocks can occur where there is lack of managerial support, funding or protected time within a lecturer's contracted hours. This was not the case in pre-92 and ancient universities where public engagement professionals are often engaged to act as a broker to improve and incentivise engagement outside the university.

Overall, early-career researchers were less likely impacted by boundary blocks to R/T/Pe due to access to CPD and training. This study suggests some recommendations for the purpose and paradigm of the university to be reconfigured, particularly at undergraduate teaching level, to integrate public (external) engagement as the third mission of the university alongside teaching and research.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This thesis gives an account of a phenomenological study that examines the way in which university lecturers in Scotland establish integrative links between undergraduate teaching and research in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). Phenomenology, being the study of lived experience of a given phenomenon and in particular, this study examines the integration of teaching, research and public engagement (R/T/Pe) to understand how lecturers might re-imagine or re-configure their practice to support undergraduate learners in research activity. This chapter will present the background to the study, a statement of researcher positionality, key terminology, research questions and an overview of the problem to be addressed, concluding with an outline of the thesis structure.

1.2 Background and justification of the study

Public engagement is at the forefront of policy and discussion relating to research funding in universities (REF, 2019; Cohen, 2019). Yet little is known about lecturers' perspectives of research/teaching linkages and how these combine with public engagement to reflect what is characterised as an alternative integration of scholarly knowledge processes (McKenzie *et al.*, 2018; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). The aim of this study is to investigate the triple nexus of R/T/Pe in STEM (now referred to as the "triple nexus"), where it sits in practice, and how it impacts on the experiences of lecturers within Scottish higher education institutions (HEIs) (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Focusing on undergraduate teaching, this thesis explores the implementation in lecturers' teaching practice and public engagement activity (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016; Healey and Jenkins, 2009). This field of inquiry is reportedly contested due to the many traditions and complexities concerning the establishment of links between teaching and research in Higher Education (HE) (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). In relation to public engagement there is a gap in tackling the triple nexus identified by Stevenson and McArthur (2015) and an opportunity for academic developers to work with lecturers to work more closely to improve teaching and learning in undergraduate settings (Beckman and Hensel, 2009; Walkington, 2015; Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016; Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017).

My study commenced in 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 crisis heightened some pressing concerns for HE lecturers, including poor internet capacity and connectivity issues (Anderson, 2020), pivoting of teaching practice and approaches to online learning (Crawford *et al.*, 2020; Cochrane *et al.*, 2020; Schwartzman, 2020), and gendered inequalities stemming from the sudden shift to home-working (Kınıkoğlu and Can, 2020). Public engagement with academia came to the forefront as scientists working for the Scottish Government issued daily briefings, which informed the public of the latest developments in incidences of infection, vaccination and movement restrictions (Soremi and Dogo, 2021). The crisis brought about debate on social media, which intensified public discussion and spread misinformation, while other spaces provided a platform for academics and scientists to engage with the public in a more prolific and ubiquitous way than before the crisis (McCrea, 2021).

During this time, members of the public were urged to “trust the science” and the COVID-19 crisis reinforced the theory of praxis through evidence communication (Blastland *et al.*, 2020). Praxis describes how learning is generated by responding to real needs in society, linking the relevance of the curriculum to the wider community: in an educational context, real-world needs can feed real-world research, which can be used to inform teaching and “...the curriculum as praxis” (Freire, 2014; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). For example, increased pressures on medical staff highlighted a sudden need for medical students to access applied practice during their final year to ensure a better level of preparedness for working as soon as they qualified. This meant that the sudden and unexpected transition to the workforce experienced by medical students during the crisis brought new teaching methods to support real-life research for those students who stepped up to provide help and assistance during their studies (Choi *et al.*, 2020).

Crisis communication during the pandemic was foregrounded by the global declaration of a climate emergency (Ripple *et al.*, 2019), and many examples of teaching practice dealt with this other crisis during the pandemic, prompting educators to adapt their approaches to teaching, through digital pedagogy, democratised learning and outreach programmes (Kluczkowski *et al.*, 2021). Despite challenges, the role of education in relation to these current public crises indicates the importance of the attendant disruptive challenges, which are noted as potential catalysts in re-

configuring teaching practice (Fuller *et al.*, 2021). The impact and disruption of the pandemic has undoubtedly revealed the precarity of systems, alongside the ability to adapt as a rapid response to crisis (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020).

As educators in STEM disciplines consider the burgeoning and advancing effects of the climate emergency, this presents an opportunity to adopt research strategies to develop technical efficiencies alongside students as co-creators to prepare them to adapt to crisis as it evolves (Cross and Congreve, 2020). This underlines the need to strengthen links between science and society through R/T/Pe, enabling students to be better equipped to deal with real-life research, as STEM skills are typically in undersupply in this respect in Scotland (Kemp and Lawton, 2013; SFC, 2019).

Returning to teaching in HE, the relationship between R/T/Pe is multifarious in terms of institutional and individual identities (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; Crawford *et al.*, 2020). Teacher agency is affected by metrics – that is, the measurement of research output and funding, which has a potentially harmful impact on lecturer agency, according to McCune (2019). The interlinkage between teaching and research has predominantly been measured in quantitative terms and little evidence reveals an influence on student agency (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). However, a call has been made to examine the role of student-as-producer and understand the ways in which lecturers implement this (Brew, 2010; Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020).

There is clear recognition within institutions and departments that the impact of public engagement through research can fundamentally impact teaching and learning (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Walkington, 2015). At this juncture, it is important to consider how public engagement is defined. It is reported that conceptions of public engagement differ from person to person and vary according to different academic contexts (Cohen, 2019; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). As a starting point, to contextualise *public engagement*, I adopt a definition from the National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCPE) 2017 report – *Reviewing public engagement in REF 2014: Reflections for shaping the second REF*:

By “public engagement” we mean interaction with people outside academia, in their capacity as citizens and members of communities of place or interest. We differentiate public engagement from engagement

with policy making, business and the professions, but recognise in practice they often overlap.

(Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017)

However, public engagement, as a defining term in HE, appears to be problematised in this respect (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) and at odds with neoliberal policies based on metrics and league tables within HE (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018; McLinden, 2015; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). I will therefore draw on literature concerning these debates and ongoing dialogues in the following chapter to guide the qualitative methodology of the study and identify knowledge gaps pertinent to Scottish HE (Creswell, 2014).

1.3 Researcher positionality

My background as a community engagement worker and rural development consultant has involved project work with academic institutions in Scotland. This has undoubtedly impacted my approach to the study (Secules *et al.*, 2021). I am a second career academic whose cultural professional upbringing was external to the university, a persona that Boyd and Grant (2019) suggest can act as a “mirror” or “health check”, underlining the role of student as teacher, as espoused by Brazilian educator Paulo Freire (Freire, 2014).

As a community education practitioner in the third sector, I have had insight into the ways in which universities can work with the public to promulgate benefits to wider society through various projects I worked with in community development and agriculture. Conversely, I have also worked in the formal surroundings of a Scottish university and become aware of the obligations of universities to public engagement relating to research funding and reporting on impact (NCCPE, 2021b). From an initial broad literature search, several challenges and debates surrounding the triple nexus are apparent, which inform the research questions of this study (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Exploring what Creswell (2014) outlines as researcher positionality, this section scrutinises the influence of my own standpoint as a researcher and is articulated as an identity memo (Robson, 2011) to explore the dialectical relationships that may

impact on the study (Mertens, 2020). This has led me to examine, through reflection, how my upbringing, gender, sexuality (Berger, 2013), ethnicity (Mertens, 2020), social class (Ball, 2006), culture (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020) and economic situation may impinge on the complexities of the study. Reflection is a foundational element of educational research (Ball, 2006; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) and, through my reflections, I aim to confer the significance of my values and ethics through critical examination (Farrow *et al.* (2020) of my worldview (Creswell (2014) in relation to this thesis.

It is acknowledged that, during the study, researcher positionality may be fluid and shift from etic (i.e. an outsider viewpoint) to emic (i.e. from within a social group) (Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021). This, Berger (2013) claims, can be modulated through reflexivity as a strategy to maintain quality control in qualitative research. Contextualising researcher positionality goes beyond mitigating bias, according to Secules *et al.* (2021). To this end, I have used data visualisation to help me examine my positionality to understand power relationships between the researcher and the researched (Berger, 2013).

Figure 1: The Wheel of Power/Privilege (Duckworth, 2021)

Educator and illustrator Duckworth (2021) visualises the power/privilege wheel in Figure 1 using data derived from studies of marginalisation and intersectionality to evidence the impact that marginalisation can have on educators. Arguably, it can also impact researchers (Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021; Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Secules *et al.*, 2021). Using data visualisation as an aid to examine my positionality is a powerful method to link my research to those who engage with it. In turn, this has appealing connections to public engagement with research in STEM (Allen, 2018; Lee, West and Howe, 2017).

1.4 My story

Storytelling is acknowledged as an academic literacy that supports public engagement (Clarkson *et al.*, 2018; Weitkamp, 2018; Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020) through a form of expressive scholarship (Sandmann and Jones, 2019) able to facilitate transparency of power and politics through aesthetic edification (Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020). This reflection therefore commences as a narrative journey drawing on elements of qualitative inquiry through portraiture and autobiographic narrative (Dixson, Chapman and Hill, 2016; Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020). The journey concludes in Chapter six by linking to an autoethnographic reflective account to contextualise the impact of the findings of the study through self-reflection (Kmita, 2017; Kinchin and Francis, 2016; Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020; Boncori and Smith, 2019).

I started out life growing up on a farm in the Northwest Highlands of Scotland. My father was the son of an Irish emigrant who came to Liverpool at the turn of the twentieth century, while my mother was a former university lecturer who gave up her career to become a housewife. My grandfather gained a scholarship to study social and political science at Liverpool despite his perceived lowly financial and ethnic status. On leaving, he joined the civil service as a modestly salaried post office clerk. My father had a propensity for academia. He came first to England for his 1927 matriculation exams. However, his parents could no longer afford to school him, so he left school aged fourteen and found work in a library as an office boy and accessed self-funded HE in his late twenties.

From a widening participation perspective (Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019), I am not the “first in the family” to attend HE, and my journey to HE has been smooth and supported in comparison to those of my father and his father. I have been privileged to have a private education and an undergraduate student grant in a time before tuition fees were introduced in some parts of the UK. However, my early learning was developed through the state education system in Scotland, a system with contemporary alignment to the civic identity of Scotland (Ozga, 2020), rooted in egalitarian principles that were developed following the Reformation with the establishment of parish schools (Leith and Sim, 2020). I am conscious and proud of this identity, which is distinct from the rest of the UK and substantiated in a national approach that prepones a state-run education system as a cultural pillar of Scottish society (Britton, Schweisfurth and Slade, 2018; Leith and Sim, 2020).

The nature of my familial academic identity and its associated diversity and complexity has led me to consider how academic identity is constructed (Annala and Mäkinen, 2016; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021; Kinchin and Francis, 2016). My academic journey had a hiatus when I was faced with the choice of continuing in my career path or coming home to run the family farm when both my parents died when I was in my early twenties. At the time, connectivity in the Highlands of Scotland was restricted to tortuous, lengthy road and rail links and the worldwide web was yet to come. I gave little thought to my academic career, relinquished an offer from University College London (UCL) to do an MSc, and came home to run the farm. Parallel to my mother's own path, I gave up any hope of academic study when I became a mother. This echoes gender barriers noted by Burdick and Sandlin (2015), suggesting a need to elucidate these critical perspectives as a mirror to one's own identity.

My mother was convent-educated and wished to study science. This was abhorrent to the conservative conditioning of the nuns, who suggested that she take up a vocation. If science had to be part of this, she should consider becoming a nurse (heaven forbid a doctor) or a science teacher (provided the pages relating to human reproduction in the textbook were neatly scored out in black pen). I therefore need to acknowledge that, sixty years on, the gendered nature of the education profession prevails and the impact of neoliberalism on the HE student intake continues to favour females (Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018; Kandiko, 2010; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019). Furthermore, within the scientific community, it has been acknowledged that there is a need to democratise the profession, while public communication of science is now widely acknowledged as a vehicle for achieving this (Weitkamp, 2018; Kahan, 2015; Kompella *et al.*, 2020b). This acknowledgement attempts to highlight imbalances in terms of how my own gender may relate to my interaction with disciplines and participants who engage with the study.

I will now share a portrait (Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020) of my undergraduate self to explore aspects of the teaching–research nexus (Brew, 1999; Brew, 2010; Healey and Jenkins, 2009; McLinden *et al.*, 2015; Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Kinchin and Francis, 2016). At agricultural college in the mid-1990s, a Wednesday afternoon meant ubiquitous rugby games and, for those who did not play or support a team, there was the prospect of study or paid work. Potato picking season was upon us and, on hearing that £3 an hour was being paid, I joined the Crop and Environment Research Centre

(CERC) as a field assistant. The CERC was a department attached to the university, yet it did not mix with our day-to-day classes. The inhabitants were uniformly clothed in white lab coats (doctors and professors) or heavy metal T-shirts and long curtain-like hair (postgrads and postdocs).

Over my four years in the otherworld of the CERC, I learned through fieldwork about groundwater pollution, nitrogen vulnerable zones (NVZs) and trials in growing crops using slurry. In my classes, sitting at the back of a dark lecture theatre, I integrated this practical knowledge into agri-policy lectures with the dry edicts of the water directive framework, which seemed little more than EU bureaucracy from the pages of a book. The integration of teaching and research by default through my Wednesday job enabled me to access deeper learning (Biggs and Tang, 2011) subconsciously through a zone of proximal development (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016). This also led to significant changes that influenced my career.

My fringe involvement with the work of the CERC started a passion for activism and environmental inquiry, and a divergence from conventional agriculture, favouring an ecological approach, which, twenty years ago, was regarded as left-field, incongruent with profitability and success. Twenty years on, I seek to understand how educational theory proposed by social constructivists, such as Dewey and Vygotsky (Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018), can underline the importance of real-life research as a means to enhance student-led learning. This has led me to examine how the links between teaching and research enhance pedagogy to achieve collective paradigm shifts relevant to pressing societal needs (Obermeister, 2020). The next section explains the background to the study through its aims and how they link to my own experience and positionality as a researcher (Beattie, 2021).

1.5 Key terminology

The study adopts a qualitative approach. It is therefore prudent to note that definitions of some key terms remain tentative (Creswell, 2014) and will be explored in greater depth within the body of the literature review.

Higher Education (HE): This refers to continuation of study upon leaving school from undergraduate to postgraduate level. In Scotland there are fully funded places for undergraduate study, which typically includes a four-year honours programme (Leith and Sim, 2020; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019; Briggs, 2006) and is distinctly

different from the system in the rest of the UK, where fees are charged for all undergraduate degrees and typically do not include an honours year.

Institutional identity: HE reforms of technical colleges from the 1960s have led to the establishment of different types of institutions with different identities. The most contemporary are “post-92” institutions, which now have degree-awarding powers alongside the ancient and established universities in the UK (Adesola and Dutta, 2020). HEI identity is traditionally immutably framed as a binary identity – research-intensive or teaching-intensive (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018; Hewitt-Dundas, 2012). Despite this, it is claimed that many universities ascribe to the ideals of unity between research and teaching espoused by Wilhelm von Humboldt, the founding father of the University of Berlin (Laiho, Jauhiainen and Jauhiainen, 2020; McLinden, 2015; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020), challenging the dominant cultural identities of HEIs (Carrillo-Durán and García García, 2020; Sandmann and Jones, 2019).

Academic identity: Academic identity is a complex understanding of the ways in which academics valorise their professional roles. Traditionally, a lecturer’s duality between teaching and research has informed academic identity. However, it is widely acknowledged within the academic community that such a dualistic viewpoint is archaic and fails to articulate the complexity of identity (Aitken and O’Carroll, 2020; Laiho, Jauhiainen and Jauhiainen, 2020). It is recognised that, while engagement with current research is foundational to a strong sense of this identity (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; McKinley *et al.*, 2020), it can foster tensions with regard to the primacy of research over teaching practice (McCune, 2019) and performativity expectations (Eardley, Banister and Fletcher, 2020; Sutton, 2017).

Public engagement: In the context of this study, this refers to aspects of public engagement within the field of HE. The definition of public engagement is complex, multi-faceted and pluralistic (Brew, 2010; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; van Der Zwet and Connolly, 2020; Hoffmann, 2020). Public engagement is characterised along a broad spectrum from the grassroots as a civic definition (Boland, 2014) to a strictly managerial definition that articulates the “*impact agenda*” (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020). From an HE funding perspective, public engagement is defined as the ways in which the benefits and activity of research can be shared with the public and

measured attendant to its consequent funding mechanisms (REF, 2018; Vohland *et al.*, 2021; VITAE, 2010b). However, this definition is contested in applied practice, which can be inherently subjective (Sandmann and Jones, 2019; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Third spaces: These are non-traditional spaces or social settings where individuals work and have impact (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). These can be online (Lo Presti and Marino, 2019) or in social media spaces such as blogs, microblogs or auto-photography channels such as Instagram (Jarreau *et al.*, 2019; Loopmans, Cowell and Oosterlynck, 2012). These spaces (e.g., blogs, podcasts and videos) facilitate free and open access publishing. In academic circles, these spaces can host what is termed “grey literature” – published material that has not been subject to formal peer review (Adams, Smart and Huff, 2017).

Communities of practice (CoP): This term was first used in 1991 by theorists Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger to describe a set of relations between persons and activity within an area of practice over time. CoPs may be formal or informal and may relate to other tangential, overlapping and bridging CoPs (Brew, 2010; Annala and Mäkinen, 2016; Carr *et al.*, 2020). CoPs are integrated into social learning theory, which claims that modes of knowledge are created and situated within the learning environment itself and that “work” is achieved through this social interaction (Eardley, Banister and Fletcher, 2020; Novakovich, Miah and Shaw, 2017). The construction of social identity as “legitimate peripheral participation” allows for the inclusion and ratification of newcomers who join and participate within a CoP (Novakovich, Miah and Shaw, 2017; Obermeister, 2020).

Authentic research activity: This refers to student-centred learning conducted using real-life examples (Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018) and informed by applied scholarly research (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Walkington, 2015). Early scholars in this field include John Dewey (1859–1952), an American philosopher whose approach was viewed as progressive social constructivism (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016; Gu, 2010) and linked to a broader public good (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018), and Lev Vygotsky (1896–1934), a Russian psychologist whose theories proposed the role of the educator as support, or scaffolding, to the learning activity (Britton, Schweisfurth and Slade, 2018; Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016). He described this as a *zone of*

proximal development enacted by learning through real-life problem-solving in practical or applied tasks (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Research-informed teaching (RIT): This is an increasingly popular approach prioritised by HEIs (Cross and Congreve, 2020; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). RIT describes the dialogic linkages between teaching and research (McKinley *et al.*, 2020). While McLinden (2015) describes five approaches to RIT, Brennan *et al.* (2019) explore the complexity of RIT, noting that there are frequent overlaps between different types of research–teaching linkages, suggesting that the definition can mean different things to different people.

Scaffolding: This is a metaphorical term used by Jerome Bruner (1915–2016), a cognitive psychologist, to describe the acquisition of learning through a social constructivist approach whereby young children were observed to acquire language through informal learning and prompts from their caregivers or parents. The assistance given to a learner through the help of a more experienced peer or teacher reputedly stems from the work of Vygotsky (Spronken-Smith and Walker, 2010) and is a concept widely attributed to the zone of proximal development. However, Shvarts and Bakker (2019) argue that Vygotsky never used this term in an educational context, suggesting that its links have been established in day-to-day teaching practice rather than theoretical exposition.

Knowledge transfer: This describes the process of sharing or dissemination of information within research. In academia this can be applied in teaching, public engagement, consultancy and innovation (Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; Spence, 2018). The term is widely used in university policy and underpins the formation of institutional research strategy (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). Alternative to this term, **knowledge exchange** suggests a greater level of porosity and opportunity for students, or publics as co-creator within these frameworks (Preece, 2016).

Research-mindedness: This describes the ways in which humans as social actors critically engage with research in their day-to-day activity. This has come to the forefront in academia as HEIs have shifted emphasis from a teaching-focused approach to greater levels of research intensity (Sandmann and Jones, 2019; Schalet,

Tropp and Troy, 2020). The theoretical roots of this approach emerge from the theory of Wilhelm von Humboldt (1767–1835), who articulated the importance of research and teaching linkages to support student learning (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Geschwind and Broström, 2015; Tight, 2016).

Open educational practices (OEPs): an emerging pedagogy rooted within the open education movement. OEPs are defined by Farrow *et al.* (2020) as education practices within a community of scholars who work towards the free and openly available access to knowledge and research. This will include the sharing of practice in the public domain and an acknowledgement by using licencing that is free and open access, such as creative commons to facilitate re-use, remix and adaptation of open educational resources (OERs) (Weller, 2018).

Science communication: refers to the communication of science in an accessible language to a broad audience (Trench, 2008). Science communication can take many different forms from workshops, to festivals, blogging, to writing, school visits to prison outreach (Metcalf, 2019). Different approaches to science communication may have different motivations and target audiences according to the need and context of delivery. Consequently, there may be various terms associated with science communication from impact, to public engagement, outreach or knowledge transfer (Bucchi, 2017).

STEM panel disciplines: as defined by the research excellence framework (REF) for STEM subjects these are classified as Panel A (agriculture, allied health, biological sciences, clinical medicine, psychology and public health) or Panel B (engineering, chemistry, computer science, mathematics, physics, earth and environmental sciences). According to Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017), STEM Panel B disciplines were least likely to mention engagement with the public in REF impact case studies in 2014, added to this, there was a considerable variation within disciplines with aeronautical engineering being the least likely to mention public engagement, and physics being the most likely.

Research Excellence Framework (REF): a system for assessing the quality of research in HEIs. Reportedly one of the most institutionalised systems in the world the system has reportedly influenced research assessment on a supranational basis (Marques *et al.*, 2017). The REF has attracted criticisms from HEIs and individuals

particularly in relation to funding which is inextricably linked to REF scores which some critics liken to leagues tables, or a football transfer window (Baird and Elliott, 2018). The REF runs in cycles, the first of which was in 2014. REF 2014 was reviewed to make a number of improvements, particularly in respect of public engagement and measures of impact (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017; Great Britain Department for Business, 2016). The second REF cycle in 2021 has attracted attention from scholars and HEIs given the performative nature of its principles and the macro conditions which is at risk of endangering the unity between teaching and research (McKinley *et al.*, 2020).

1.6 Aims and focus of the study

Based on the preceding discussion, this research investigates how lecturers support undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness in the context of the triple nexus of R/T/Pe in STEM Panel B disciplines as defined by the Research Excellence Framework (REF) (REF, 2018). Within this definition units of assessment are within the following disciplines: Chemistry; Physics; Mathematical Sciences; Engineering; Computer Science and Informatics; Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences which are noted to be the least likely of all panels of assessment (A-D) to submit an impact case study (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017). The research questions proposed in [Section 2.3.7](#) aim to elicit descriptive data concerning the lived experience of STEM Panel B lecturers in Scottish universities to frame the context of the study.

1.7 Structure of the study

Following this introductory chapter, I move to a review of the literature in Chapter two, presented in two sections and examining the history, theory and current discourse relating to public engagement in HE and the teaching–research nexus. Chapter three, meanwhile, outlines a justification for the choice of methodology and methods used to gather empirical data, and the findings from the study are presented in Chapter four. In Chapter five, I discuss the findings and critically evaluate these in the context of the literature review and chosen methodology. Lastly, the thesis concludes with an autoethnographic reflection on the study before moving on to discuss the study limitations and propose relevant recommendations including directions for future research arising from the empirical findings.

1.8 Conclusion

This introduction has identified my positionality as a researcher to mitigate and acknowledge my stance in relation to the social and political context of the study. I have situated the research within a R/T/Pe nexus lens and introduced current issues and interactions between scholarly research, pedagogy and public engagement in HE. I have set out the key terminology and main theorists informing the development of teaching and learning theories that link the research to the research questions that will guide this study. I now move to Chapter two, which presents a review of literature pertinent to the study.

Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews current literature, exploring how the notion of *re-imagining* or *re-configuring* the relationship between R/T/Pe in Scottish HEIs is approached through a review of relevant educational theory together with contemporaneous studies. Opening with an outline of the literature search strategy, the sections following focus on current studies in public engagement defining terms will introduce the ways in which public engagement intersects with the teaching/research nexus to develop a critical understanding of the research topic (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015; Wellington, 2010). To conclude, gaps in understanding are highlighted to frame the context of the study and narrow the focus of the research questions.

2.1.1 Literature review search strategy

The purpose of a literature review is to advance knowledge and theory generation by providing a framework from which to define and clarify concepts (Boote and Beile, 2005; Creswell, 2014). This will reduce partiality and bias (Punch and Oancea, 2014), critically engage with literature to highlight research gaps (Bryman, 2016; Boote and Beile, 2005), and contextualise the study through the identification of research gaps (Klein, 2012). This is characterised as a scholarly process of evidence synthesis using existing datasets and peer-reviewed journal papers (Punch and Oancea, 2014; Boote and Beile, 2005). Social science reviews are typically dialogic and iterative, which necessitates regular re-reviews of literature throughout a study (Wisker, 2008; Wallace and Wray, 2016). Awareness of the current breadth and acceleration of knowledge production within the chosen field of study therefore underlines the crucial importance of the review (Snyder, 2019).

The UWS Academy research brief and working title for the PhD project included key references to inform the direction of the study. Using this as a starting point, initial broad searches were carried out using electronic search engines, namely Google Scholar, Web of Science and Ethos online. Searches explored formative theory and key concepts relating to R/T/Pe in HE (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011) and focused on its relevance through concept mapping the research proposal to locate

literature in a preliminary map using the software package NVivo 12 Pro (Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2016).

Figure 2: Preliminary literature map exploring the R/T/Pe nexus developed from NVivo 12 Pro.

The relevance of key concepts is preponed by Maxwell (2016), who critiques Boote and Beile (2005) for their resolute adherence to literature as “foundational”. Adopting a vernacular metaphor, Maxwell (2016) suggests that a literature review is less like the foundation of a building and more like a tool, such as a drill. This metaphor fits well with constructivism theory, following the notion that public engagement activity in academia aligns well with Vygotsky’s constructivist theory in teaching (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). I therefore adopted a literature search strategy developed through keyword search terms (stage 1 and 2 below) from which to inform a search strategy beyond the overview of key papers (Mertens, 2020).

Stage 1: Key papers

Twenty-five initial papers, some of which were contained within the research proposal, were read and reviewed to search terms with branched search words:

- Public engagement (HE/history/metrics/strategy/impact)
- HE research (intensity/metrics/funding/impact)
- HE teaching (research/undergraduates/funding/impact)
- Science communication (impact/strategies/funding/teaching/research)
- Researcher positionality (bias/ethics)

Stage 2: Initial search terms

I put these search terms into two online search engines – *Google Scholar* and *Web of Science* – to identify and read a number of peer-reviewed journal articles matching the conceptualisation of the study (Wallace and Wray, 2016). To prioritise the currency of data, papers were limited to a search that focused on those published within the last five years of the outset of the study (2016–2020) and then extended to establish whether any older research papers had relevance within the preceding fifteen years. Papers were downloaded and deposited in an online reference management system, EndNote 20. This software was used from the inception of the literature search to enable a system to categorise and store papers with a seamless referencing system that could be integrated with MS Word. Following this, I made notes by hand in my research journal to critically analyse the relevance and synergy between papers, noting themes as I went along.

Visual data was constructed in NVivo as a word cloud to give weight to themes. This was created after uploading the second stage papers to the programme (Allen, 2018). It should be noted that NVivo is limited in that it can only analyse digital text. Where possible, I therefore ensured that I uploaded copies of digital versions of print books when available. Words were weighted according to frequency, revealing research as the most frequently occurring word, with education and teaching used less frequently but still featuring prominently.

Stage 3: Conceptualising themes through extended literature search

During this stage, I gathered 312 papers for review and eighty-eight methodology and methods papers on EndNote 20. On 31 October 2023 the literature re-review was

completed and the database included 439 publications, incorporating new papers as well as additional information gathered following data analysis. To analyse literature I wrote mini essays and cameos to summarise and structure the written work thematically (Creswell, 2014; Mertens, 2020). In addition, I read and accessed papers using alternative methods to a keyword search. This was done through targeting specific journals to read, citation searches and following current research identified at relevant conferences, webinars and journal clubs. Further, I accessed grey literature – literature that has not been subjected to peer review, such as blogs, tweet chats and podcasts (Adams, Smart and Huff, 2017). The rationale for using this type of non-traditional literature as well as peer-reviewed publications was to incorporate some more informal publicly available material relevant to the subject area.

For example, the London School of Economics Higher Education blog, although not peer reviewed, is a highly respected source of information and has been used to disseminate the findings of Watermeyer and Rowe (2021; 2021a). The blog goes to publication more swiftly than peer-reviewed journals and is publicly available, unlike closed access or pay-per-view papers which cannot be viewed without an institutional access licence (Weller, 2011). The content of blogs such as these can provide a place for any member of the public to sift through digital information to build knowledge, arguably shifting content from knowledge capitalism to digital socialism (Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021). Interestingly, Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards (2021) concur, they highlight blogs and digital spaces as a valid pathway, alternative to traditional routes such as journals, for the dissemination of findings for virtual qualitative research. This is particularly valid in the COVID-19 era.

I maintained a careful awareness of the traditional bounds of scholarly knowledge production in terms of the hierarchy of evidence. This ranking is typically reinforced through journal quality ratings and citation scores, which influenced my choice of source to some extent (Sheridan *et al.*, 2019). Any information signposted through grey literature was followed up by a search for a reference to a connected journal article or conference proceedings linked to the information. An example of such was the British Society for Phenomenology (BSP) podcast (BSP, 2020). The development of the methodology was aided by the ability to access a multi-modal range of information relating to phenomenology through listening and reading. The BSP

podcast signposted me to the associated journal repository and the work of Keane (2019), who was featured on a number of podcasts relating to phenomenology.

Stage 4: Writing the review

NVivo was utilised to organise the review and enhance the collation of literature (Beekhuizen, 2007). This was done by querying key terms and snipping elements of papers, using cut and paste functions, into a thematic coding framework based on the concept map of literature produced in the preliminary review. Each concept node was assigned child nodes on the software, which emerged from the themes within literature. An example of the aspects of public engagement and associated child nodes is outlined below. At this point, the review was paused to start the process of finalising research questions and methodology prior to gathering primary data (Klein, 2012).

Figure 3: Child nodes for public engagement derived from thematic coding framework in NVivo Pro 12.

Stage 5: Re-visiting the review

The possibility of emergent hypotheses arising during the study is an intrinsic feature of social science, according to Mertens (2020). The written review therefore was iterative and critical in the context of the relevance of new literature as it was published (Bryman, 2016). Consequently, new literature relevant to the study following the stage 4 review was saved in EndNote 20 in a file incorporated into a new file to ensure the currency of research data was reflected within the thesis when the review concluded on 31 October 2023. The next section presents findings from the literature review. [Section 2.2.](#) discusses the positioning and role of public engagement within academia and considers how knowledge is produced in this respect. Following this, [Section 2.3](#)

explores approaches to the research/teaching nexus in the context of its history, present day practice and integration with public engagement.

2.2 Engaging with academia

The twenty-first century has brought heightened scrutiny of the role of HEIs in terms of public perceptions of impact and public engagement (Bergan, 2004; Brew, 2010; Byrne, 2016; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Preece, 2016; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). The formation of wider ideas about public engagement from literature is the starting point of this section (Wallace and Wray, 2016). These are discussed in context within educational theory, policy and practice. To establish a context and bound the study, this chapter aims to provide a structure to broadly examine the theoretical foundations of the interaction between the triple nexus within STEM Panel B disciplines in terms of history and context (Wellington, 2010; Creswell, 2014). The HE landscape is interspersed with value pluralism (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Janke, 2019) and a strong emphasis on value for money and performativity (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020). There is a need to address new challenges such as massification (Brew, 2010; Spence, 2018) and widening participation (Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019; Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018) with political and economic drivers (Byrne, 2016; Thomson and Walker, 2010).

The direct link between funding mechanisms and the public impact agenda (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015) has unsurprisingly added pressure to the workload of academics, who have experienced a net transfer of time from research to teaching (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). An academic's "ladder of competing priorities" is susceptible to the further demands associated with demonstrating impact (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) and there is friction between reporting of short-term, linear, neoliberal impact measures (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020) in contrast to longer-term change, which Archer *et al.* (2021) suggests could be mapped using techniques rooted in the theory of change to support a holistic learning ecology model, as preponed by Bronfenbrenner (1979).

Critics allude to policies that constrict the motivations of scholars and students in an increasingly marketised model (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Olmos-López

and Tusting, 2020). This highlights its focus to serve primarily political or economic concerns (Annala and Mäkinen, 2016; Sandmann and Jones, 2019) rather than a societal function (Bergan, 2004), suggesting that the relationship between academia and society has lost its relevance. The benefits of public engagement strategies that attract funding incentives (Preece, 2016; Byrne, 2016; UKRI, 2019) are tempered by the concerns of academics (Sandmann and Jones, 2019; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) regarding the distinction between their scholarly practice and engagement with civic intervention. Cohen (2019) notes that this could be regarded as a “neoliberal trap”.

The UK *Concordat for Engaging the Public with Research* (VITAE, 2013a) sets out an explicit recognition and reward for research that is linked to public engagement (UKRI, 2019). Arguably, this has motivated HEIs to embed public engagement strategies to step down from the inaccessible “ivory tower” to broaden and democratise their research practices (Preece, 2016; Bergan, 2004; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). It must therefore be considered how these institutions ensure competitiveness in a neoliberal landscape (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018; Marques and Powell, 2019) and how they reconcile civic duty (Cohen, 2019) with research excellence (Marques and Powell, 2019; Martin, 2011) and teaching practice with development for wider engagement (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; UKRI, 2019). McKinley *et al.* (2020) note that public engagement activity in HE is connected to innovation and enterprise, indicating a scholarly recognition of its connection to teaching and research, which they claim is a relatively new area of inquiry. To situate the literature, I examine in this section the background to public engagement in teaching and research at university at international, national and local level.

2.2.1 Deconstructing the ivory tower

The metaphorical term “ivory tower”, which describes the aloof purity of the university as an institution, has ancient roots dating back to the Bible. Although the term was not commonly used in the UK until the post-war era (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015), its contemporary use essentially defines criticisms levied at HE for a level of disconnection, or divorce, from the day-to-day concerns of ordinary lives. In an educational context, the foundations and philosophy of civic responsibility have an ancient establishment. Cicero, a reforming statesman in ancient Rome, outlined his vision for *Res Publica* (Public Matters) and in particular the education of statesmen

within society (Hodgson, 2016). A philosophy that Giorgini (2014) argues has influenced humanist philosophy in education both directly and indirectly, this is reinforced by sociologist Professor Massimo Bucchi (2017), who notes multiple intersections found between science and everyday life practices (Bucchi, 2021), thereby underlining the significance of science communication and impact (Archer *et al.*, 2021; Metcalfe, 2019; Orritt and Powell, 2020; Selin *et al.*, 2017; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

However, the shift in humanism to the modernist approach, or being more *fully human*, as expressed by Freire (2014), is charted by Burdick and Sandlin (2015), who discuss the re-positioning of public pedagogy and post-humanism in the modern era. Boyer, Darder, Freire and Giroux are cited variously as some of the instrumental theorists to deconstruct and challenge the democratisation of education (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Sandlin, Burdick and Rich, 2016; Thomson and Walker, 2010; Sandmann and Jones, 2019). Humanism is transcended by public pedagogy and norms are diffused via non-traditional sites through a process of transfer (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015), which can be bolstered through academic communities (Brennan *et al.*, 2019). In this era, a snapshot of disruptive events has heightened unprecedented social challenges, namely COVID-19, Brexit, Black Lives Matter and the global declaration of a climate emergency (NCCPE, 2020; Ripple *et al.*, 2019).

Internationally, Alcoff (2002) has claimed that, while in the UK and USA public intellectual work can be seen as a sacrifice, at odds with a scholarly identity, in Latin America this approach is valued, aligning with the tenets of praxis outlined by Paolo Freire (Freire, 2014; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019). An explicit articulation is proposed by Freire (2014) of the pressing, political duty of the,

...progressive educator to familiarise herself or himself with the syntax and semantics of the popular groups – to understand how those persons do their reading in the world, to perceive that “craftiness” of theirs so indispensable to the culture of resistance that is in the process of formation, without which they cannot defend themselves from the violence to which they are subjected.

(Freire, 2014)

Preece (2016) and Freire (2014) note that, in developing nations, the socio-cultural role of the university in public affairs is made prominent by heightened injustices concomitant with a myriad of issues arising from political oppression that intersect with pressing human concerns: poverty, crime, disease, hunger and racial divisions. Furthermore, Preece (2016) highlights the fact that, in Africa for example, university education continues to be reserved for a privileged, elite minority despite political positioning to counter social inequity underlining the duty bestowed on HEIs to critically examine their role in society.

In contrast, Scotland, an industrialised nation, has less heightened inequality than the developing world, but some areas suffer significant poverty and deprivation which is markedly iniquitous compared to other areas of the country (Pietka-Nykaza, Leith and Clark, 2020). This accelerated in the 1980s following Thatcherite policies that saw the closure of steel plants, coal mines and shipyards (Leith and Sim, 2020; McGregor and Christie, 2021). The rapid deindustrialisation of the central belt of Scotland has undoubtedly left social, environmental and economic scars (McGregor and Christie, 2021). The socio-economic consequence of this and other inequalities is partly attributed to the educational attainment gap in Scotland (Leith and Sim, 2020; Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019). This is a direct result of deindustrialisation over a period of nearly 200 years.

Historic industrialisation and deindustrialisation has influenced the provision of Higher Education in post-industrial areas, which aligns to evidence presented by Brabazon (2019). In the 18th and 19th Century a systematic depopulation of rural areas of Scotland and Ireland concurrent with times of famine saw the population shift to the central belt of Scotland where the urban population increased exponentially to feed the industrial revolution. As industrial decline began at the turn of the 18th Century after the Napoleonic Wars this adjustment led to the establishment of places of learning. In industrial places such as Paisley where the manufacturing of linen and jute declined the Paisley Technical School (later University of Paisley) was founded in 1897 (Dickson and Speirs, 1980).

According to Brabazon (2019) the consolidation of universities in areas affected by deindustrialisation is rooted in social justice. “Third-tier cities” arise through the confluence of post-industrialisation and the expansion of the HE sectors in a non-

traditional university town. The notion of local citizenship is foundational to the place-making of universities, which disrupts and deconstructs the *ivory tower* (Bank, 2019). These towns are historically working class (Loopmans, Cowell and Oosterlynck, 2012) and, often, have lost their primary industry (Brabazon, 2019). In Scotland for example, Dundee, “jute, jam and journalism”; or weaving in Paisley (Dickson and Speirs, 1980; Leith and Sim, 2020). Third-tier cities are characterised as complex, multi-interest HE spaces, which can generate urban renewal, economic regeneration and strengthened cultural identity (Bank, 2019).

Historically, central Scotland was a highly industrialised society. In Paisley, for example, the period between 1750 and 1845 was dominated by the emergence of a capitalist economy that metamorphosed from agrarian to industrial and was heavily reliant on a single industry – textiles (Leith and Sim, 2020). Concomitant to this were changes in class structure, a segmentation that privileged the weaver with the highest remuneration, while the bleachers and dyers, who were mainly women, were paid the lowest wage. This was only subordinated by the wage of women who had re-located during the Highland Clearances and had only Scots Gaelic as their native tongue (Dickson and Speirs, 1980). These social injustices were highlighted by the *Paisley Mill Girls*, who held the mill owners to account and demanded better pay and conditions – a story re-told in modern times through music in the production *Mill Girls on Tour* (UWS, 2018).

The privileging of artisans meant that Paisley textile weaving was regarded as a highly skilled occupation in comparison to plain cotton or jute weaving, which typically drew Irish immigrant workers. Leith and Sim (2020) designate this type of economic or political migration as the “victim diaspora”, echoed in the re-locations and emigrations of the Highland Clearances. Political awareness of these types of social issues in the early industrial era of Paisley was notably strong amongst the artisan classes, and Dickson and Speirs (1980) highlight the works of Robert Tannahill, a prominent figure, in the reputedly numerous “weaver-poet mould”:

It was a common saying at that time that in Paisley every third man you met was a poet.

Blair (1904) cited in Dickson and Speirs (1980)

Tannahill wrote in both English and Scots dialect after Robert Burns. Burns, the national poet of Scotland, has been recently quoted in a political context – “the rocks will melt wi’ the sun” – referring to the protection of fee-free education for all undergraduates espoused by the Scottish National Party (SNP) (Arnott and Ozga, 2016). Burns’ works contrasts with the “kailyard” genre of literature (Leith and Sim, 2020) (the kailyard, or back garden, is a feature of home life and still referred to in crofting communities, whereby an area of ground is tended to produce vegetables for consumption in the home) – and criticisms levelled at this genre imply that it is too narrow, indeed parochial (Leith and Sim, 2020). Yet post-industrial Scottish identity, which echoes the changes in localised class structures, is underpinned in contemporary popular culture – for instance, through the writing of John Byrne, brought up in Ferguslie Park in Paisley (Elliot, 2018) or the music of Gerry Rafferty (Brabazon, 2019) and The Proclaimers (Leith and Sim, 2020). These are forms of public engagement that are staunchly geographically situated and problematised by depopulation, social immobility, dereliction, environmental pollution and the after effects of de-industrialisation, highlighting a milieu that is distinctly realist and day-to-day. Elliot (2018) describes this as the “...drabness of Scottish quotidian life”.

The subsequent decline and fall of the textile industry in Paisley led to significant economic change and social deprivation in the area (Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris, 2019). By the 1970s, failed interventions to sustain new industries through car manufacturing at Linwood (Leith and Sim, 2020) saw areas such as Ferguslie Park become known as some of the most deprived areas in western Europe (Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris, 2019). According to Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris (2019), public involvement in research underpinned place-based community development in Ferguslie, which they claim “...cast doubt on the monolithic conceptions of the state”. This links to the role of the university in a third-tier city (Dickson and Speirs, 1980; Brabazon, 2019) and aligns with the parallel changes brought about through the public impact agenda, challenging the monolithic constructs of the university (Collini, 2012).

Third-tier universities typically support knowledge transfer projects between universities and industry, which is a key feature of the formation of new graduate knowledge skills (Steed and Gair, 2020). This is particularly relevant to STEM disciplines, given that STEM research impact and funding is recognised as one of five key “assets” of distinction in Scottish HE (Kemp and Lawton, 2013). This is timely, as

the Scottish Government's commitment to a place-making agenda supports the needs of marginalised communities (Mabon and Crawford, 2020), which merits further consideration in the context of teaching and learning in STEM. Historically, the Scottish education system was prized, open to all and egalitarian – synonymous with a distinct national identity (Leith and Sim, 2020; Paul, 2020). Since the election of the first SNP administration in 2007, Arnott and Ozga (2016) articulate a contemporary realignment of Scottish HE framed within a democratic civic national ideology.

The conviction that academic work is a public service has been at the heart of Scottish universities since the sixteenth century (Leith and Sim, 2020; Collini, 2012). Consequently, Scottish academics are in support of the civic role of the university and this is embedded within the governance of academia following Scottish Government educational reforms in 2016 (Leith and Sim, 2020). Yet Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) and Riddell, Blackburn and Minty (2019) point out that, despite government targets for widening access, student intake from the most deprived areas in Scotland remains low. This indicates a failure by Scottish universities to deeply engage with this socio-cultural issue and points to an opportunity for HEIs to embed localised place-based engagement strategies to combat these inequities.

2.2.2 Linking socio-cultural problems with pedagogy in the public domain

The theory of praxis proposed by Freire (2014) highlights links between critical practice and public pedagogy, which Sandlin, Burdick and Rich (2016) characterise as a conceptual lens, drawing on the nexus between learning, culture and social change. The relevance of this concept has been heightened in the twenty-first century by the prevalence and threat of globalised issues defined as wicked problems (Head, 2008). Persistent poverty (Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris, 2019), food security (Sandmann and Jones, 2019), climate change (Cross and Congreve, 2020; Strachan *et al.*, 2019) and, more recently, the COVID-19 pandemic (Schwartzman, 2020) which represent wicked problems and globalised issues that affect all of society. These issues are often contested in terms of their cause, effect and solutions because of the pluralistic nature of modern society (Head, 2008), presenting an ethical challenge to educators (Hoffmann, 2020). Yet there is potential to address these wicked problems, as well as other discrete socio-cultural problems, through public engagement in pedagogy and reflexive practice (Sandlin, Burdick and Rich, 2016; Hoffman *et al.*, 2021).

Literature indicates that several knowledge gaps remain relating to evidence communication, notably the integration of science and environmental communication (Blastland *et al.*, 2020; Davis *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, Obermeister (2020) has claimed that, in the UK, there is a persistently poor integration between scientific knowledge and policy, which can act as a barrier to the disentanglement of problems such as climate change. Environmental communication integrates scientific knowledge with socio-cultural evidence, which Davis *et al.* (2018) claims bridges a gap that traditional science communication strategies cannot, suggesting a need to find equity between the two disciplines. At global level, the United Nations (UN) sustainable development goals (SDGs) present a higher level framework to address complex issues of resource-limited conditions through sustainable development education (Schneider, Avellan and Le Hung, 2019) and public engagement through use of a common language to address complex socio-cultural problems (Shulla *et al.*, 2020).

In Scotland, Strachan *et al.* (2019) make an explicit link between the pedagogical potential of SDGs and opportunities to embed research-informed learning in the HE curriculum. Consequently, Cross and Congreve (2020) and Strachan *et al.* (2019) outline examples of pedagogical interventions in Scotland that go beyond scientific learning and integrate social, environmental and economic aspects through authentic inquiry. Mabon and Crawford (2020) note that Scottish social policy supports a wellbeing economy and participatory action for climate justice. This has strong potential to integrate public engagement within academic practice in this field (Scottish Scottish, 2023). For lecturers, this presents an opportunity to develop pedagogical interventions to integrate science communication with environmental communication for sustainability to support learners in HE to develop practices and habits to address problems through research-informed teaching (RIT) (Moraes *et al.*, 2019).

Mindful of the current significance of climate action and apparent gaps in integration of environmental communication and public communication of science (Davis *et al.*, 2018), there may be a need to elicit deeper understandings of how public engagement affects the teaching–research nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Examples such as vertically integrated projects (VIPs) – projects which integrate research across student cohorts and disciplines (Strachan *et al.*, 2019) – are lauded by Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham (2020) as means to contribute to research alongside critical societal needs. However, the tenuous position of public engagement in the context of

sustainable development is highlighted by Bensaude (2014), who explores the tensions between meaningful communication and buzzwords used for transient impact. This suggests a need to explore pedagogical approaches to understand longer-term impact and resolve fragmented approaches to teaching (Kaasila *et al.*, 2021; Schneider, Avellan and Le Hung, 2019; Schneider, Folkens and Busch, 2018; Archer *et al.*, 2021).

Returning to other problems that impact social mobility in Scotland (Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019) evidence presented by Cross and Congreve (2020) highlights potential areas for further research in relation health (McTavish, 2020) and persistent poverty (Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris, 2019; Pietka-Nykaza, Leith and Clark, 2020). Currently, HE policy is shifting in the UK, recognising a need to demonstrate impact beyond the scope of socio-economics (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016), but there needs to be targeted support to ensure widening participation reaches places beyond academia. According to McKinley *et al.* (2020), there is a need for research in relation to individual academic perceptions of research to make knowledge available beyond the confines of the academy (Clark, 2020; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019). Little is known about the experiences and perceptions of Scottish lecturers in this respect according to McKinley *et al.* (2020).

2.2.3 Measuring public accountability in academia

Throughout the world, HE is largely publicly funded, with some exceptions – for example, private HEIs in Portugal and the USA (Coy, Fischer and Gordon, 2001; Pedro, Leitão and Alves, 2020). Consequently, because of heightened public accountability demands over the last forty years arising from scandals and greater awareness of the public's right to information (Coy, Fischer and Gordon, 2001), it has been recognised that value for money must be demonstrated within HEIs (Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020). This has created tensions in HE, which are widely expounded in current literature. McKinley *et al.* (2020) suggest that a historical lens should be employed to understand the ways in which HE policies have affected the problematised links between teaching and research in HE (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Kenny, 2017; Marques *et al.*, 2017; McCune, 2019; Sutton, 2017). This section explores the history and current policy implications of accountability.

Technical rationality based on analysis of performance metrics in HE (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Spence, 2018) inculcates adopting a positivist worldview to apply a systematic and rigorous approach to scholarship, which Sandmann and Jones (2019) argues can impair dialogic knowledge that is engendered through public engagement. Dialogic approaches to knowledge generation in STEM echo a shift in scholarly practice whereby knowledge transfer is delivered as a deficit model through communication from experts to perceived non-experts (Metcalf, 2019; Braha, 2017; Gani *et al.*, 2024). However, this step-change continues to challenge academics (Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Shulla *et al.*, 2020). Now, knowledge transfer in STEM is repositioned as a dialogical or participatory model, representing a shift from knowledge transfer to knowledge exchange using science communication techniques (Bensaude, 2014; Davis *et al.*, 2018; Metcalf, 2019; Preece, 2016; Schalet, Tropp and Troy, 2020; Menlove *et al.*, 2019).

Neoliberalism is a term used to describe a reaction to collective governance and is claimed to be a tacitly accepted norm in HE, driven by metrics that measure performativity (Kenny, 2017; Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020). The term was encapsulated in 1938 by economists Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich Hayek, who described the essence of a free market economy liberated through entrepreneurial skills and supported by strong property rights (Baird and Elliott, 2018). Critics claim that this is at odds with the rich qualitative landscape of educational impact and academic identity (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018; Pirrie and Fang, 2021)

This raises the question of *who owns knowledge?* Measures of engagement performativity are limited (Lo Presti and Marino, 2019), yet neoliberalism places students as consumers. Potentially this is positive, according to Kandiko (2010), however, he cautions that competition does not always mean an improvement in quality, suggesting that all metrics are problematic (Carter, 2020; Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016; Jovanovic, 2017; Kenny, 2017; Collini, 2012). This has led some universities, such as the University of Utecht in 2023, to withdraw from league table assessments citing doubts on the scoring criteria for ranking (NL Times, 2023).

In Scotland, Kitagawa and Lightowler (2012) posture that there is a divergence between appraisal of research excellence in the devolved nations of the UK, which is

most marked in Scotland. Although there are less formal, voluntary benchmarking awards for HEIs such as the UKRI-led NCCPE Engage Watermark quality scheme, only two have been awarded to Scottish universities to date (Dundee and Strathclyde), representing 20% of the overall awards since 2016 (NCCPE, 2021a). The UKRI requires impact measures for public engagement to be integrated into funding bids through mandatory assessments, including “Pathways to impact” plans and “Impact summaries”, leading to criticism from academics and suggesting the diminution of impact through a “tick-box” exercise (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016; Holliman *et al.*, 2018). As such, these assessments have no longer been a funding requirement since 1 March 2020 (UKRI, 2020a), resulting in a mixed response from the research community (Ma, 2020).

STEM subjects have been the focus of attention in public engagement since the 1990s (Bensaude, 2014; Healey and Jenkins, 2009) and this landscape is changing, not only in the way that information and knowledge is exchanged (Metcalfe, 2019; Taddicken and Wicke, 2020) but also in terms of its transformative impact on the public, particularly in groups under-represented in STEM (Archer *et al.*, 2021; Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Kompella *et al.*, 2020a). Individual excellence can be recognised through academic-led applications (University of Dundee, 2021; Stanley-Wall *et al.*, 2020) or nominations for awards such as the Royal Society of Edinburgh’s public engagement medal (RSE, 2021). Less formal competitions can be led by the third sector, such as the British Ornithologists’ Union science communication awards (BOU, 2021). All lecturers are encouraged to benchmark and enhance individual research excellence for public engagement through adherence to the VITAE framework (VITAE, 2013a; VITAE, 2010a; VITAE, 2015). As such, individual self-assessment for public engagement occupies a liminal space between the formal and informal – potentially impacting identity dynamics (Gregg, Sedikides and Gebauer, 2011; Boncori and Smith, 2019) – and the implications of this are considered in [Section 2.2](#).

Informal recognition of grassroots-led public engagement initiatives that link impact and research in HE has global reach through social media channels such as “X” (formerly known as Twitter and interactivity measures such as re-tweets or comments. These can be utilised as “altimetric” to measure impact or to act as a gauge for public opinion (Smith, 2015; Lim and Lee-Won, 2017; Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019; Beckers and Harder, 2016). Nationally, grassroots-led initiatives can follow a formal process

such as the UK/EU/Asia and African initiative FameLab (Zarkadakis, 2010), although Braha (2017) claims that, in the USA, such awards are few.

Despite the variety of measures to assess public engagement impact, it remains unclear (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020), and a growing paradigm shift has taken place in the landscape of HE, which has created tension between neoliberal organisational decision-making (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019) and the need to engage with the public at student (Bergan, 2004; Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020), policy (Byrne, 2016), industry (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012) and community level (Preece, 2016). Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) and McKinley *et al.* (2020) have claimed that universities construct their identity based on the primacy of research over teaching, highlighting the need to address this imbalance to develop wider research skills for learners in all types of HEI (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016; Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon, 2014). This merits consideration of the boundaries of technical rationality and the civic function of HE (Coy, Fischer and Gordon, 2001). A congruence is suggested by Connolly *et al.* (2020), but such an empirical link has yet to be explored in Scotland, suggesting an imperative to examine existing initiatives to understand how lecturers integrate public impact with research and teaching in STEM (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015; McKinley *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.4 Third spaces for public engagement in STEM

Increasingly, learning has been found to take place outside formal spaces, challenging the traditional function of HEIs (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). Third spaces are defined by Carr *et al.* (2020) as porous, non-formal spaces for learning where power relationships are equal and different identities meet. A social focus for collaborative learning linking popular culture to the HE curriculum (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015) creating relevance and vibrancy in the wider community, which aligns with praxis: i.e., reflexivity and response to real needs in a society (Clark-Taylor, 2017; Freire, 2014). This reinforces the significance of porosity (Preece, 2016) and permeability (Jones, Fawns and Aitken, 2020), which is foundational to third spaces. It echoes Vygotsky's theory of a zone proximal development (Carr *et al.*, 2020; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020) to make an explicit link between a constructivist approach to learning through social processes and interaction.

Face-to-face engagement in third spaces can take place in a variety of ways, settings and physical places, which can act as bridges (Carr *et al.*, 2020) for civic engagement with academia (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). Such dialogic approaches can lead to the enhancement of research and teaching (Walkington, 2015) whereby students, lecturers and the public can work together for socio-cultural change (Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018; Schneider, Avellan and Le Hung, 2019). Third spaces are ubiquitous and lecturers have to be dynamic to react to this opportunity to develop their identities and engage with the public in third spaces, such as social media, integrating research interests with personal interests and experiences (Whitchurch, 2018; Jarreau *et al.*, 2019; Menlove *et al.*, 2019). Watermeyer and Lewis (2015) playfully articulate the depth and variety of public engagement as a “promiscuous strategy, penetrating many specialisms and agendas”, suggesting the elusive and impalpable nature of third spaces that are divested from institutional boundaries.

Digital spaces for engagement have seen exponential growth this century (Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019; Sandmann and Jones, 2019) with the advent of web 2.0, diluting the overall institutional presence of HEIs in non-formal, open, digitally mediated third spaces (Weller, 2011). This has markedly increased following the COVID-19 pandemic, which had a catalytic effect on learning and teaching (Cochrane *et al.*, 2020). Academic blogging, for example, has been established as a popular scholarly practice outside the confines of institutions, stimulating wider public debate and discussion (Heap and Minocha, 2012; Weller, 2018). Blogging engenders a confluence between self-promotion and democratic communication to an undifferentiated public, according to Weingart and Guenther (2016). This suggests that the credibility of communication is paramount to the integrity of blogging as a medium for meaningful dialogue. It can also facilitate an important third space for academic peers through individual or team autoethnography, which can ameliorate academic literacies and reflexivity (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020), creating a dextrous space in which to explore and test conceptual knowledge (Farrow *et al.*, 2020).

Microblogs through the social media platform X enable users to post short message service (SMS) text of 280 or fewer characters. This can be indexed and curated with a hashtag (#) symbol (Clark, 2020). Microblogs have functional similarities to blogs, but tend to provide a synchronous medium for conversation (Smith, 2015) and feedback (Cohen, 2019). This hybrid medium can reach a diverse community of

scholars, peers, politicians, journalists and members of the lay public (Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019). According to Lim and Lee-Won (2017) and Jünger and Fähnrich (2019), this is an established communication strategy within organisations. The dissemination of information directly or automatically through use of microblogging technologies can backchannel information synchronously from events such as conferences (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020; Weller, 2011), with pleasing implications for wider circulation amongst knowledge networks.

Lecturers and academics who use microblogging to connect and share information to linked content (Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019) are also found to form CoPs that can be bound using a hashtag symbol (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020) or via the “@” symbol. This has beneficial impacts for scholarly collaboration in a public arena and is an effective means to curate and collaborate at grassroots level in real time (Johnson *et al.*, 2019; Lewis and Rush, 2013). Given the acceleration and significance of digital spaces in education during the COVID-19 pandemic, there is scope to integrate digital pedagogy through a variety of low-tech mediums to support lecturers, particularly when home-working presents a variety of challenges to delivering teaching practice (Crawford *et al.*, 2020).

The use of image-based or video-based social media sites such as Instagram for engagement has risen in popularity since 2010 (Marcella-Hood, 2020; Weller, 2018) and the active user base of Instagram is now more numerous than that of X (Stuart, Stuart and Thelwall, 2017). Differentiated from narrative platforms, Instagram offers a subjective approach to engagement (Matthews and Djawoto, 2020) measured through *likes*, which are more superficial, requiring less cognitive effort than commenting (Stuart, Stuart and Thelwall, 2017). There is a paucity of literature examining HEI use of Instagram (Stuart, Stuart and Thelwall, 2017) and it is claimed that universities tend to use image-based social media tactically rather than strategically (Carrillo-Durán and García García, 2020). Humanising images were found to be the most common output of UK universities’ Instagram feeds in a study by Stuart, Stuart and Thelwall (2017), who postured that these types of image can lend warmth, humour and amusement to an HEI’s identity.

The same can be said for individual academics, an aspect that could be explored in the context of Scottish identity and humour (Zhang and Pearce, 2020). Jarreau *et al.*

(2019), Marcella-Hood (2020) and O'Donnell (2018) all highlight the impact of Instagram on identity. According to Jarreau *et al.* (2019), “selfies” (self-portrait photos taken using a smartphone to upload to social media) by scientists can build relationships with the public. Finding that “#ScientistsWhoSelfie” are viewed as more trustworthy, competent and approachable, they go further, posturing that selfies can break down gender and race stereotyping.

Communication and creativity through use of cultural imagery draws on the concept of storytelling through contemporary popular folklore (Aaltonen, 2011; Sandmann and Jones, 2019). Drawing on this, Donnelly (2009) discusses an everyday cultural icon, Coca-Cola, in a scene from a post-apocalyptic novel. He notes a commonality of “...understanding is based around the idea of the consumption of one product, instantly identifiable, one name with one meaning”, underlining the mainstream perceptions of everyday cultural icons. In this paper, he describes how the cultural identity of Coke is ironically re-positioned to reflect inauthenticity in a society that no longer places value on consumerism. Similarly, internet memes merge messages with popular icons and can exist as words, videos, hashtags or images (Bucchi, 2017; Beskow, Kumar and Carley, 2020). Memes are valuable cultural units and symbols that can be re-purposed and changed. They are shown to foster familiarity and responsiveness and democratise qualitative academic research methods by reflecting everyday communication (Iloh, 2021).

Political advances in the democratisation of learning have brought about new opportunities for academics to connect with a wider public through a variety of mediums (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015; Canfield *et al.*, 2020). However, Selin *et al.* (2017) note a research lacuna on the political and institutional dimensions of public engagement activities. Given that digitally mediated third spaces have such an impact on the interplay between academia and the public, the COVID-19 pandemic has amplified this phenomenon through the rapid and widespread uptake of OEPs (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020; Havemann and Roberts, 2021). Learners in informal and formal settings were able to come together to create learning communities as needed (Cochrane *et al.*, 2020), underlining the use and potential of third spaces for serendipitous interactions with university learning materials through distribution of OERs (Weller, 2011). Early discourse focuses on the role of the post-pandemic university and how this can be co-located at home and on campus using a

variety of technologies for teaching and learning (Havemann and Roberts, 2021; Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020; Schwartzman, 2020).

2.2.5 Who owns knowledge?

Due to the pluralistic valorisation of knowledge creation (Brew, 1999; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; REF, 2018; Kahan, 2015), it is important to consider which publics (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019) are served by academia, and how this is defined. Nineteenth-century theorists John Henry (Cardinal) Newman and Wilhelm von Humboldt are cited as the founding fathers of the theoretical debate concerning the public duty of the university in Europe (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018; Tight, 2016). While Hazelkorn and Gibson (2018) note that Newman is most associated with the secular reform of contemporary European universities, Tight (2016) focuses on Newman's polarised approach to research and teaching, which he claims has impacted English collegiate traditions, arguably influencing the attendant primacy of research over teaching (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019).

In contrast, von Humboldt is resolutely associated with the foundation and valorisation of public good in HE through linking research and teaching (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). Alexander von Humboldt (brother of Wilhelm) was also renowned in this field, particularly for his abilities to communicate and illustrate scientific research through writing and oration (Schrodt *et al.*, 2019; Frigerio *et al.*, 2021). It is claimed that, in a post-modern era, von Humboldtian values are being eroded by the managerial constricts of academia (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Carr *et al.*, 2020; McKinley *et al.*, 2020; McKenzie *et al.*, 2018), which focus on employability (Wheaton, 2020; Carnicelli and Boluk, 2017), performativity (Spence, 2018) and the primacy of research (Laiho, Jauhiainen and Jauhiainen, 2020). This draws an epistemological distinction between empiricism and enlightenment (Brew, 1999; Brew, 2010; Vohland *et al.*, 2021).

Scientific research illustrated through the written word, spoken word and imagery was fundamental to Alexander von Humboldt's mode of inquiry (Buttimer, 2012). His works included early diagrams and representations of large-scale gradients and ecosystems, which enabled the communication of science through interdisciplinary connections and collaboration with the arts. The complexity and beauty of his diagrams characterise an engaging approach to the communication of scientific ideas that has

endured time and is relevant to predictive modelling. As such, the timeless relevance of his work is evidenced by the presence of his diagrams on the walls of many institutions and public spaces today (Schrodt *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 4: A technical illustration of vegetation in the Andes and neighbouring countries. Source: A. de Humboldt, *Essai sur la géographie des plantes* (1805), *Vème partie* cited in Buttimer (2012).

In Scotland, it is claimed that traditional HEIs are rooted in the constructs and identity of the Scottish Enlightenment (Britton, Schweisfurth and Slade, 2018; Leith and Sim, 2020), which underpinned a nation state through a close connection between society and the university (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018; Ozga, 2020). The Scottish Enlightenment refers to a period of time between the eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries characterised by a surge in intellectual and scientific achievements, when university education was made available to all levels of society (Leith and Sim, 2020). This is a policy stance extant today, distinguishing Scotland from the other nations of the UK, which, since 1998, have charged HE tuition fees (Arnott and Ozga, 2016). Arguably, the Scottish Enlightenment has impacted the universities in Scotland (Arnott and Ozga, 2016). However, the trend towards policy and funding intervention highlights frictions and there are fears that the original view of science as part of the

public sphere means the values of the enlightenment are in danger of being obscured (Vohland *et al.*, 2021).

The Scottish Enlightenment has had a global impact through the influence of the Scottish diaspora (Leith and Sim, 2020), and it is claimed that Humboldtian values impacted the work of Scottish-born naturalist and conservationist John Muir, whose work is deeply connected to the legacy of the Scottish diaspora (Schrodt *et al.*, 2019). The “branding” and “ownership” of knowledge creation in Scotland therefore brings focus on how this is disseminated globally (Swanson and Akdağ, 2018; Withers, 2001), suggesting a need to grant attention to the ways in which scholarly knowledge is created and shared in the public domain. The emergent Scottish Public Engagement Network (ScotPEN) is starting to develop a strategic networked model to distribute public engagement funding from the Wellcome Trust to support STEM engagement between universities, learned societies and informal science organisations. This is likely to have beneficial longitudinal impacts (Archer *et al.*, 2021). Accordingly, the following table examines aspects of public engagement relevant to context and type of engagement.

2.2.6 Socio-economic and socio-cultural factors

UK policy now focuses on democratised research with real-world impact and a discourse of public-facing research linked to public and taxpayer legitimacy (Connolly and Van Der Zwet, 2020). Public value, however, must be recognised within a dimension that has led to new ways of working to determine public policy in Scotland. Citizens’ juries and assemblies, for example, can capture the pluralistic complexity of societal views, but may be “empowerment heavy” (van Der Zwet and Connolly, 2020). Some institutions will situate their research explicitly linked to empowerment within a place-based context (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Carnicelli and Boluk, 2017), which reflects an institutional desire to relate research output to the local community.

The first EU public engagement conference held in Lisbon in 2007 (Bensaude, 2014) cemented its acceptance within EU policy, leading to national HE research reform. The impacts of public engagement on research in the UK were examined in the Stern Review (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016), which has broadened the focus of research excellence criteria (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). Following a

review of the 2014 REF, returns for the 2021 REF assessment case studies were explicitly recommended to include public engagement impacts (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017; Great Britain Department for Business, 2016). Impact is loosely described as “an effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, the environment or quality of life, beyond academia” and the impact aspect of REF scores for 2021 rose from 20% to 25%, which has affected organisational reactivity, capacity and capability to deliver and evaluate impact case studies (Oliver and Fraser, 2020; Baird and Elliott, 2018; Obermeister, 2020).

Activities concerning generation of scientific knowledge through public engagement initiatives, such as citizen science, can have spin-off effects on impact through the formation of legal, economic and socio-ethical knowledge production (Vohland *et al.*, 2021).

Ownership of knowledge has been re-configured following ratification of open knowledge practices, which includes use of OERs licensed using an open copyright licence system developed in New Zealand: *Creative Commons* (Weller, 2011). OERs and OEPs have changed the ways in which knowledge can be produced, co-created, shared and formalised, thereby enabling the democratisation and ownership of knowledge production to be re-configured through licensing (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Weller, 2018). This has accelerated since the pandemic and allowed both students and teachers to “pivot” their educational practice (Havemann and Roberts, 2021). The pandemic enabled science communicators to share information about health that is both conversational and accessible through social media (Yammine, 2020).

Yet as these channels had no gatekeeping, allowing for the spread of misinformation about the pandemic and potentially greater loss of life (McCrea, 2021; Blastland *et al.*, 2020). Evidence communication of both certainties and uncertainties is a well-established practice in medical communication (Blastland *et al.*, 2020) and the pandemic has underlined the importance of communication to de-bunk myths within public perception. There is an understandable hesitancy in public opinion concerning health communication in a world where the medical profession has been discredited through falsified research (Bucchi, 2017). Power dynamics like these shift when universities work with third sector organisations (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017) and there is strong potential for public/private hybrids to displace hierarchies and

provide alternative routes to disseminate information and engage with the public (Ozga, 2020).

Knowledge transfer partnerships (KTPs) between universities and industry are a useful means to develop skills for learners in terms of employability and industry awareness and can generate rich case study data to report impact (Steed and Gair, 2020). This includes a number of factors for social exchange: contract research, consultancy income, income from business or community use of equipment and facilities, income for local, regional development and regeneration, intellectual property income and external income for CPD courses (Kitagawa and Lightowler, 2012). KTP projects can be as short term as ten weeks and last up to three years, enabling businesses to develop additional capabilities or innovations (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012). However, Michels (2020) notes a divergence between top-line reporting of impact and institutional differences, which highlights barriers to innovation in short-term interventions (Marques *et al.*, 2017). Linking HEIs and business through innovation projects (UKRI, 2019) can bring about technological advances and generate additional income for HEIs (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012).

Increasingly, community engagement is recognised as a scholarly practice through dedicated journal publications in this area of focus in a range of languages and open access formats (Sandmann and Jones, 2019). Researcher reflexivity and critical engagement is essential to supporting community-led projects rooted in lived experience, particularly for social justice e.g. domestic violence projects or gendered studies (Berger, 2013; Clark-Taylor, 2017). A push has taken place for the democratisation of research through public involvement and co-creation (Arnott and Ozga, 2016; Carnicelli and Boluk, 2017; Ozga, 2020).

Table 1: Summary of aspects of public engagement with examples relevant to Scottish HE (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017).

	Examples
Political	Place-based governance guides the structural management of universities through the Higher Education Governance (Scotland) Act 2016. The inclusion of students and community members in HEI governance is mandatory (Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020; Leith and Sim, 2020).
Legal	Outcomes for public bodies are linked via the National Performance Framework (SFC, 2019), specifically linking HE funding to national objectives (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018; SFC, 2019). Activism can change the law, e.g. the implementation of a marine protected following public outcry after evidence showed environmental damage from a scallop dredger on the seabed (Burns, Hopkins and Bailey, 2020).
Health	Public involvement in health research is mandatory for grant-funded initiatives, but these projects are claimed to be in danger of being tokenistic or “ <i>tick-box</i> ” (McAteer <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Oliver and Fraser, 2020). The NCCPE analysis by Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017), however, notes a paucity in impact studies from the clinical medicine sector suggesting a disarticulation between academic and applied practice.
Cultural	Links to science and society through cultural collaboration in the arts (Schrodt <i>et al.</i> , 2019) e.g. the <i>Music Planet</i> project at St Andrews University draws the Music Centre and School of Earth and Environmental Sciences together to investigate the relationship between humans and their environment through artistic collaboration (Music Planet, 2021).
Technological	Collaboration through science centres and outreach projects with schools (Clarkson <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; VITAE, 2010a). The Heriot-Watt <i>EnLightenment</i> project worked with the “Our Dynamic Earth” science centre in Edinburgh to provide secondary schools with smartphone microscope kits and associated lesson plans (Wicks <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Societal	Access to university via alternative means can encourage widening participation through provision of outreach and pre-entry summer schools for community-based service learning as module options for undergraduates (Boland, 2014; Healey and Jenkins, 2009), e.g. The <i>Volunteering Academy</i> at UWS (Carnicelli and Boluk, 2017).
Economic	UKRI and REF core funding (UKRI, 2020; REF, 2018) amounts to £1.1 billion from the Scottish Government to HEIs, translating to £7.1 billion of gross value added to the economy, contributing £1.5 billion towards Scotland’s total exports (Universities Scotland, 2017). Scotland’s universities directly employ 42,900 people, which equates to 1.6% of all employment in Scotland, and indirectly support another 142,000 jobs (Universities Scotland, 2017).
Environmental	Citizen science in the SCAPE project, led long-term monitoring of coastal sites (Dawson <i>et al.</i> , 2020). The “Third Generation Project” at St Andrews trained undergraduate students to engage in climate justice curriculum development with Scottish schools (Mabon and Crawford, 2020). The pilot workshops engaged with six schools and delivered a six-week training programme facilitated by students (The Third Generation Project, 2021).

Despite the preceding examples of public engagement in academia, there is frequent reference to knowledge creation in the public realm “beyond academia” in policy documentation. According to Watermeyer and Lewis (2015), this draws a distinction between “specialists” and “non-specialists”. This hierarchy of knowledge creation is “othering”, a term that describes groups excluded from the norms of other social groups. There is significant recognition in social studies that othering adversely affects people through colonialism (Beals, Kidman and Funaki, 2019; Swanson and Akdağ, 2018), ethnicity (Pirrie and Fang, 2021), national identity (Pietka-Nykaza, Leith and Clark, 2020), gender (Bleijenbergh, van Engen and Vinkenburgh, 2012) and marginalisation (Swanson and Akdağ, 2018). Othering in academia is acknowledged as a problematised space (Renwick *et al.*, 2020), where negotiating space to engage the public in research projects - described as “edge-walking” - is important (Beals, Kidman and Funaki, 2019; Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021). An analysis of public engagement in research by Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017) concluded that many REF case studies talk about “the public” while failing to discriminate and make sense of the complex ways in which people engage with research.

Othering affects scientists too. Girkontaitė, Benneworth and Muhonen (2020) note that early career researchers tend to undertake less engagement work than senior academics, highlighting institutional hierarchies that impinge on academic identity, career paths and workload divisions. Cohen (2019) is critical of “milquetoast” engagement from academics who blandly satisfy institutional imperatives whilst failing to engage with the gritty issues of day-to-day life. The impact of engagement within the hierarchy of HEIs (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019) and upon academic identity (Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021) underlines the challenges surrounding the evolving nature of public engagement in research to bring about transformative change (Obermeister, 2020). However, Papatsiba and Cohen (2020) warn that the instantiation of public knowledge creation can be encumbered by powerful actors in the public domain. Consequently, *public good* can be obfuscated by powerful and dominant public interest groups.

2.2.6 Conclusions

From this analysis, common themes emerge that point to opportunities to build the relevance of HE through public engagement by integrating broader societal research activity to develop critical thinking and meta-analytical skills in students (Lazonder and

Harmsen, 2016; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019; Sandmann and Jones, 2019). As such, the significance of public engagement and the impact agenda (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019) is linked to teaching and learning through social processes, characterising the notion of permeability and porosity and constituting Vygotsky's zone of proximal learning (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). This is reinforced by McKinley *et al.* (2020), who note the emerging role of public engagement in the teaching–research nexus is rarely defined (Archer *et al.*, 2021). The relevance of public engagement strategies in relation to the teaching–research nexus in STEM are evident given the changes in the prominence of public engagement within HEIs (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Kinchin and Francis, 2016; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). In the next section this is consequently explored within disciplinary gaps highlighted by Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017) and the institutional hierarchies highlighted by Papatsiba and Cohen (2020).

2.3 Connecting research with teaching in HE through public engagement

The relationship between teaching and research in HE has drawn significant attention since the 1980s and is now identified as a major area of interest in HE scholarship (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; Tight, 2016; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). This is prioritised in the UK through institutional policy (Cross and Congreve, 2020) and performance metrics such as research and student satisfaction league tables (Collini, 2012; Kemp and Lawton, 2013). Consequently, research and teaching are denoted as the core *commodities* of HE (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021). The commodification of these aspects of HE accentuates the ways in which the intersection between teaching and research can be at odds with the vocational nature of the profession (Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021), echoing Brew's assertion that knowledge is in crisis (Brew, 1999).

Connections between research and teaching are often problematic in practice, and McKenzie *et al.* (2018) despairingly portray these as the “end of collegiality”. Research expectations placed on lecturers are stressful (Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018) and academic burnout is commonplace (Wheaton, 2020). Additionally, Empson (2012) problematises the links between research and teaching practice as a knowledge transfer or knowledge production problem. It is claimed that a risk exists of pedagogic

frailty (Kinchin and Francis, 2016), affecting lecturers, particularly when institutional pressures to maintain links between teaching and research heighten these tensions (McKinley *et al.*, 2020) and the added dimension of public engagement can lead to the exploitation of academics (Gani *et al.*, 2024).

This is foregrounded by the precarious nature of funding regimes where research needs overtake teaching priorities (Geschwind and Broström, 2015; Hewitt-Dundas, 2012), following a path predicted by Healey and Jenkins (2009), who described the shift in focus concurrent with the examination of performativity in academia through the 1986 *Research Assessment Exercise* (RAE). They predicted that academics would move away from writing textbooks and teaching-focused material as the superseding REF would perpetuate a funding regime in support of a valorisation of research over teaching. This in turn has reportedly affected career promotion opportunities (Reid and Gardner, 2020; Geschwind and Broström, 2015). Griffiths (2018) illuminates this disparity, noting that the rank of professor is generally awarded solely on the basis of research rather than teaching excellence.

Given the dismal framing of the teaching–research nexus, scholars have questioned the current relevance and significance of universities (Collini, 2012; McKenzie *et al.*, 2018; Munthe and Rogne, 2015). This narrative captures the debates concerning the unique inquiry-driven rationale of HEIs and questions why they cannot simply be replaced by business and innovation initiatives or research labs in the public domain (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). According to Collini (2012), the difference between inquiry driven by an imperative to address an immediate practical problem (such as those encountered in business and industry), and policy-driven research imperatives reveals a tension between the two (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012). This contrasts with “blue skies research” driven by intellectual logic (Collini, 2012) and curiosity aligning with the ethos of the university as a place to generate knowledge (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; McLinden, 2015).

The following section explores this narrative through the ways in which research and teaching are linked in HE and how this relates to public engagement. Aspects of these linkages are explored in terms of the teaching–research nexus (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016). Concepts will be defined and analysed in relation to their constructs within literature, curriculum, practice, policy and funding

mechanisms. The interaction between R/T/Pe will be considered through the disciplinary foci of STEM education to understand how this may affect the experience and practice of HE lecturers in STEM Panel B disciplinary fields.

2.3.1 Exploring research and teaching linkages

The relationship between research and teaching in HE is often problematised as a binary whereby academic prestige is afforded to research over teaching (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018). Furthermore, in the UK, this distinction is widely ascribed to “old pre-1992” HEIs, which identify as research intensive, whereas “new post-92” institutions typically identify primarily as teaching intensive (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). This dualism extends to students, as illuminated in a Scottish study conducted by Briggs (2006). She found that undergraduates who applied to pre-1992 HEIs favoured academic reputation over teaching and vice versa for those students who applied to post-92 HEIs. This indicates that a range of institutional power imbalances and perceptions exist, which are further entrenched by measures for performativity and funding that espouse this paradigm (Sutton, 2017).

The linkages between teaching and research advance a pluralistic approach to knowledge creation (Brew, 1999) and are described as a symbiosis between the two activities. Neumann (1992) (cited in Brew, 1999; McLinden, 2015; Tight, 2016) proposed the concept of the “teaching–research nexus”. This non-directional conceptualisation broadly categorises the bridge between teaching and research (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Jones, 2013):

- i) a tangible, conscious transmission of contemporary research through teaching.
- ii) an intangible connection that promotes critical inquiry that mutually benefits academics and students.
- iii) a global connection that may promote linkages at a departmental level.

The concept is rooted in the philosophy of the Prussian theorist Wilhelm von Humboldt (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020), and Healey and Jenkins (2009) cite this as a key origin from which to build the undergraduate curriculum:

... universities should treat learning as not yet wholly solved problems and hence always in research mode.

— Wilhelm von Humboldt on the future University of Berlin (1810, cited by Elton, 2005, 110)

Wilhelm von Humboldt was assiduously aware of the moral philosophy concerning the intervention of the state and its effects on individual freedom and creativity. He presented a challenging treatise in 1791 – *The Sphere and Duties of Government (The Limits of State Action)* (von Humboldt, 1854 English translation ed. Coulthard) – which explored the bounds of state intervention. The book was not taken on by publishers apprehensive of its critical stance of the state. Consequently, von Humboldt continued to add to the work until his death in 1835 and the manuscript was published posthumously by his brother, Alexander, in 1852. Inevitably, this commentary on the role of the state turns to education, where he postures that, without its interference, “...all the arts flourish more gracefully – all sciences become more largely enriched and expanded...” (ibid., 1854). This ideal undoubtedly informed his plans for the opening of the University of Berlin in 1810:

The relationship between teacher and students will therefore become quite different from what it was before. The former does not exist for the latter, both exist for science. [. . .]

The state, too, must remain faithful to this image if it wants to bring together in a more solid form the inherently undetermined and in a sense accidental activities.

(von Humboldt, 1810)

Despite Tights’ (2016) assertion that von Humboldt’s influence was largely confined to German HE, it is apparent that his ideals have influenced the identity of the modern university throughout Europe (Brennan *et al.*, 2019). Hazelkorn and Gibson (2018) contend that this was a “disembodied, cosmopolitan” public good in comparison to the ecclesiastical approach adopted by Cardinal Newman (Collini, 2012; Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021). Scholarly interest in the conception of the Humboldtian notion of unity between research and teaching continues to grow in the twenty-first century (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021), yet it is often hard to achieve in

practice despite supportive institutional rhetoric, which contributes to this bifurcation (Wheaton, 2020; Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021; Brennan *et al.*, 2019).

The unity between teaching and research (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Yau, 2019) is, in some European countries, foundational to educational policy. Pre-service teacher education in the Republic of Ireland fosters explicit links to research, which Connolly *et al.* (2020) suggest has embedded a previous niche activity into the mainstream of teaching practice both in schools and HE. Arguably, the 1988 Bologna Process, which was instituted to harmonise the quality and comparability of universities in Europe, prompted Scottish HEIs to adopt supporting policies through the quality enhancement framework (Wareham and Trowler, 2007) underpinned by the Dearing review of 1997, which examined the dominant research culture in the UK HE sector (Fanghanel and Trowler, 2008). The Bologna Process explicitly linked teaching and research, reinforced through the *Magna Charta Universitatum* (Geschwind and Broström, 2015), affirming the autonomy of signatory HEIs (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018) and stating fundamental ideals based on the European humanist tradition:

- *The University produces, examines, praises and hands down culture by research and teaching.*
- *Research and teaching must be morally and intellectually independent of all political authority and economic power.*
- *In a contemporary University there should be no separation of research and teaching to meet the demands of society and advance scientific knowledge.*
- *Teachers who are recruited to universities must obey the principle that research is inseparable from teaching.*

(Magna Charter Observatory, 1988)

Laiho, Jauhiainen and Jauhiainen (2020) found that, in Finland, despite a commitment to Humboldtian ideals, “bruising and constricting” managerial demands have meant that teacher identities are often obscured by research demands, which is at odds with the principles of the Bologna Process. The reported disconnect between teaching and research (Geschwind and Broström, 2015; McKenzie *et al.*, 2018; Stappenbelt, 2015) suggests a scarcity of the creativity and individuality espoused by von Humboldt and points to a need for individual academics to become intentional in their work, which

Carter (2020) suggests can be an imaginative and recuperative process. This is reinforced by Dooley (2017), who argues for a humanist approach to science communication. Given that linkages between research and teaching can be multifarious (Brennan *et al.*, 2019), it appears that they are frequently poorly articulated (Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021; Gros Salvat *et al.*, 2020) and sometimes entirely unsubstantiated (Stappenbelt, 2015). This could present an opportunity for lecturers to enrich creativity and individuality through research–teaching linkages (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; McLinden, 2015).

The overlaps described by McKinley *et al.* (2020) in their study of humanities and social science faculties in England and Wales revealed that the nexus only exists in a small selection of specific activities.

No.	Activities	Teaching	Research
1.	Face to face teaching	198	
2.	Online teaching	81	
3.	Preparation	197	
4.	Designing new materials	191	
5.	Formative assessment	171	
6.	Summative assessment	185	
7.	Supervision of dissertations on taught programmes	170	188
8.	Supervision of postdoctoral research students	103	87
9.	Keeping up to date with current research	180	203
10.	Conference attendance	103	182
11.	Public engagement	97	133
12.	Developing new ideas		195
13.	Writing and publishing		195
14.	Working on unfunded research projects		166
15.	Working on funded research projects		141
16.	Applying for funded research projects		151

Figure 5: Academic's perceived overlaps between teaching- and research-related activities from McKinley *et al.* (2020).

The study found that, although academics agreed that an overlap exists between teaching and research, there was significant difference in the perceptions of those working in teaching-intensive HEIs where the linkages identified were less frequent than those working in research-intensive or research-balanced HEIs. Interestingly, the role of public engagement was found to intersect with both activities, which McKinley *et al.* (2020) link to its connection to the innovation agenda (Kitagawa and Lightowler, 2012), suggesting that a split could exist in line with tension in the rationale of the

university, as Collini (2012) has described. This highlights the potential for further investigation of the role of public engagement in the nexus in Scotland and in other fields beyond the humanities and social sciences, as well as in universities with varying levels of research power and intensity (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020).

2.3.2 Research-informed teaching (RIT)

RIT in HE can take different forms and is a term borne out of Griffith's (2004) classification of research–teaching linkages (cited in Brennan *et al.*, 2019), which Healey and Jenkins (2009) further refined. A detailed case study by Edwards *et al.* (2017) outlines the ways in which lecturers ensure these elements of “pedagogic resonance” are embedded and led through research. Although research and teaching are generally accepted as fundamental to postgraduate study (Brew, 1999; Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; McKinley *et al.*, 2020), scholarly discourse reveals particular barriers relating to the foundation of RIT in the undergraduate curriculum (Beckman and Hensel, 2009; Edwards *et al.*, 2017; McKenzie *et al.*, 2018). This review will concentrate on aspects of RIT at undergraduate level to inform the substance of the research questions posed in Chapter one.

Table 2: Typologies of RIT pertinent to undergraduate teaching. Adapted from Edwards et al. (2017).

Research-led (RL): Students learning “about” the research of others.

There appears to be some variation in undergraduate RIT, according to Munthe and Rogne (2015), who observed instances where RIT takes the form of “*students as audience*” through academic reading and writing. However, their study found that, often, textbooks are not regarded as sufficiently up-to-date or research informed, indicating a congruence with the suggestion that academics will move away from writing teaching-focused materials in favour of funded research outputs (Healey and Jenkins, 2009). New ways of disseminating research-informed pedagogy through third spaces (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019) and digital spaces such as blogs and tweet chats can evolve the nexus and enculturate a deeper understanding of RIT between students and teachers (Yau, 2019; Clark, 2020).

Research-oriented (RO): Students learning about research processes.

This involves developing written and oral presentation skills through public engagement to foster collaboration and peer-to-peer support (Chen et al., 2018). Presenting research findings in different ways, both formal and informal, develops multiple modalities for the dissemination of research findings (Beckman and Hensel, 2009; Brennan et al., 2019; Walkington, 2015). Students can gain an understanding of ethical issues in research (Beckman and Hensel, 2009; Edwards et al., 2017).

Research-based (RB): Students learning as researchers.

Students learn how to handle ambiguity in research (Beckman and Hensel, 2009), which fosters metacognitive skills through a cycle of action and reflection on new avenues of inquiry (Ambrose et al., 2010; Smith, 2017). Critical thinking skills are ameliorated through initiative, autonomous thought and self-belief (Joseph-Richard et al., 2021).

Research-tutored (RT): Students critiquing others’ research.

Scaffolded dissemination opportunities (Spronken-Smith and Walker, 2010) can lead to the unbundling of traditional teaching modalities (Connolly et al., 2020). Peer critique of research dissemination fosters confidence for students to share their research findings (Walkington, 2015). Supervisory support in multi-disciplinary innovative pedagogies such as VIPs can originate from staff and PhD students and amongst undergraduate peers (Strachan et al., 2019; Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021).

Scholarship of teaching and learning (SoTL): Enquiring and reflecting on teaching and learning.

A community of scholars (Brennan et al., 2019) can foster von Humboldt’s ideal of the common goal of knowledge creation between student and teacher (McKenzie et al., 2018; McPherson and Heggie, 2015).

These illustrations of RIT in practice suggest that a “one size fits all” approach does not work when trying to articulate its complexity (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Reid and Gardner, 2020). The same applies to multi-disciplinary contexts (Strachan *et al.*, 2019), an under-researched area at odds with the framework proposed by Healey and Jenkins (2009), which “...masks the individual, departmental, institutional and national differences generally found in undertaking research and teaching in specific educational contexts...” (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). Using the teaching–research nexus as a lens for innovation, McKinley *et al.* (2020) propose an enterprise-focused typology following an analysis of the dimensions of the nexus proposed by Wareham and Trowler (2007).

Figure 6: Teaching/research nexus following an enterprise-focused typology adapted from McKinley *et al.* (2020) and Wareham and Trowler (2007).

The enterprise dimension of the nexus is expounded by Lopes *et al.* (2013), who suggest that it could be expanded to include the theory of professions and professionalism. This supplements its relevance to human and social professional fields such as social work and nurse and teacher education (Munthe and Rogne, 2015). Another example of refinements to the nexus within health professions proposed by Jones, Fawns and Aitken (2020) includes the modelling of Bronfenbrenner’s ecological system as a means to situate the scholarship of research-

informed learning and teaching to co-locate real-life research projects within a “bigger picture” (Archer *et al.*, 2021), consistent with Vygotsky’s approach to inquiry-based learning (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016).

Figure 7: Theoretical model of Bronfenbrenner’s research/teaching ecological system from Reid and Gardner (2020).

Reid and Gardner (2020) draw on the theory of research–teaching ecology in the context of RIT, revealing that biology graduates in their study had a positive appreciation of the synergy between research and teaching. According to the authors, this has a significance to undergraduate teaching – they note that graduates are increasingly serving as undergraduate instructors and are therefore instrumental in outcomes for success in undergraduate STEM education. This reflects the recommendations of Healey, Flint and Harrington (2014), who proposed creative partnerships citing a case example of a successful multi-disciplinary course design at

the University of Uppsala one of the foremost research-intensive HEIs in Sweden (Geschwind and Broström, 2015). However, according to Geschwind and Broström (2015), the experience of Swedish lecturers diverges from von Humboldtian ideals, and teaching is perpetually undervalued, particularly in those HEIs classed as research-intensive. This echoes the findings of McKinley *et al.* (2020), who found that, in these circumstances, the nexus will struggle to prosper.

The instability of the unity between teaching and research challenges the tenets of von Humboldt, exposing a tension in the rationale of the contemporary university (Collini, 2012) and presenting practical challenges to lecturers' teaching practices. Academic professionalism, according to Brew (2010), should be evidenced in scholarship, inquiry, attention to detail and rigour. There is CPD (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021), support and training to help lecturers who adopt RIT approaches (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Sharp *et al.*, 2014; VITAE, 2015) through a dialogic partnership with students in line with the UK Professional Standards Framework (UKPSF) (Advance HE, 2011; Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014). Yet the blurring of traditional student/teacher boundaries raises issues of ethical concern relating to ownership, practice and equality when adopting a "students-as-researchers" pedagogy (Smith, 2017; Walkington, 2015) and this must be a key consideration that informs the professionalism of RIT.

The "RIT mindset" elucidated by Joseph-Richard *et al.* (2021) critiques the framework proposed by Healey and Jenkins (2009), cautioning that the mindset cannot be established solely through HEI strategy, funding or policy. They posture that, although the framework orientates the nexus, it is void of any deference to power relations, echoing the findings of a number of scholars who expose the hierarchical nature of RIT and public engagement (Brew, 1999; Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Reid and Gardner, 2020; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020). Sharp *et al.* (2014) found that some lecturers feel inferior if not involved with REF-level research, which is strikingly reinforced in the Wellcome Research Culture Townhalls Report. This highlighted hierarchies that "institutionalise bad behaviour" (Hill and Knowlton Strategies, 2020). A lacuna of empirical evidence regarding the possible side effects of RIT on students and lecturers is illuminated, which may impact professional identity (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). The RIT mindset model seeks to integrate the impact relationships between the UKPSF's five areas of teaching practice with RIT.

Figure 8: The RIT mindset (Joseph-Richard et al., 2020).

This model invokes the pathways to “impact-informed” teaching and engagement linking to the UKPSF’s teaching framework, suggesting that the lecturer is fundamental to embedding the RIT mindset through a variety of pathways including teaching-informed research (TIR). This does not sit alongside policy incentives or funding weighting, which tends to favour research intensity rather than teaching (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020). There is often a partial understanding of these links and they frequently overlap (Brennan *et al.*, 2019), while the impact agenda has insidiously progressed from the RAE to the REF, which appears to disenfranchise the role of the educator. The ways in which impact is measured must therefore be considered in alternative ways (Archer *et al.*, 2021; Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021).

2.3.3 Teaching-informed research (TIR)

TIR describes research informed through teaching practice. Wareham and Trowler (2007) are critical of phenomenological analyses of the teaching–research nexus, arguing for a more dispassionate approach rooted in a theorising framework to illuminate the disentanglement of the two functions. Drawing on these phenomenological findings, the “teaching and learning influences research” dimension posits co-creation between students and teachers and highlights possible dysfunctions that could affect the quality of the resulting research (Wareham and Trowler, 2007). Examples of TIR in practice are scarce (Brennan *et al.*, 2019) and it has received scant attention in scholarly discourse (Charles, 2017) as very few publications present the nexus as a bi-directional causality (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). Stevenson and McArthur (2015) also highlight the reluctance of lecturers to improve teaching at the expense of research and propose that public engagement could be a means to scaffold learning and teaching enhancement in STEM subjects.

Charles (2017) draws on the theories of philosopher Jürgen Habermas to explain how the theory of human capital enables TIR, as sketched in the recommendations of the Boyer report. The Boyer Commission report was issued in 1998 and concerned the experience of undergraduate education at research-intensive HEIs in the USA (Brew, 2010; Healey and Jenkins, 2009). The student-as-creator approach enhances learning and teaching, aligning with the wider academic work of HEIs (McPherson and Heggie, 2015). Key findings from this report bore relevance to the role of CoPs and interdisciplinary collaborations (Matthews, McLinden and Greenway, 2021), suggesting that these aspects of scholarship were essential to improvement in quality (Brew, 2010). Arguably, the critique of elitism in HEIs in the report re-configured the approach to research and teaching, both in America and internationally (McLinden, 2015; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). However, little attention is paid to the experience of the academics engaged in this work (Brennan *et al.*, 2019), suggesting a lack of meaningful discourse focused on teaching practice .

The nuances of TIR are explored by Connolly *et al.* (2020), whose study of a teaching-led STEM CoP in the Republic of Ireland found a fusion between RIT and TIR linking tertiary education providers and schools through a shared educational goal between student teachers, teachers and lecturers. Digital transformation through the use of no-cost access to OER (Weller, 2011) to enhance and extend the impact of research was

outlined as a critical aspect of CoP resources. Drawing on this, the authors cite Penuel (2019), who uses the term “infrastructuring” as a means of scaffolding a CoP to transcend traditional hierarchies. Connolly *et al.* (2020) suggest that this can support a coalescence between RIT and TIR. The innovative potential of this crossover could support “impact-informed teaching”, where the shared goal of research impact is postured as a starting point for classroom instructions (Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021).

Instances of TIR are outlined in outcomes from studies focused on the nexus (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021), demonstrating the fundamental need for student engagement to achieve this inversion of causality from the traditional dominance of RIT (Charles, 2017; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). A dialogic approach to the nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) is outlined in the context of Laurillard’s conversational framework (Connolly *et al.*, 2020), which is a less formalised, teacher-led understanding than the analysis of TIR. Smith (2017) describes the key characteristics in his case study at Liverpool John Moore University’s architectural programme. He asserts the case for “...a journey into an unknown rabbit warren of unanticipated twists and turns...”, echoing the unanticipated findings of Brennan *et al.* (2019) and aligning with the creative serendipity of reflective dialogue (Carr *et al.*, 2020; Gosetti-Ferencei, 2015).

Smith (2017) outlines the naissance of “studio projects” as a student-led, divergent process, citing the work of Doevendans *et al.* (2002), which elucidates the “research of the imagination”, suggesting a parallel to the concept of “blue skies research” (Collini, 2012). Unlike the “impact-informed teaching” model described by Joseph-Richard *et al.* (2021), the “studio projects” method had no set agenda to create a research output. Smith (2017) therefore advocates caution regarding briefs that challenge real-world problems, suggesting that students may have a more developed cognitive process to reconcile imposed boundaries within the creative process. This has implications for the practice of TIR with undergraduates and aligns with the critique of McKenzie *et al.* (2018), who have suggested that the bridge from high school to HE needs to establish cognitive development towards independent research skills rather than prioritising an agenda for original research. The studio projects outline the development of a research question through TIR, but it fails to explicitly foreground the position of ethical consent within the process as Smith (2017) argues that the learning experiences of the project should precede any planned research outputs.

This could present practical problems relating to ethics (Walkington, 2015), particularly if consent to publish students' work has to be sought retrospectively. As such, Smith (2017) recognises the need for a critically informed framework to evaluate TIR projects and identifies other barriers relating to the timeframes associated with student-led projects completed in one academic year as there is no scope to feed into subsequent projects conducted by the same student cohort. This highlights the need to understand that this process can be better embedded into CoPs to identify and support an iterative process for TIR through an RL agenda that interlinks *small and large "r" research* to enact a coalescence between TIR and RIT as outlined by Connolly *et al.* (2020).

2.3.4 Student interaction with the teaching–research nexus

Although this thesis focuses on the experience of lecturers, it is essential to consider how the student experience may affect this (Geschwind and Broström, 2015). The integration of teaching and research is rhetorically favoured by HE policy (Edwards *et al.*, 2017; Grant and Wakelin, 2009), which can reportedly equip students with skills to integrate thinking with decision-making through RIT approaches (Schneider, Folkens and Busch, 2018) and socio-cultural learning (Brew, 1999; Jones, 2013). Its implementation is nascent in the UK (McKinley *et al.*, 2020) and has been bolstered through HE policy in Scotland (Brennan *et al.*, 2019) with a focus on research funding adjunct to HE policy changes (Healey and Jenkins, 2009; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; Walkington, 2015; UKRI, 2020; SFC, 2019; Kemp and Lawton, 2013). This has paved the way to re-configuring student/teacher relationships within HEIs and aligns with findings in the Republic of Ireland, where Connolly *et al.* (2020) have reported support for the integration of research and teaching within institutional policy.

However, this re-configuration reportedly lacks coherence in terms of policy translating into practice, with several barriers to implementation identified in undergraduate teaching cohorts, which can be indeterminate (Munthe and Rogne, 2015) and nuanced (Beckman and Hensel, 2009). It is claimed that, sometimes, staff and student perceptions of the linkages may be misaligned and students may have little awareness of RIT approaches, even when intentionally employed by lecturing staff (McLinden, 2015; Stappenbelt, 2015). There is also a recognition that such an approach to teaching aligns with traditionally research-intensive HEIs (Brennan *et al.*, 2019), with such approaches considered focal to undergraduate and postgraduate learning in Russell Group universities, according to McLinden (2015). Yet there is very little

evidence to illustrate its application in post-92 HEIs, which are typically viewed as teaching-intensive (Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018) and recommendations may try to shift this focus (Sharp *et al.*, 2014; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019).

In contrast to postgraduate education, whereby research-mindedness is expected in the mode and level of study (Brew, 1999), undergraduate students have reported negative experiences when lecturers are too focused on research and do not allow enough time to support them (Tight, 2016; Griffiths, 2018). It is not a straightforward step-change for undergraduate learners to transition from high school to HE (McKenzie *et al.*, 2018) and it can be challenging for lecturers to facilitate this change (Edwards *et al.*, 2017). Undergraduates may typically only engage with research as part of an honours year, if at all, and Griffiths (2018) suggests that very few undergraduate students perceive the symbiotic aspirations of the teaching–research nexus (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Brew, 1999; Jones, 2013). The honours year is a fundamental component of the four-year Scottish undergraduate curriculum (Leith and Sim, 2020) that formally interlinks research and HE teaching (Grant and Wakelin, 2009) and culminates in the production of a thesis.

It is claimed that, although undergraduate research may not produce novel results, it develops metacognitive skills to foster research-mindedness and co-operation between students (Munthe and Rogne, 2015). The benefits of intra-student learning opportunities through research are pinpointed by Brennan *et al.* (2019), who highlight support between postgraduates and undergraduates (McLinden, 2015). These methods align well with the constructivist approaches Vygotsky proposed, enabling co-operative social learning between peers (Erbil, 2020). However, Stevenson and McArthur (2015) assert that, although this theory is palatable to academic developers, this does not always translate in practice. They note that “...the language of such educational theory, while powerful in its underlying message, is often alien and inaccessible to colleagues...”. Healey and Jenkins (2009) suggest four ways to engage undergraduates with research that put a greater emphasis on the role of the student as a creator of knowledge, which explicitly brings the student into a research context.

Table 3: The nature of student research and inquiry relevant to Scottish HE.

RT: engaging in research discussions.

This allows for holistic curriculum development through collaboration (Hoffman *et al.*, 2021), which could develop a programme rather than modular themes through real-life research to address issues of sustainability, such as climate change (Cross and Congreve, 2020). Graduate-led engagement programmes can be used to develop a CoP to teach undergraduate skills in research communication and engagement techniques (Chen *et al.*, 2018; De Clippele *et al.*, 2021).

RB: undertaking research and inquiry.

KTP projects foster collaboration between HEIs and industry to support students in developing research and inquiry skills – for example, in the form of increased levels of resilience and hybridisation through industry collaboration between the Scottish oil and gas sector with art and design (Steed and Gair, 2020), enabling the articulation of research-driven curriculum enhancement through a KTP.

RL: learning about current research in the discipline.

The ecosystem services community (EsCom) is a CoP based in Edinburgh that brought together 600 diverse actors (researchers, policy-makers, practitioners and students), presenting an opportunity for outputs to be shared through public engagement (Metzger *et al.*, 2019).

RO: developing research and inquiry skills and techniques.

Creativity through undergraduate scaffolded inquiry can develop academic research agendas (Smith, 2017) and synthesise research through a public forum (Kahan, 2015). Authentic learning and assessment to enable students to develop skills appears rare in the geography undergraduate curriculum (Cross and Congreve, 2020).

Adapted from Healey and Jenkins (2009)

2.3.5 Crossing the divide: measuring impact in research and teaching

In the UK, research performance in HE was first measured through a Thatcherite government initiative (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Coy, Fischer and Gordon, 2001; Martin, 2011) – the RAE in 1986. Initially developed to clarify the opacity of research block grants (Burrows, 2012), this brought a diversion from a progressive educational movement to a technicist orientation driven by policy-makers (Thomson and Walker, 2010). Today, the impact value of research excellence (Marques and Powell, 2019; Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018) is measured through the REF, which Collini (2012) critiques as a regulatory criteria that promotes “monochromatic discourse”. This stands in the face of an expectation for HEIs to actively promote a research agenda utilising increasingly shrinking budgets (Jovanovic, 2017; McKinley *et al.*, 2020) – a source of consternation, particularly in the UK where teaching and research are funded, evaluated and managed separately (Brew, 2010; McKinley *et al.*, 2020).

In most of the UK nations, additional measures are in place to assess performance through the teaching excellence framework (TEF) and the knowledge excellence framework (KEF) (McKinley *et al.*, 2020). Although these measures have been consulted on, they have not been adopted in Scotland (Universities Scotland, 2019) and Ellis, Souto-Manning and Turvey (2018) suggest that the attendant endorsement of evidence and econometrics as a measure of teaching quality will lead to the disenfranchisement of students and teachers. They go further, suggesting that the impact agenda encultures the dehumanising of teaching, aligning with critiques posed by Collini (2012). Although Watermeyer and Lewis (2015) point out that academics are accustomed to accounting for their activity, there is a recognition that the HE landscape has consequently become fragmented, through pressures on lecturers to perpetuate a connection between teaching and research in daily practice (McKinley *et al.*, 2020) alongside public engagement (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020).

The Stern review of the REF framework in 2016 enacted a greater focus on public engagement as an impact measure of research (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016), disrupting the perceived ivory tower culture by bringing a focus onto the ways in which research impacts non-academic lives (Tilley, Ball and Cassidy, 2018). There is a chasm between neoliberalism and public pedagogy, according to Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth (2019), which highlights the tensions that may arise

when trying to assess impact measures that do not focus solely on socio-economics, as per Lord Stern's review (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016). Certain academic disciplines are arguably further polarised in the depth and complexity of public engagement impact, according to an NCCPE analysis of the 2014 REF by Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017).

Figure 9: An analysis of REF case studies that refer to engaging with the public as a proportion of the total submitted case studies from Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017).

Their assessment found that only 47% of the 2014 REF case studies referred to public engagement and there was distinct disparity between the incidences and ways in which engagement was reported between the arts and humanities compared with certain scientific disciplines such as medicine and public health. The 2021 REF recommendations explicitly linked impact to HE funding (REF, 2018). On one hand this can promote an imposed focus on competitive research output through engagement with the public to sustain budgets (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015), which may make the teaching/research nexus precarious. This can be further complicated when funding regimes are consolidated by an agenda to attract international students, according to Collini (2012). However, Kemp and Lawton (2013) underline the importance of this aspect of Scottish HE. Scotland hosts the highest proportion of international students in the UK, contributing to its overall economic output, which draws focus on the effects of power relationships created through the marketisation of publicly funded education (Swanson and Akdağ, 2018).

Papatsiba and Cohen (2020) found that these power relationships are often attributed to the most prestigious HEIs (Tier 1 and 2), which are over-represented in sampled REF impact case studies. In contrast, Tier 3 and 4 HEIs were under-represented and tended to return REF impact reports focused on “coalface” or “frontline” sector-level practice, suggesting a lessened ability to influence the shape or direction of national policies. Despite these power imbalances in Scotland equality of access is a key focus for policymakers (Arnott and Ozga, 2016). Scotland, since 2010 is the only nation in the UK to offer free HE undergraduate tuition for Scottish domiciled students and the modern civic identity of Scotland is politically embedded as a learning society. A distinction is made between public funding gaps for teaching and research (Universities Scotland, 2017), indicating a shortfall in research funding, which supports the view held by Brew (2010) that the teaching–research nexus is not always supported holistically through funding mechanisms (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Healey and Jenkins, 2009).

McKinley *et al.* (2020) note that HEI identity is categorised pluralistically but essentially framed within the binary of research- or teaching-intensive. However, other categorisations are presented as follows:

Hewitt-Dundas (2012) denotes four distinct HEI groupings in the UK:

- The Russell Group
- Post-92
- Post-94 (now dissolved)
- Specialist universities focusing on research and education: e.g., vocational, technical

Papatsiba and Cohen (2019) categorise identities according to the categorisation used by Boliver (2015):

- Tier 1 and Tier 2: all pre-92 HEIs
- Tier 3 and 4: all post-92 HEIs

In Scotland, Briggs (2006) pinpoints three distinct HEI identities:

- “Ancient” universities – those founded before 1600
- 1960s, or “redbrick” universities
- “New” universities – those given university status under the 1992 Further and Higher Education Act

There are nineteen Scottish universities (Leith and Sim, 2020), ranging from the oldest – St Andrews, the third oldest university in the English-speaking world (University of St. Andrews, 2020) – to the newest – the University of the Highlands and Islands (UHI), which gained university status in 2011 (UHI, 2020).

Table 4: Categorisation of universities in Scotland.

Name of HEI	Ancient	1960s	Post-92	Post-94	Russell	R&Ed.
Abertay University *			Post-92			
University of Aberdeen	Ancient					
University of Dundee		1960s				
University of Edinburgh	Ancient				Russell	
Edinburgh Napier University *			Post-92			
University of Glasgow	Ancient				Russell	
Glasgow Caledonian University *			Post-92			
Glasgow School of Art						R&Ed.
Heriot-Watt University		1960s				
UHI *			Post-92			
Open University in Scotland		1960s				
Queen Margaret University *			Post-92			
Robert Gordon University *			Post-92			
Royal Conservatoire of Scotland						R&Ed.
Scotland's Rural College						R&Ed.
University of St Andrews	Ancient			Post-94		
University of Stirling		1960s				
University of Strathclyde		1960s				
University of West of Scotland *			Post-92			

(*) denotes the "million plus" modern universities (Million Plus, 2020). Adapted from (Universities Scotland, 2020; Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; Briggs, 2006).

The four “ancient” universities extant in Scotland are traditionally viewed as research-intensive, scholarly institutions (Briggs, 2006). The more modern, technical and vocational institutions are, meanwhile, associated more often with practical teaching rather than research. Research intensity, it is claimed, bounds the traditional foundations of knowledge construction and scholarship (Sandmann and Jones, 2019; Alcoff, 2002). Matters of human capital and day-to-day practice are perceived to be associated with lower research intensity HEIs (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020). Yet there is a pressing and unresolved mandate to embed the role of HEIs at the heart of human experience in cultural and community settings (Preece, 2016; UKRI, 2019; Freire, 2014; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019) and this is further strengthened by policy (Ozga, 2020; Arnott and Ozga, 2016; Paul, 2020).

A categorisation that Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) expound presents three types of organisational identity at Scottish universities in relation to undergraduate admission policies:

- The globally competitive university
- The nationally selective university
- The locally transformative university

They note the disparity of access to HE between school leavers from affluent Scottish households, who are three and a half more times likely to enter HE than students from the lower centiles of the Scottish index of multiple deprivation (SIMD). Moreover, competitive, highly selective HEIs are five times more likely to select undergraduates from affluent backgrounds, which the authors found could be linked to the organisational identity of HEIs, representing a barrier to progressive admissions policies. However, Riddell, Blackburn and Minty (2019) point out that, despite political interventions to improve access to HE, the absence of undergraduate tuition fees in Scotland does not appear to have had an impact on widening access. These studies expose aspects of critical engagement central to the framing of HEI identity in terms of the teaching function of universities in relation to the pressing social issues extant in Scotland (Pietka-Nykaza, Leith and Clark, 2020), which Ozga (2020) cites as an essential element of Scottish educational policy debate.

There is a need to understand the ways in which teaching and research linkages can be configured to underpin the civic duty of the university (Boland, 2014; Clark-Taylor,

2017; Preece, 2016; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015) and the ways in which this may link to Scottish HEI identity. Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) note the perceived importance of hierarchy in terms of global, national and locally competitive HEIs as a barrier to widening access, yet this is arguably at odds with the primacy of civic function over neoliberalism, which is the thrust of current Scottish education policy (Arnott and Ozga, 2016; Leith and Sim, 2020). REF is a blunt instrument (Collini, 2012) delineated by accountability that fails to account for social reconstructionism and authenticity (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016), which is central to the teaching–research nexus and indicates an avenue for investigation of Scottish HE in this context (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020; McKinley *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.6 Engaging with STEM at the teaching–research nexus

The neoliberal university has a public duty articulated through a variety of institutional, political and public sources, which has drawn particular attention in STEM education (Davies, 2020) where public dialogue has become a leading concern for over two decades (Davis *et al.*, 2018). There is increasing focus on the marginalisation of specific groups in STEM (Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021; Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Jarreau *et al.*, 2019; McKinnon and O’Connell, 2020) through “othering” (Said, 1978 cited in Swanson and Akdağ, 2018). The notion of othering is evident in the stratification of public intellectual work outlined by Alcoff (2002), who expounds the hierarchical complexity of the ways in which academics interact in the public sphere, linking to power relations and structural inequalities identified in STEM (Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021).

The colonisation and carbonisation of the STEM curriculum has drawn scrutiny (Cross and Congreve, 2020) that now extends beyond the field of edge-walking (Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021) and grassroots activism (Davis *et al.*, 2018) to develop capacity through public engagement with science (Selin *et al.*, 2017). Pedagogical intervention is considered fundamental to social justice and transformation narratives (Seatter and Ceulemans, 2017), which underpins the relevance of real-world research and public engagement to undergraduate teaching in STEM (Archer *et al.*, 2021; Davies, 2020; Pegrum, Bartle and Longnecker, 2015; Weitkamp, 2018).

Public communication of science and technology has been foregrounded by an approach to science research and education encultured through what is defined as a linear, non-dialogic deficit model of communication (Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon, 2014; Taddicken and Wicke, 2020; Metcalfe, 2019). The evolution of public understandings of science is charted by various authors, revealing a longitudinal trajectory. For example, the first printed instance in renaissance Italy originated in 1682 with a publication that urged the importance of being competent in both physics and cookery (Bucchi, 2021), or, in eighteenth century England, the storytelling and poetical prowess of eighteenth-century Cornish chemist Sir Humphrey Davy (Illingworth, 2019) and nineteenth-century Dutch conjurer and science populariser “Maju”, who wowed his crowds with circus-like performances (da Rocha Goncalves, 2020). A plethora of emergent cultural references frame the unravelling of the public communication of science throughout history, but only relatively recently have the modes and methods for communication been the focus of scholarly attention (Braha, 2017; Davies, 2020; Hawley and Ocobock, 2020; Trench, 2008; Callahan and Rosser, 2016; Illingworth, 2020).

Despite institutional rhetoric that indicates a shift from a one-way deficit model of communication to dialogic discourse in STEM, a lacuna of evidence supports this (Metcalfe, 2019; Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon, 2014; Selin *et al.*, 2017). This suggests a need to align public engagement with participatory communication practices to step beyond the emic/etic divide (Beals, Kidman and Funaki, 2019). Typologies to integrate different aspects of science communication draw on multiple socio-cultural intersections (Bucchi, 2017; Trench, 2008): philosophy, psychology, linguistics, sociology, humanities, communication and political science (Metcalfe, 2019). The orientation of science communication within the public sphere is illustrated in Table 5, ordered in an ascending hierarchy to represent the shift in power from scientists to the public (Metcalfe, 2019).

Table 5: An analytical framework to delineate modes of science communication and the public sphere.

Model		Values		
Communication	Method	Worldview	Role	Orientation of science towards the public
Deficit	Dissemination	<i>Settler*</i> Positivist Scientism Technocratic Accountability Promotional	<i>Pure scientist*</i> Defence Marketing	Othering “They are hostile, ignorant. They can be persuaded.”
Dialogue	Consultation	<i>Prospector*</i> Pragmatist Constructivist Instrumental Democratic	<i>Communicator*</i> Contextual Consultation Engagement	Emic/etic, i.e. insider/outsider “We see their diverse needs. We find out their views.”
Participation	Conversation	<i>Pioneer*</i> Participatory Relativism Cultural Transformative	<i>Issue advocate*</i> Deliberation Critique	Edge-walking “We invite. They and we set the agenda. We share meaning. We negotiate.”

*Professional roles that scientists adopt during their careers and the values they assign to these roles are set out by De Clippele *et al.* (2021) and denoted in italics.

Adapted from Beals, Kidman and Funaki (2019), Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah (2021), Davies (2020), De Clippele *et al.* (2021), Metcalfe (2019) and Trench (2008).

More recently, the STEM landscape has shifted from policy to raise scientific awareness and literacy levels (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015) to an impact agenda consequentially funded and assessed through REF impact case studies (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020) to measure the "...effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, the environment or quality of life, beyond academia" (REF 2019 cited in Obermeister, 2020). This definition highlights that students, peers and institutions, as well as end-users of research, are intermingled within the definition of "public" (Collini, 2012; Sandlin, Burdick and Rich, 2016), thus reinforcing the civic duty of the academic community that they serve, comprising a variety of actors sitting outside institutional boundaries (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015; Lo Presti and Marino, 2019; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020). This suggests a "commodification" additional to the commodities of research and teaching, as pinpointed by (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021).

Public engagement is a commodity linked to teaching and research and literature reveals barriers that separate experts from their public communities to develop critical awareness (Selin *et al.*, 2017). An enabler for this work is found through the purposeful interrelation of scholarly interests with the day-to-day concerns of ordinary people (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015; Bucchi, 2017). Authenticity and passion for a subject allows lecturers to step in to an identity (Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021) that can significantly affect the aspirations and scientific identity of the students they teach (Archer *et al.*, 2021; Cross and Congreve, 2020). Furthermore, it is evident that scientists may have anti-positivist, arts-based side identities (Illingworth, 2019; Matthews and Djawoto, 2020) in music (Gordon and Lense, 2020; Newstalk, 2020) or performance, for example (Roche *et al.*, 2019), which help inform these roles and develop novel methodologies (Boal, 2005; Davidson, 2021; Allen, 2018; Dixson, Chapman and Hill, 2016) to deepen connections with their audiences.

Identity and trustworthiness is foundational to public engagement and impact (Jarreau *et al.*, 2019; Hawley and Ocobock, 2020), which can positively affect cultural perceptions of the "other" (McKinnon and O'Connell, 2020). A disentanglement of public identity through "...knowing what's known by science and being who they are..." prevents polarisation of opinion by affirming, rather than denigrating, cultural identities, according to Kahan (2015). The need for this deference has been evident in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, with the communication of science a vital vehicle to

counter misinformation concerning the intersection between public knowledge of virus spread and immunology with social, political and economic concerns (Hood, 2020; Newstalk, 2020; Yammine, 2020; Kerr, 2021).

Crisis can act as a catalyst, and, as research about the pandemic became openly available online in public spaces, the same happened for education. Havemann and Roberts (2021) observed that this pushed educators to become digital pedagogues as a result, but they observed that the period following the initial crisis, mid-pandemic – or the “new normal” as it was often referred to – was regarded by many as a temporary “workaround” for many lecturers. As Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth (2019) have underlined, a well-defined polarity exists between HEI leadership and technology adoption, generally regarded as different domains of expertise and responsibility. The COVID-19 crisis forced a closer relationship between the two functions and, arguably, the lockdowns became an enabler to integrate OERs into the “new normal” (Schwartzman, 2020; Crawford *et al.*, 2020).

Concomitant to the public health crisis during the pandemic is a continuing narrative concerning the climate crisis in Scotland (Mabon and Crawford, 2020). In 2019 Scotland became the first country to officially declare a climate emergency (Ripple *et al.*, 2019). Climate change, and, similarly, COVID-19 are contested “wicked problems” (Blastland *et al.*, 2020; Mabon and Crawford, 2020) because of their multifarious permutations of cause and effect and their global and ubiquitous consequences (Cross and Congreve, 2020; Head, 2008). The literature reveals a gap in understanding about how these issues are captured within curricula through the sustainability imperative (Schild, 2015; Seatter and Ceulemans, 2017). Some examples in practice have used real-world research to support HE teaching and learning with public outreach in STEM, although these are often piecemeal in provision when they are one-off or brought in for a specific project, and there is a need to embed this practice into longer-term projects (Archer *et al.*, 2021).

It is therefore timely to situate these educational issues within an analysis of the public communication of science during a time of pedagogical disruption brought about by the sudden shift from traditional modes of face-to-face teaching to hybrid and remote learning via digital means during the pandemic (Anderson, 2020; Crawford *et al.*, 2020; Fuller *et al.*, 2021; Schwartzman, 2020). The pedagogic pivot (Farrelly, Suilleabháin

and McCarthy, 2020) has illuminated attention on the emerging use and distribution of OERs in teaching (Nordmann *et al.*, 2020), which may have positive lasting benefits in co-locating the teaching–research nexus in digital spaces that are publicly and openly available (Connolly *et al.*, 2020; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019). Jünger and Fähnrich (2019) define the assessment of the quality and popularity of these spaces through *altimetrics*, which indicate reputation through public visibility and research outputs (Smith, 2015). They note the role of communication scientists as public bridge builders, but they also suggest that engagement in digital spaces is not always clearly defined and it is necessary to embed community-orientated strategies to support public research engagement in HE (Lo Presti and Marino, 2019).

2.3.7 Research gaps

Little research in Scotland has investigated the scholarly processes that link R/T/Pe at undergraduate level (Walkington, 2015; McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Archer *et al.*, 2021). An investigation of these links is timely given the emergent network models for engagement that are developing in Scottish HE (Archer *et al.*, 2021), suggesting a need to understand how academics experience and integrate research into STEM undergraduate teaching through the teaching/research nexus (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Such an examination yields insight into the ways in which academic practice is re-configured by individuals to exemplify a synergy in the triple nexus to invoke an *impact identity* which links to the aims of this study (Menlove *et al.*, 2019).

To understand the approaches that lecturers employ to integrate the triple nexus into STEM teaching the following questions and sub-questions are proposed to examine aspects of the study in relation to theory and teaching practice within a range of HEIs in Scotland (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018; Mertens, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

R1: How do STEM disciplines in Scottish HE make integrative links between public engagement, research and teaching at undergraduate level?

R1a – How do the linkages between research, teaching and public engagement affect the lecturer’s experience and practice in those disciplines defined as STEM Panel B within the REF?

R1b – Are there similarities and differences in institutional identity in relation to the demands of teaching, research and public engagement?

R2: Does this activity align to Humboldtian ideals, and how is knowledge generated accordingly?

R2a – Can von Humboldtian ideals link research and teaching with public engagement?

R2b – Does this form of scholarly practice hold a greater relevance to the creation of knowledge and re-configuration of teaching in the post-pandemic university?

2.4 Summary

This chapter has explored the literature concerning R/T/Pe in HE finding that although universities are purported to be founded on Humboldtian ideals (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Collini, 2012; Geschwind and Broström, 2015; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021), the conceptions are nuanced (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). Education is, by its very nature, highly politicised – it has multiple stakeholders, is a consistently prominent part of local and national government policy, and is therefore fundamentally driven by public accountability (Punch and Oancea, 2014). It appears that the concept of unity between research and teaching could be under threat at best, or, at worst, unstable. This suggests a need to examine the perspectives of academics to gain better insights into their practices, therefore a phenomenological approach will be used to explore the research questions in the following chapter.

Chapter 3: Research methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter sets out the ontology and epistemology for this study. The rationale for the chosen methodological selection is outlined, including the theory, methods and research approach employed. The stages and order of the research process are set out in terms of sampling, data collection and data analysis to ensure transparency, consistency and clarity of methods employed (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Finally, the practicalities of data collection and ethical implications are explored in the context of researcher positionality and methodological selection.

3.2 Rationale for methodological selection

The overarching aim of the study was to explore the lived experiences of lecturers in Scottish HE to gain insight into their teaching and research in STEM Panel B subjects and how they balance this with public engagement (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017). The triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) was used as an analytic lens for this study to connect with emergent “educational ideologies” rooted in Humboldtian ideals (McKinley *et al.*, 2020). According to Creswell (2014), it is therefore important to pinpoint the audience of the study to inform the methodology. The study thus aims to generate a valid analysis with potential to be beneficial for HE lecturers, HE researchers, educational developers, HEI management, policy-makers and public engagement professionals (PEPs) in STEM (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021).

3.2.1 My ontological stance

The ontology, or assemblage of reality, within this qualitative study is based upon the premise that material circumstances will be encountered during the research process (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). It is important, therefore, to consider how the impact of my past research experiences and discipline orientations may affect this, together with the culture and inclinations of the supervisory team (Creswell, 2014). Ontology, which is described as the “...science of being” by King, Horrocks and Brooks (2018), suggests that human behaviour is shaped by these realities. These can be further distilled within the theory of existence as realist or relativist positions. It must be recognised that a diverse community of scholars will approach research using concepts aligned to their discipline and training. Although I have a positivist background as an undergraduate

in agricultural sciences, my ontology as an educational researcher is distinctly qualitative, which supports the collection of rich data.

Different methods that were considered could have looked at educational statistics, or measured impact case studies and associated REF reports, for example (Cohen, 2019). However, the primary aim of the study was to encapsulate common experiences and generate a rich view of lecturers' perspectives. A relativist approach within phenomenology was therefore adopted (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020). This approach prompts a recognition that individual and cultural influence cannot be set aside from the research (Farrow *et al.*, 2020; Mertens, 2020) or used to cloud the findings through conscious or unconscious bias (Klein, 2012). Using lived experience as a primary data source acknowledges that human realities are multiple and socially constructed, underlining the central understandings of positionality that shift between fore-understandings and findings (Creswell, 2014). An interpretative approach exists at macro- and micro-level in phenomenology (Pitard, 2015), which tantalises the researcher to uncover the "natural attitude" of the phenomenon being investigated (Starr, 2014). As a qualitative approach was used to explore lived experience, a positivist approach to examine impact case studies in relation to the triple nexus is thus indicated as an area for further research ([see Section 6.1](#)).

The debate surrounding the bifurcation between realism and interpretivism is arguably at odds with some aspects of phenomenology, which is explored in more depth in the following section. Robson (2011) postulates that this divide is a common preoccupation in philosophically grounded methodologies such as phenomenology. He suggests that a pragmatic approach, whereby moderate social constructionism can align with realism, to reconcile the debate. Braun and Clarke (2006), who note the often-implicit framing of thematic analysis within phenomenology, also explore this, describing the subjective, relative "...experiences, meanings and the reality of participants". However, they acknowledge that the method can sit on a spectrum of relativism and realism and, as such, the subjectivity of such an analysis is inescapable (Braun and Clarke, 2020).

Literature suggests that a polarised approach to the realist/relativist stance is unjustified, particularly given the historical context of HE in terms of its social constructions and its political and professional contexts (Punch and Oancea, 2014;

Wood, Farmer and Goodall, 2016). As Ellis, Souto-Manning and Turvey (2018) suggest, a quantitative assessment of teaching can be dehumanising, and theory can be “violent”, according to Ball (2006). This study aimed to uncover the human side to lived experience and interpret this within education studies from a humanist perspective, meaning that a quantitative or mixed-methods approach is not appropriate (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015).

Eatough and Smith (2008) draw attention to the “always-unfinished” nature of interpretivism. Based on the above discussion, this must be acknowledged within the methodology as a gap that cannot be reconciled, rather mitigated, through an acceptance that there will be avenues for further research, identified during the study ([Section 6.1](#)). Throughout the study, I adopted autoethnographic methods to mitigate this aspect of “unfinished” work, affirming and accepting my subjectivity during the research process (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010; Kmita, 2017). According to Empson (2012) and Lapadat (2017), autoethnography sustains a closer dialogical contact between the researcher and practitioners (lecturers) to enact the co-creation of knowledge, whereby personal experience can be compared and contrasted with cultural understandings, existing research and research interviews (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Autoethnographic reflections were therefore shared with participants to embed intentional, critical reflection in the methodology and understand researcher assumptions, biases and preoccupations (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Lapadat, 2017).

3.2.2 Epistemology

Qualitative research uses methods typically adopted to understand complex, socially constructed norms (Nolen, 2020). As such, this approach was used alongside a theoretical lens or perspective to orientate data gathered relating to the behaviour and attitudes of people and their interactions with cultural and social constructs (Creswell, 2014). The process of evaluating knowledge statements in this study is guided by phenomenology to articulate the values of research study participants (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). The reported lacuna of empirical studies in the triple nexus therefore favours an interpretative methodological approach that elicits rich descriptive detail able to be achieved using phenomenology (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Sloan and Bowe, 2014).

The rationale for this methodological choice sits within social constructivism – the primary objective to place reliance on participant views of the situation being studied (Creswell, 2014). Given the indefinite and nuanced conceptions of the teaching/research nexus in HE and the lack of research, definition and discussion in Scotland, there is scant basis on which to propose a quantitative approach (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). Wareham and Trowler (2007) contend that a pure phenomenological analysis is most appropriate as a means of collecting singular, phenomenon-specific data. Pure phenomenology is an idiographic approach, whereas this study aims to give insights into the ways in which a given person in a given context reacts to, or understands, their social reality, meaning that an interpretative approach to phenomenology is best suited.

Notably, multi-layered perspectives surrounding the emergent research into public engagement align closely with the theoretical constructs of phenomenology, aiming to elicit, report and make sense of variations amongst socially constructed concepts previously undefined (Sin, 2010; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). In order to determine the selection for this methodology I considered the practicalities of the study together with the theoretical appropriateness (Creswell, 2014; Mertens, 2020). Importantly, a distinction must be drawn between phenomenology (where patterns are observed and commonality of experience is reported) and phenomenography (where the *variation* of experience is the focus) (Farrow *et al.*, 2020).

Phenomenology is a robust social science methodology that offers an account of human existence, whereby a subject or phenomenon (the R/T/Pe triple nexus) is understood culturally and socially (Zahavi, 2018). This is generally considered idiographic – offering a detailed account concerned with specific social settings, relationships or processes (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Zahavi, 2019). Although Zahavi (2018) notes that phenomenology is usually applied to anthropology, sociology, psychology, literary studies and education, King, Horrocks and Brooks (2018) drill deeper into its use as an interpretative research method in practice-based disciplines, notably education and health.

Interpretative phenomenology is widely used and accepted in education studies and applicable to STEM, according to Han and Ellis (2019), whereby a close examination of individuals' lived experience in specific settings provides a pragmatic approach to

understanding the human condition, without resorting to abstract theorisation on “human nature”, which risks the danger of “experts” imposing their own theories upon the study’s participants (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). This aligns with Creswell (2014), who points out that, aside from discipline orientations, worldviews arising from a researcher’s past research experiences or from mentors’ or student advisors’ inclinations must also be accounted for.

A mixed-methods approach was considered given the pragmatism of actions, situations and consequences within practice-based education settings (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018; Mertens, 2020). The “reality” of this phenomenon can be more readily understood through a descriptive account of individual experience, rather than attempting to build an abstract theoretical understanding of the issues (Charles, 2017; McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Reid and Gardner, 2020). It is understood that lecturers are susceptible to tortuous identity conflict between the demands of teaching and research and this deserves an individualised focus to develop a better understanding of this (Kinchin and Francis, 2016; Empson, 2012). More recently, academic identity conflict has been co-located with an implicit institutional expectation for lecturers to take part in some form of public engagement that can add to a perception of work pressure (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Notably, Watermeyer and Rowe (2021) maintain that public engagement is now an imperative for lecturers. Despite this, public engagement is put to one side of a university’s mission and, in some cases, viewed by university management as a third mission, outside the scope of core scholarly activity. Yet, the impact agenda enables greater scope for access to research funding if linked to specific public engagement activity (Ma, 2020; UKRI, 2020a; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). It appears that the subsequent repercussions of this culture change are infrequently explored through the perspectives of lecturers (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016). The methodology therefore elicits a phenomenological analysis of lecturers’ common and unique experiences surrounding these phenomena.

The precepts of phenomenology are given by Han and Ellis (2019), Mertens (2020) and Sloan and Bowe (2014), linking the classical philosophical theorists of the early twentieth century – Husserl and Heidegger – to later theorists – Sartre and Merleau-Ponty. Mertens (2020) outlines the development of theory with reference to

researchers who initiated the use of phenomenology to conduct contemporary studies in education and psychology. Specifically, Moustakas (1994), cited in Mertens (2020), is regarded as the first to introduce this approach into the research world, thereby bringing research focus to the subjective experience of individuals. In turn, this is determined by the phenomena of experience (Sloan and Bowe, 2014). At first glance, the use of phenomenology appears at odds with scientific inquiry. This was, indeed, the intention of Edmund Husserl, regarded as the founding theorist of phenomenology (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Zahavi, 2018).

Husserl created a new relationship between philosophy and science as a direct challenge to Cartesian philosophy (Sloan and Bowe, 2014; Eatough and Smith, 2008), and Zahavi (2018) observes that, although his theory presented a challenge to the traditional tenets of positivism, it should not be critiqued as a form of philosophical idealism:

...if we really wish to understand the status of physical objects, mathematical models, chemical processes, social relations, cultural products, etc., then we need to understand how they can appear as what they are and with the meaning they have.

(Zahavi, 2018)

This statement underlines the notion that pure science cannot be unaffected by meanings and understandings in a social world. Eatough and Smith (2008) articulate this through two contrasting descriptions of a table. They outline and compare how astrophysicist Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington (1933, cited in Eatough and Smith (2008)) describes a table:

My scientific X is mostly emptiness. Sparsely scattered in that emptiness are numerous electrical charges rushing about with great speed; but their combined bulk amounts to less than a billionth of the bulk of the X itself. Notwithstanding its strange construction it turns out to be an entirely efficient X. It supports my Y as satisfactorily as X No. 1; for when I lay the Y on it the little electric particles with their headlong speed keep on hitting the underside, so that the Y is maintained in shuttlecock fashion at a nearly steady level. If I lean upon this X I shall not go through; or, to be accurate,

the chances of my scientific Z going through my scientific X is so excessively small that it can be neglected in practical life.

Against this, philosopher Lubica Učník's (2013 cited in Eatough and Smith (2008)) description was as follows:

It is a table that unites people when they come to visit me, and we talk in agreement. It also seems to divide us when we disagree. But it is always in between us, familiar and dependable: to put cups of coffee on; or indeed for whatever purpose we might use it at different times. I sit at that table when I am happy as well as when I am sad, and many memories come rushing in when I look at it. It is slightly damaged on one side from the time my daughter tried to climb up onto it and the table toppled onto her. Years later, she has no scars left, but the table reminds us of this event by the scratch that has remained there ever since: it is a memory writ large. I like to stroke that chipped table, as it reminds me of all the people who sat there once upon a time; and I imagine that others will sit there sometime in the future. It is not just a useful table that I have breakfast on, it is a part of my life.

This resonates with the discussion concerning the evolution of public engagement with science (Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon, 2014; Trench, 2008) and its contemporary positioning within a social world that attends to economic growth, accountability, democracy, culture and the promotion of science (Davies, 2020).

Furthermore, it highlights the validity of Husserlian theory as a way of exploring how lecturers in pure science disciplines make meaning within the reality of the social world they inhabit. Husserl's work was grounded in philosophical concerns and was primarily descriptive (Sloan and Bowe, 2014), whereas Martin Heidegger proposed an interpretative, or hermeneutic, theory (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019). Both theorists shared a preoccupation with the human condition and experience in relation to the intersection between the mind and the world (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019). According to Sloan and Bowe (2014), there are many differences between descriptive and hermeneutic phenomenography, underlining the complex, socially constructed and ambulatory nature of the world.

Table 6: Phenomenology: Husserl and Heidegger key terminology.

<p>Edmund Husserl (1856–1938)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Husserl used epoché, or bracketing (Mertens, 2020), to set aside preconceptions (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020) including commonplace societal understandings (natural attitude) and popular beliefs and theories from previous academic work to distil the transcendental essence of the phenomenon in rich, descriptive detail (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Sloan and Bowe, 2014).• His theory was rooted in perceptual intentionality stretching back to Aristotelian philosophy (Keane, 2019), following the teaching of Franz Brentano. This defines the features of consciousness as the “aboutness” of an intentional subject, object or phenomena of a lived experience (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Zahavi, 2018).• He argued that it was facile to conceptualise a phenomenon in binary, as “inside” or “outside”. He termed this as “noema” – <i>what</i> we experience – and “noesis” – <i>how</i> we experience (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).• He coined the use of the term <i>lifeworld</i> to describe the ways in which humans make meaning in the world that they find themselves in. This, Zahavi (2018) argues, is a criticism of science, citing Stephen Strasser, who compared the lifeworld to a fertile soil, suggesting that “...science draws on the lifeworld.” This concept was further expanded upon by Merleau-Ponty, who pinpointed the notion of experience of the lifeworld through our bodies – that is, embodiment (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).• The essential features of descriptive data gathering in phenomenology have been formalised in one contemporary technique known as Giorgi’s method (Giorgi, 1985; Giorgi and Giorgi, 2008), cited in King, Horrocks and Brooks (2018), which utilises many aspects of Husserl’s method.
<p>Martin Heidegger (1889–1976)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Heidegger articulated the process of hermeneutic self-understanding of human behaviours (Han and Ellis, 2019), “Dasein” or presence within the world (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Sloan and Bowe, 2014). This is a dialogical (Groenewald, 2004), interconnected (Keane, 2020) and mutual process (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020) that describes a de-distancing, rather than a disorientation – existential “being-in”, or categorical “being in” (Zahavi, 2018).• Inquiry may be guided by the imagination, which is described as eidetic variation and can illuminate “...hitherto unnoticed aspects of inner experience” (Zahavi, 2018).• Hermeneutic inquiry is temporal and transcendental (Keane, 2020) – that is, it describes a moment in time. This is distinct to descriptive phenomenology, which uses epoché to transcend the influence of time (Sloan and Bowe, 2014). Hermeneutics therefore grant attention to change over time (Pitard, 2015).• His view disclosed that the interpretative process is systematic and argumentative “...characterised by a certain violence” (Zahavi, 2018). A variation of this is interpretative phenomenology methodology (IPA), developed by Smith (1996) and Smith and Osborn (2008) (cited in King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). This usually analyses interview data using a two-stage interpretative reduction process.

Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) is a method that emerged in the UK in the 1990s (Eatough and Smith, 2008) and situates the researcher within an active, rather than passive, role within data gathering and interpretation (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019). The method is attached to the exploration of subjective experiences as a phenomenon (Mertens, 2020; Braun and Clarke, 2006) and is combined with the study of cultural meanings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019), interpretative hermeneutics (Keane, 2019) and the exploration of identity and self through idiographic inquiry (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Wood, Farmer and Goodall, 2016). The principles of IPA foreground dialogic data through interviews and autoethnographic reflection, grouped into themes and elements determined in the first instance by the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Saldaña, 2021; Braun and Clarke, 2020).

The IPA methodology is a flexible design (Eatough and Smith, 2008) that allows the researcher to use prompts and creativity to elicit and interpret a dialogical understanding of qualitative data (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020; Sin, 2010). The role of dialectics in phenomenology is explored by Keane (2019) in relation to rhetoric. He strips back the meaning of the word *rhetoric* to its Aristotelian conceptualisation as a means of persuasion based on *potential* and *possibility*. In contrast to a positivist approach, researcher subjectivity and interpretation shape findings derived from IPA (Giorgi, 2011). This is an appealing aspect of hermeneutic inquiry as it allows for space within a research design (Wisker, 2008; Frick and Brodin, 2019). Consequently, meaning is not fixed in the data or dialogue. Autoethnography was used to complement IPA within this flexible design (Starr, 2014). During a time when COVID-19 lockdowns meant that interviews could not be conducted face-to-face this method helped to share meaning with the study participants, to check that the interpretation hit the right mark and solidify the results as a means of member checking (Robson, 2011).

3.3 Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was sought in an application to the UWS ethics committee supported by an outline of the study and its aims and research questions, together with the proposed interview schedule, consent form and participant information sheet (Appendix A). The British Educational Research Association code of ethics directed

the early development of the proposal (BERA, 2018; Creswell, 2014). It was essential to develop trust with participants and the strict and explicit integrity of the research to guard against impropriety or misconduct underpins this (Creswell, 2014; Punch and Oancea, 2014). However, as the study did not focus on research involving children or vulnerable adults, it was deemed that no special provisions needed to be in place (Bryman, 2016). Institutional review was applied for according to the ethical standards guidelines published by UWS (UWS, 2016). Ethical approval application 16437 was submitted electronically via the UWS ethics portal. Approval was granted on 18 June 2021 by the UWS ethics committee with conditions.

Increasingly, issues of personal disclosure, credibility and authenticity of research are under scrutiny (Creswell, 2014). As such, autoethnography can raise ethical issues whereby the researcher becomes the researched and appropriates information from informants to develop or facilitate storytelling (Lapadat, 2017). This places responsibility on the researcher to be aware of relational ethics (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010; Ettore, 2016), with these issues to be noted down in the research diary if arising during data collection (Roy and Uekusa, 2020). Individual autoethnographic reflections on the interviews were shared privately with participants, together with verbatim, anonymised interview transcripts for approval prior to their use to assemble data in the findings and discussion sections.

In qualitative research, Braun and Clarke (2020) opine that grounded theory may be the best suited methodology to achieve saturation through an iterative approach to inquiry. Achieving saturation in phenomenology may therefore be viewed as problematic. Data saturation is typically a positivist concept whereby saturation is achieved when a research question is sufficiently investigated to achieve an understanding of the topic, justifying discontinuation of the research in question (Wisker, 2008). However, Groenewald (2004) suggests that the necessary breadth and depth of investigation can be achieved in phenomenological studies by interviewing a suitable number of participants. The study therefore aimed to recruit ten participants in line with these recommendations. These amendments to the ethics application were agreed within the supervisory team prior to the commencement of data collection.

3.4 Sampling and recruitment of study participants

After ethical approval was granted, I made an open call for respondents with a view to recruiting participants for interview. I considered whether to employ a very detailed reductive phenomenological analysis in the tradition of Husserl on a very small sample of lecturers (Zahavi, 2018). Or to adopt a more idiographic approach that focused on values, elements and themes derived from a larger sample of cases (Zahavi, 2019; Eatough and Smith, 2008; Braun and Clarke, 2020; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). Given that the description of lived experience derived through epoché and reduction is typically the method that underpins descriptive phenomenology (Giorgi, 2011) I chose IPA - a subjective, interpretative process that lends an understanding to the everyday experiences of people (Larsson and Holmström, 2009).

At the outset of the study, I needed to decide whether to adopt a narrow sample or to engage with a wider pool of participants. There is no clear route and debate is ongoing regarding these approaches (Giorgi, 2011; Wood, Farmer and Goodall, 2016; Zahavi, 2019). For example, Eatough and Smith (2008) chart a methodology where sample sizes can be as numerous as thirty people. Moreover, they suggest that the method is dynamic and evolving – indeed, Giorgi (2011) critiques this as a superficial assessment. This illuminates the ongoing debate concerning ways to approach IPA as an empirical research method, and how it relates to the depth of description of phenomenological data (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Zahavi, 2019). I chose to recruit around ten respondents, in line with the suggested sample size outlined by Groenewald (2004).

The reported lack of integrative research links with undergraduate teaching reveal a lack of articulation of the teaching/research nexus from the lecturer perspective (Brew, 2010). Few studies appear to have been conducted in Scotland, meaning that I chose to purposively sample lecturers who actively teach undergraduate cohorts in Scotland (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021). Although Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham (2020) have commenced a longitudinal Scottish study, its focus is on social science, and few studies examine the experiences of STEM lecturers in Scotland, which is surprising given that public engagement with science has been entrenched within mainstream policy and practice for over twenty years (Ramsey and Boyette, 2021). The history of the fruitful period of arts and learning that flourished during the Scottish Enlightenment in the mid-1700s influenced the focus of

the study on Scotland (Collini, 2012). The nation in modern times has a strong public engagement identity with STEM and gave rise to the first modern science festival, held in Edinburgh in 1989 (Ramsey and Boyette, 2021).

Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017) noted in their assessment of public impact that REF reporting indicated a distinct lack in reporting from STEM Panel B subjects (chemistry, mathematics, engineering, physics, and computing science). This disciplinary focus was adopted for sampling purposes, which enables the phenomenon to direct the method and sample (Groenewald, 2004; Walkington, 2015; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). However, it must be noted that such a narrow sampling strategy could lack stratification – for example, in the form of a gender imbalance or disciplinary imbalance (Creswell, 2014). However, the essence of IPA as a methodology privileges the experiences of participants as the source for the interpretative activity of the researcher (Elliott, Fischer and Rennie, 1999). Validity is therefore drawn from meaningful inferences constructed through a rich qualitative picture derived from a small sample size rather than a representative sample (Eatough and Smith, 2008).

A total number of twenty-seven informants were approached, with ten selected for first stage interviews using a combination of purposive sampling through direct contact, including snowball sampling via participants' and supervisors' personal contacts, an open call via social media, online journal clubs and virtual conferences (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018; von der Fehr, Sølberg and Bruun, 2016). Notably, as much of the research was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns of 2021, the use of digital platforms to recruit participants was heavily relied upon in the absence of face-to-face contact (Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards, 2021). Consequently, participants naturally drawn to digital outreach and social networks may have emerged.

It must therefore be acknowledged that the study may not have reached STEM lecturers less likely to come forward to engage using non-traditional methods such as digital platforms and social media. This is a limitation and an area for research outside the scope of this study ([Section 3.7](#)) (Selin *et al.*, 2017; Shulla *et al.*, 2020; Trench, 2008). Such “real-world constraints” are unavoidable within the confines of a PhD

study led by a solo investigator working to a timeframe (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

3.4.1 Recruitment of study participants

Following an open call for participants at Scottish universities the study adopted a qualitative approach to understand the experiences of STEM Panel B lecturers and how they interlink these aspects of practice within the lens of higher education (HE). The “historical lens” of HE is anchored in political, social and cultural influences explored within the literature review – accordingly, sampling was restricted to HE settings (Punch and Oancea, 2014; Collini, 2012; McKinley *et al.*, 2020). The use of several theoretical lenses (Sharp *et al.*, 2014) beyond the primary guiding lens was used to focus further on the extension of the teaching/research nexus to a triple nexus, which incorporates public engagement (Tight, 2016; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). At undergraduate level, the teaching/research nexus is noted by Healey and Jenkins (2009) as “...a powerful way to reinvent the undergraduate curriculum”, so sampling was further narrowed to focus on the experience of lecturers who undertake research and actively teach undergraduate cohorts.

Table 7: Sampling characteristics of participants.

Characteristic	Requirement
Institutional	Scottish HEIs only (Universities Scotland, 2020).
Discipline	STEM Panel B only: mathematics, computer science, environmental science, Earth sciences, physics and chemistry (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017).
Pedagogical	Actively engaged in research and teaching undergraduate cohorts (Brew, 2010).

The timing of the study meant that I had an eighteen-month window to collect interviews. To some extent, this was complicated by lockdowns and illness during the COVID-19 pandemic. I therefore aimed to gather data from a sample of participants over the course of four semesters to elicit a “structure of experience” (Van Manen 1997, cited in Sloan and Bowe, 2014). Accordingly, the findings that are reported, and the methodology used to achieve this, aim to fortify and explain methods that can be

used by researchers to elicit a *structure of experience* in IPA. Access to lecturers was not always straightforward because of their commitments, so a range of sampling strategies were adopted to recruit them. My former position as an FE lecturer made it easier to understand the needs and availability of lecturing staff during an academic year, which contributed in a major way to the recruitment process, making it easier for potential participants to share concerns about availability:

It's really difficult to suggest someone directly as, as you recognise yourself, pressures and demands on lecturers would mean that it might be difficult to commit to anything.

R20 – respondent declined invitation to participate.

Furthermore, I felt a sense of the pressure that lecturers face with their daily workload. One participant had to withdraw prior to the second round of interviews:

For now, I'm busy with many other things, so I'd prefer not to participate any further. Thanks for the interactions we have had.

Kappa M – ceased participation after the first round of interviews.

The following tables indicate that the respondents were approached through personal networks, purposive sampling or snowball sampling (Creswell, 2014). In total, twenty-seven informants were approached through contact with four networks via social media. Ten respondents were selected for first stage interviews using a combination of purposive sampling through direct contact, snowball sampling elicited via participants' or supervisors' personal contacts, an open call via social media, online journal clubs and virtual conferences (von der Fehr, Sølberg and Bruun, 2016; Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018).

Table 10: Respondents via personal contact.

Respondent ID	Role*	Discipline	Gender**	Follow-up
Zeta E	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
R1	Research	STEM Panel B	M	n/a
Gamma S	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	Participant
R2	PEP	STEM Panel B	W	Snowball
Alpha K	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
R3	Research	STEM Panel A	W	Snowball
R4	PEP	STEM Panel A	W	n/a
Delta I	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant

Table 8: Respondents via snowball sampling.

Respondent ID	Role*	Discipline	Gender**	Follow-up***
R12	Network	All	W	n/a
R13	PEP	STEM Panel B	W	Snowball
R14	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
Kappa M	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
R15	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	n/a
R16	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	n/a
R17	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	n/a
R18	Network	All	All	Snowball
R19	Network	All	W	n/a
R20	Research	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
Eta B	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
Theta A	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
R21	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
Iota C	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	Participant

Table 9: Respondents via purposive sampling.

Respondent ID	Role*	Discipline	Gender**	Follow-up***
R5	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	n/a
R6	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
Beta A	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	M	Participant
R7	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
R8	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a
Epsilon M	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	Participant
R9	Network	STEM	W	n/a
R10	Lecturer	Arts	W	Snowball
R11	Lecturer	STEM Panel B	W	n/a

*This column indicates the job role or status of the respondent.

** This column indicates the social construct of a participant's gender.

Lecturer: an individual with lecturing responsibilities for undergraduate cohorts.

Research: an individual who reports that they only undertake research and no teaching.

PEP: a public engagement professional

Network: a network of interested persons, or relevant community of practice.

W: identifies as a woman

M: identifies as a man

***This column indicates whether individuals agreed to participate.

Snowball: indicates that the participant was able to suggest other relevant contacts.

n/a: either that the respondent could not participate or did not respond.

3.4.2 Sampling plan

The timing for collection of data is important for two reasons. Primarily, for expediency to ensure that the PhD research project kept to the agreed timeframe (Mertens, 2020). Second, to ensure that data was collected at the right time for participants, in order that the particularities of individuals are not obscured (Wood, Farmer and Goodall, 2016; Eatough and Smith, 2008). Having reflected on my position as a researcher and my background as a former FE lecturer, I was aware of the pressures and demands placed upon lecturers, which could be through teaching or administrative loads at different times of the year (Collini, 2012; Pirrie and Fang, 2021; Wheaton, 2020). Stage 1 interviews were therefore completed before the end of semester 2 in 2021 and stage 2 interviews were undertaken at the start of semester 2 in the 2021/22 academic year. The sampling plan was recorded using MS Excel to check in on the timeframe and the participant responses within that period.

3.5 Data collection methods

The study utilised two methods of qualitative data collection: phenomenological interviews and autoethnography. The justification for these methods is rooted in the essence of the *lifeworld*, which explores the subjective interpretation of spatiality (lived space), corporeality (lived body), temporality (lived time) and relationality (lived human relation) (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Zahavi, 2019; Larsson and Holmström, 2009). As such, the methods were used in tandem to attempt a dialogue within the research in order that personal experience and assumptions could be set aside and communicated with participants to share meaning concerning the phenomena they experience (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020). Moreover, the methodology and methods aimed to elucidate a framework or method within IPA able to be replicated and repeated as a way of collecting qualitative data virtually (Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards, 2021; Sin, 2010).

3.5.1 Interview design

Interview design was derived from the research questions and arranged thematically in an interview schedule see Table 11 (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Braun and Clarke, 2020; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). The UWS ethics committee approved this as a framework for a semi-structured interview. However, interviews were flexible by

design and allowed for unstructured prompt questions (e.g. *Can you tell me a bit more about that?; Do you mean?; Can you give me examples of that?*) to guide the process (Eatough and Smith, 2008; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). This was a useful means to uncover data that had not been considered within the guide questions, allowing space for participants as “social actors” to converse about their experiences and understandings of specific social settings, processes and relationships (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

Interview schedule themes:

- Orientation, demographics, career and background information
- The R/T/Pe triple nexus
- Supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness
- Using digital spaces to support public engagement activity
- Hierarchies and institutional identity
- Reflections on practice and findings

Interviews were grouped into three phases. The aim of each phase was to establish and maintain a trusting and dialogic relationship with participants (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Mertens, 2020). This is particularly important for IPA where the research participant is privileged as a storyteller, as opposed to a respondent, and the researcher is a facilitator who brings the story to life (Eatough and Smith, 2008). The interviews are based on a framework proposed by Punch and Oancea (2014) to test and refine semi-structured interviews (prepare, produce, prune, polish, pilot). Re-iterative *pruning* took place following each interview – for example, if a number of respondents concurred on certain points, I could assume a certain strength of data validation and concentrate on other themes (Creswell, 2014; Sin, 2010).

Table 11: Interview schedule.

Stage 1: Orientation interview – max. thirty minutes (unrecorded)

Unstructured opening discussion to establish rapport, introduce myself, share the purpose of the study, set out confidentiality issues, obtain consent to participate virtually or face to face and schedule follow-up interviews, as well as checking in on participant personal demographic data to ensure sampling compatibility:

- Name
- Institution
- Job role and academic discipline
- Extent of teaching or research duties with undergraduate cohorts

Summarise and clarify any details regarding timeframe of study and time commitment required, as well as researcher and participant expectations, to agree future interview dates.

Stage 2: Semi-structured interview – one hour (recorded and transcribed)

Discover idiographic data through conversation using warm-up questions and structured questions

- The R/T/Pe triple nexus
 - Supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness
 - Using digital spaces to support public engagement activity
 - Hierarchies and institutional identification, probes, prompts and follow-ups.
-

Stage 3: Semi-structured interview – one hour (recorded and transcribed)

Prior to this interview, participants approve their transcripts and have sight of interim data findings from the study, with the intention of reflecting on findings and developing a richer understanding with participants to highlight resonance and uncover meanings within the central themes of data elicited from stage 2 interviews.

(Bryman, 2016; Creswell, 2014; Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2018; Farrow *et al.*, 2020; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Mertens, 2020)

3.5.2 Recording and conducting interviews

All interviews, except one that was conducted face-to-face and recorded on a password-protected iPhone XR, were conducted on MS Teams and recorded and saved on a password-protected file on the UWS institutional MS OneDrive repository. Ethical consent was sought and recorded in writing prior to the interview or recorded at the commencement of the interviews. Informed by the guidelines presented by King, Horrocks and Brooks (2018) and Punch and Oancea (2014), the following procedure was used:

Table 12: Steps to generate semi-structured interviews.

Prepare

Ensure a stable broadband connection with a backup connection – the disadvantages of virtual research include the potential for it to be disrupted by technical failure (Archibald *et al.*, 2019). Ethical approval is obtained either in writing or verbally on the recording (Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards, 2021). Ensure that the interview setting is warm and inviting, that the camera is at the right angle to replicate a face-to-face conversation as much as possible and that the audio recording is enabled (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

Produce

Build rapport through conversation informed by pre-interview research on the respondent's background via their research profiles, HEI profile page and social media channels (Bryman, 2016; King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018). Note positionality (Berger, 2013) and emotions (Kmita, 2017) with a reflection in research notebook to produce an autoethnographic analysis in tandem with data collection (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010).

Prune

Data saturation may have been achieved through a common understanding of a certain theme (Mertens, 2020) rather than simply by conducting the same interview questions with a given number of participants (Groenewald, 2004). IPA is grounded in the flexibility of real-time interaction with participants (Eatough and Smith, 2008) and the consequent ability to fine-tune.

Polish, pilot and pivot

The individual and unique nature of interpretative phenomenological interviewing meant that each interview was essentially a pilot, running ahead of the next participant conversation or story (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Sin, 2010). Using this iterative process, interview findings and flow were used to inform and pivot the questions as necessary on the return to the preparation stage for subsequent interviews to refine the process and structure (Punch and Oancea, 2014).

3.5.3 Autoethnography

Autoethnography is a humanist approach to research practice that uses tenets of autobiography and ethnography to embody research on the self (Berger, 2013; Empson, 2012; Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010; Lapadat, 2017). Findings are presented through a range of creative methods, which can include very personalised writing, reflection, collaborative writing, art, poetry, music and film (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Autoethnographic reflexive pieces produce knowledge (Hernández *et al.*, 2010) through a liminal practice that positions academic writers as both researchers and objects of research (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020). The practice is “painterly” – i.e., characterised by layers of literary artfulness (Magrini, 2015) that can be ameliorated in writing, sound or vision through qualities of colour and texture (Amoroso, 2021; Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010).

Autoethnography offers a dialogic space to share meaning through reflexive sense-making in educational practice and is sympathetically positioned to provide a nurturing approach to managing the shifting identities experienced as a PhD candidate (Boncori and Smith, 2019). I favoured this approach for data gathering because of expediency through circumstances brought about by social isolation and distance data gathering – during the COVID-19 pandemic, there were few spaces to meet colleagues or attend face-to-face events (Lahiri-Roy, Belford and Sum, 2021). The essence of virtual research, particularly during a global health crisis, is a form of disembodiment, and, arguably, autoethnography addresses this disembodiment through embodied reflexivity (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Leigh and Bailey, 2013). This is perhaps a useful method to employ in educational research given that the post-pandemic HE landscape will lean more heavily towards distance or blended learning models (Martini, 2020; Nordmann *et al.*, 2020).

The decision to use autoethnography alongside phenomenological interviews sits within the application of reflexivity as a methodological tool to address issues of bracketing in interpretative inquiry (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020; Starr, 2014). For example, within engineering, Secules *et al.* (2021) highlight the value of statements of researcher positionality and intentionality through autoethnography to enhance credibility and reliability of findings (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Furthermore, Schmidt (2019) has illuminated the benefits through identifying the connection between cognition and emotion as a means to transform educational practice.

Additionally, autoethnography used as a reflexive approach in STEM education (Hains-Wesson and Young, 2016; Amoroso, 2021) points to the value of an intentional commitment to sensitivity and self-awareness in educational inquiry (Berger, 2013). It is interesting to note the emergent value of collaborative autoethnography within teams and disciplines and this is identified as an area for further research ([Section 6.4](#)) (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020; Warwick, McCray and Palmer, 2021). This perhaps offers an antidote to the pedagogic frailty that (Kinchin and Francis, 2016) note in academic communities, which has the potential to be more widely explored as a novel methodology for educational research in STEM disciplines (Sheridan *et al.*, 2019).

Autoethnographic reflections were collected in four ways:

- i) Datawalking, using walking as an embodied activity to collect post-data reflections. Voice notes recorded on an iPhone XR using the voice memos app while (Amoroso, 2021; Eardley, Banister and Fletcher, 2020; van Es and de Lange, 2020; Beattie and Zihms, 2024).
- ii) Formative notes recorded in a written research interview journal to create cameos of each participant (Golsteijn and Wright, 2013; Pitard, 2015; Warwick, McCray and Palmer, 2021).
- iii) Reflexive writing on emotions (Schmidt, 2019; Kmita, 2017) before and after interviews were recorded in a written interview journal and shared privately, together with transcripts, for approval with respondents to develop mutual trust and intimacy (Lahiri-Roy, Belford and Sum, 2021).
- iv) Formative autoethnographic writing cameos shared publicly on my research blog www.researchblog.scot. The benefits of open access blogging over closed notes allowed additional scope for a public dialogue with other web users or readers for comment and feedback, an open and publicly available space for discourse and a space that could be shared through a variety of channels including conferences and social media links (Weingart and Guenther, 2016; Weller, 2011; Yau, 2019; Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020).

It is important to note that autoethnography in this study relates to my reflections on positionality and interactions with other people. It is therefore essential to be aware of the ethical considerations pertaining to this, outlined in [Section 3.3](#).

3.5.4 Use of creative methods in autoethnography

Creative methods were used to inform autoethnography in the study. Specifically, to highlight the use and applicability of creative methods for public engagement with science and how this could aid reflection on approaches to teaching and learning in STEM. Specifically, Moraes (2019) supports the idea that creative approaches help to generate innovation and ideas particularly within student bodies, suggesting that teaching and learning can be enhanced this way. This is supported by Kompella (2020) who recommends the use of creative analogies and metaphors to reach broader audiences and explain a research topic at hand effectively. Seatter (2016) asserts that creativity is a pathway within the theory of change which ultimately adds a different dimension to the potential for metacognition and critical thinking which is supported by Archer *et al.* (2021) who found this in their work with schools in Scotland.

This adds to the notion of the civic capacities of public engagement outside of formal academic spaces outlined by Selin (2017). Furthermore, creative approaches in science communication are supported by Illingworth (2020) as a means to develop a creative approach to generate a meaningful dialogue with multiple and diverse publics. The dialogical aspect of creativity is exemplified by de Clippelle *et al.* (2021, p.138) who note “value in using non-controversial language and approaching our message in an unexpected and creative way, especially when we were communicating about a topic such as ocean acidification, which is rather abstract and a challenge to get across if people have either never heard about it or have preconceived ideas about what the language means.”

Specific methods used in this study included writing; storytelling; music and memes. Creative writing is posited by Ellis, Adams and Bochner (2010) as an important aspect of autoethnography. Similarly, Leitch (2022, p.7) posits that storytelling blends “a range of different types and forms of knowledge: stories where local voices and local knowledge are interwoven with western science knowledge and are not just told using words but also through other creative routes.” Autoethnography moves away from the conventional bounds of academic writing styles and Orrit (2020, p.6) infers that there

is potential to reach a broader audience when “writers can promote engagement by breaking the usual rules of grammar and using language creatively, particularly when writing for a less formal purpose.” Another form of communication, music, is explored by Zarkadakis (2010) and Selin (2017) who posit the use of music and song as a sonorous form of communication along with singing, laughter and noise. According to Zarkadakis (2010) music may only be appropriate where a science communicator is comfortable and open to its use. This worked for my study given my background in music and openness to using this as a form of communication although it must be recognised this may not work for all who embark on autoethnographic methods.

Two memetic images were created in this study to explore the themes of gender and STEM through the lens of intersectionality and feminism (Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Iloh, 2021). The use of third spaces and digital media are supported as a means of communicating to broader audiences which is explored by (Seatter and Ceulemans, 2017) who explains how creative visuals that involve meme transfer of popular cultural icons can inculcate as a shift in “...mindset (one could relate this to critical thinking and a new frame of reference) or lifestyle (one could call this creative thinking, as it involves a change in behaviour).” Added to this, Yammine (2020, p.5) explores hashtag curation as a useful way to generate interest and reach out to a digitally distributed population of interest, “Your hashtags should always be relevant to the content you’re sharing, but you can broaden your reach beyond science ‘echo chambers’ (content that preaches to the converted, reinforcing existing beliefs) by incorporating other trends.”

3.6 Qualitative data analysis – preparation steps

3.6.1 Analysis of interview data

There is some debate concerning the replicability of IPA as a methodology (Eatough and Smith, 2008; Giorgi, 2011; Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Zahavi, 2019). As this inquiry focuses on the subjective, heterogeneous experiences of individual lecturers and their experiences of a given phenomenon within HE it is, according to Keane (2020) and Zahavi (2019), important to ensure that the analysis of data accounts for the philosophical foundations of phenomenology, which explore a common experience or phenomenon of experience. A growing body of literature

concerns applied phenomenology, as Zahavi (2019) has noted, but this focuses on philosophy and psychology. I therefore present my account of a multi-layered method for analysis of interview data to provide a potentially useful framework for IPA research in education.

Stage 1: Transcription of first interviews

Recordings created verbatim transcriptions of interviews using MS Teams and Otter.ai. Anonymised transcripts were edited while listening back to include written notation of pauses, accent (emphasis, not pronunciation) and laughter (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Klein, 2012). In addition the bodily actions of participants and the researcher were noted, although the limitations of this must be noted in a digitally mediated environment (Archibald *et al.*, 2019).

Stage 2: Approval of first interview transcripts

Written interview transcriptions with autoethnographic reflections on themes were sent back to participants for member checking (Robson, 2011). This was to ensure that the meaning of each theme was in accord with the experiences of the participants (Giorgi, 2011).

Stage 3: Preliminary analysis of themes

A read-through of transcripts while listening to interview recordings noted resonance of voice and tone (Muccio, Reybold and Jidd, 2015) was followed by a re-read to pinpoint sub-themes arising from interviews to cluster and populate findings within the main themes (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

Stage 4: Autoethnography and imaginative variation

Autoethnographic pieces associated with the main themes were created using imaginative variation (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019). This was used as a special form of interview prompt prior to second stage interviews (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

Stage 5: Second stage interviews

All participants were invited to a second stage interview to derive a richer understanding of their experience of the triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015),

to substantiate a fertile description of the lifeworld and lived experience of those lecturers (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020; Starr, 2014; Zahavi, 2018).

Stage 6: Transcription and approval of second stage interviews

The processes for stage 1 were used to transcribe, notate and approve transcripts with participants who participated in stage 2 interviews.

Stage 7: First cycle coding – participant portraits

Once first and second interviews were complete, transcripts were coded and memos noted to record resonance thoughts in line with the framework proposed by van Manen (1997), cited in (Sloan and Bowe, 2014), which highlights *noema* – what is experienced – and *noesis* – how it is experienced (Harris, 2011; Sloan and Bowe, 2014).

Lived space – Spatiality

Lived body – Corporeality

Lived time – Temporality

Lived human relation - Relationality

This first cycle of coding, which Saldaña (2021) outlines as *affective methods*, investigated the subjective human experience of emotions and values. This contributed to the creation of participant portraits to inform an understanding of the interpersonal and intrapersonal experience of the participants. Portraiture adds *painterly depth* and *focus* for the generation of data, while giving relevant context to understandings of research participants' experience (Golsteijn and Wright, 2013). Accordingly, anonymised portraits of participants record and report the natural attitude, or essence, of participants (Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020).

Stage 8: Second cycle coding using NVivo

Second cycle coding arranged and explored the themes from interviews. Transcripts were uploaded to NVivo Pro 12 to gather and curate primary data within the thematic coding framework and sub-themes identified in stage 3. Any themes outside the coding framework were recorded as open codes (Klein, 2012; Ryan and Bernard, 2016).

Themes derived from the research questions were identified as follows:

T1: The R/T/Pe triple nexus

T2: Supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness

T3: Using digital spaces to support public engagement activity

T4: Hierarchies and institutional identity

T5: Reflections on practice and recommendations

Stage 9: Memoing

Novel ideas or concepts derived during the process of data coding were recorded concurrently via memoing on NVivo (Groenewald, 2004).

Stage 10: Synthesis

Data derived from interviews was used to provide a detailed rendering of the information gathered from lecturers (Creswell, 2014) and to report on and interpret findings (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Starr, 2014; Sloan and Bowe, 2014).

3.7 Limitations

This study commenced at the same time as the COVID-19 lockdowns in 2020 and this limitation is identified as a barrier in terms of access to participants and gatekeepers (Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards, 2021). Furthermore, as all interviews had to be conducted virtually, this may have meant that some potential respondents were excluded (e.g. if they did not have broadband access or wish to be interviewed online) (Archibald *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, this may have affected some of the findings that relate to respondents' openness to the use of digital and virtual spaces in their teaching practice (Cross and Congreve, 2020). Of the nine participants who were interviewed, only three were women. This gender imbalance represents a further limitation of the study, perhaps in part because of the increased pressures on women in their roles as caregivers during COVID-19, or as a result of the imbalanced numbers of women working in STEM (Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021; McKinnon and O'Connell, 2020).

Identity is an important aspect of the study, explored through autoethnography to add dimension to virtual interviews (Starr, 2014). Within this, I have reflected on my

positionality within the study. This will be concluded in a reflection in [Section 6.4](#). Further, it must be acknowledged that identity is a phenomenon that cannot be examined in one moment in time, a notion borne out by the shifting perceptions observed within the participants between their first and second stage interviews. As Bruhn and Jimenez (2020) observe, identity is not static, reminding researchers of the assertion of Harvard academic Professor Sarah Dryden-Petersen that, "...research considers sites and phenomena over extended periods of time rather than limiting our inquiries to one specific moment." This must be accepted as a limitation of a PhD study because of the time limits of the study, as it is not longitudinal in nature (Farrow *et al.*, 2020).

3.8 Summary

This chapter has justified the methodological selection of the study and described the methods employed to gather data. The theoretical underpinning of the methods used within interpretative phenomenology and autoethnography have been discussed and applied to ordinate the direction of the study appropriately, according to the interpretative nature of the inquiry. Ethical considerations have been presented and discussed with reference to professional codes of ethics and institutional reviews (BERA, 2018; Creswell, 2014; UWS, 2016). The following chapter presents the research findings following completion of the stage 1 and stage 2 interviews.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Findings

This study used an interpretative phenomenological methodology to examine the lived experience of nine STEM lecturers working at Scottish universities between January 2021 and April 2022. The concepts discussed centred on the triple nexus in STEM and how this aims to coalesce public engagement within the teaching/research nexus in HE. This chapter presents an overview of the chosen sample commencing with a profile of each research participant. A qualitative analysis subsequently reports on themes arising from participant interviews. Autoethnographic pieces are contained within this chapter together with reflective dialogue derived with participants. The chapter concludes with an overview of common themes found following interpretative phenomenological analysis of the data.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Gender equality of sample chosen

Although Kerr (2021) maintains that gender equality is a key asset of the UK's *soft power* – i.e. a coalescence of culture and political values to co-opt, rather than coerce, through the work of government, citizens, non-governmental organisations and cultural institutions, Scotland, in the past, has been viewed as a “macho nation” (Leith and Sim, 2020). In Scotland, a combination of national policy and targeted initiatives to support women in STEM has re-positioned political change in recent years. However, reportedly, there continues to be gender bias in STEM subjects at school (Leith and Sim, 2020).

In HE, women in STEM tend to be less equally represented, and in Scotland the disciplines of engineering and physics are noted as particularly male-dominated (Leith and Sim, 2020; Briggs, 2006; Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021). Yet teacher educators in HE are predominantly female, which may mean that women in STEM are routinely assigned roles within teams to take on teaching responsibilities (Czerniawski *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, reporting of gendered data is considered relevant to this study as it adds to these critical perspectives able to feed into an understanding of the quality and equity of education in Scotland (Ozga, 2020). Despite initiatives such as the *Athena Swan* charter to support gender equality in academia (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016), there is still a reported lack of support for female

academics in STEM (McKinnon and O’Connell, 2020; Bleijenbergh, van Engen and Vinkenburg, 2012).

Aware of researcher positionality, I needed to consider and reflect on my own position and the positions of others to ensure that gender equality was considered and how discussion of these issues can dismantle structural oppression (Clark, 2020). Notably, Beta A has no lived experience as a woman in STEM and sees gender equality within his STEM Panel B discipline from a very positivist viewpoint: “because we’re generally talking about numbers and operations and procedures, people’s sex, gender, colour, it’s not important for us because it doesn’t change how you approach the problem.” Consideration must be given to all participants in relation to presumptions about gendered roles often associated with women, as Gamma S highlighted:

I don’t have caring responsibilities, so my life is quite different than a lot of women’s, but I think there’s a lot of men that are single parents, they’re on their own and they’re looking after kids too and I’m not sure we talk about that as much as we talk about the female perspective...I think we need to maybe move away from the sort of gender stereotypes and these gender perceptions, because I don’t know if it’s tipping the balance in the wrong direction.

Gamma S, second stage interview

Acknowledging my position as a researcher, homemaker and caregiver resonates with the findings of Carr *et al.* (2020), who highlight the tensions in academia when societies continue to gender women as the principal caregivers in the home. However, the comments from Gamma S made me more aware that, although gender stereotyping in STEM exists, I should be conscious of the ways in which researchers stereotype women as primary caregivers when some women do not take on that role (Archer *et al.*, 2021). Despite Gamma S’s assertion that attention to gendered barriers in academia may be tipping too far in one direction, the unspoken expectations borne by women can be multiple, as Carr *et al.* (2020) have pointed out:

Life presses and penetrates academic work. Women can find this especially hard (Carter, Blumenstein, & Cook, 2013): societies still often gender them as principal caregivers in the home. So, they are expected to be wonderful

cooks, affectionate wives, and child-focused mothers at home; at university, they must meet deadlines while being sharp-edged and critical.

Adopting a feminist lens, I therefore chose to report the gender of participants to highlight any issues of inequality uncovered (Mertens, 2020). The vulnerabilities of gender in STEM are tellingly exposed by Caltagirone *et al.* (2021) and McKinnon and O’Connell (2020), who highlight the importance of its discussion, particularly given the imperatives of the UN SDGs to work towards gender equality (Shulla *et al.*, 2020). Intersectionality – the ways in which social identities such as gender can intersect with other social identities such as race, class and ethnicity – is identified as an area for further research ([Section 6.1](#)), but is not covered within the scope of this study (Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Klein, 2012).

In the first round of interviews, I spoke to three women and seven men. In the second round, I interviewed four men and one woman. Some women replied to let me know that they could not commit because of additional family pressures during the pandemic, while others did not respond at all. The following chart indicates the gender equality of the study.

Figure 10: Gender equality of respondents and participants.

I found that, despite having a greater number of women respondents, I was not able to recruit an equal sample of men and women to interview. On recommendation, I contacted two women-only academic networks (Scottish Women's PhD Facebook group and Science Grill) and shared my posts via Twitter to @STEMWomen to engage with potential participants. This yielded some initial interest but only one follow-up. Some respondents who could not be interviewed reported difficulties with time, particularly during lockdowns, when home-schooling and caring responsibilities often fell firmly on the shoulders of women:

I was having to home-school two kids in primary school, there was triple teaching load, there was not time really to do anything else.

Epsilon M, first stage interview

Male respondents were painfully aware of these challenges and how they affected colleagues and family:

I've got three sisters, two of them have got kids. One's got four kids from twenty-one down to eight, and one's got two kids who are twin six-year-olds. They're both primary teachers, so during lockdown they had to teach at home, but they had to home-school. I don't know how they managed it.

Delta I, first stage interview

Such pressures on time were congruent with my own experience as a working mother, leading me to reflect emphatically on the experiences of those interviewed:

I'd scheduled 1.5 hours for our meeting in my MS Teams calendar because I'm aware that when you are connected to the rhizomic and transparent web of MS Teams your hours can be scrutinised and snaffled up by colleagues who can create meetings and request time slots through the ether. The concept of "protected time" on a calendar is something I have become aware of, so I protected thirty minutes for after our interview to recharge and refresh.

Epsilon M got hold of me as soon as I scheduled the meetup and asked if we could keep it an hour tops as she had a commitment following. She was clearly, and understandably, concerned that I'd eat into thirty minutes of her MS Teams calendar. I reassured her it was 1.5 hours for me and that we'd keep to the allotted time of one hour for the interview. This early interaction highlighted the fragility of both our times, a reflection on the precarious nature of time in academia.

Autoethnographic reflection following interview with Epsilon M

Adopting a feminist lens to narrow the focus of the study builds on the critical perspectives that foreground the position of women in STEM. With this in mind its relevance to the study is clear as gender affects the nuanced and complex facets of reflexivity in qualitative research (Berger, 2013). The use of remote research methods and video interviewing have likely supported more women to be involved in the study as they could participate from home while negotiating their “invisible” roles as caregivers and homemakers (Carter, 2020). Moreover, my “cultural competence” as a woman who understands these perspectives interviewing other women inevitably brought added insight and reflexivity to the *emic* and *etic* dimensions of the research (Beals, Kidman and Funaki, 2019; Mertens, 2020)

4.2.2 Respondent profiles

All nine respondents who took part in the study consented to sharing information about their disciplinary field, career stage and category of institution. These aspects are reported in the pie charts below. The first pie chart indicates disciplinary field, which is defined within the boundaries of the REF case studies as STEM Panel B (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017). These are defined as units of assessment (UOA) by REF (2018).

Disciplinary field of participants

Figure 11: Disciplinary fields of STEM panel B participants in the study.

The results indicate roughly equal numbers of participants across all STEM Panel B disciplines within the study, with slightly more participants in chemistry and mathematical science. As such, the small-scale sample does not allow for multiple participants in each discipline, potentially representing a limitation.

The literature review indicated that academics from those universities defined as ancient or post-92 HEIs tend to identify as research-intensive, whereas those defined as new, or post-92, HEIs may place primacy on their teaching activity over research (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). The following chart denotes the institutional identity of participants at the time of their interviews. These are broadly defined as pre-92 or post-92 HEIs according to Table 4 based on the categorisation defined by Universities Scotland (2020), Briggs (2006) and Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) in Chapter one.

Institutional identity of participants

Figure 12: Institutional (HEI) identity of participants.

The results indicate an even spread between new HEIs (post-92 and vocational) and pre-92 HEIs (ancient and 1960s). The final piece of demographic information recorded in participant profiles is career stage. The literature reviewed gave very little indication of the impact of career stage upon academic approaches to public engagement. Although Girkontaitė, Benneworth and Muhonen (2020) found that early-career researchers (ECRs) were less likely than late- or mid-career researchers to take on public engagement work, this was not true of the participants in the study who identified as ECRs (see Fig. 13 below). The pie chart below indicates the distribution of participants according to their career stage.

Career stage of respondents

Figure 13: Career stages of participants in the study.

4.2.3 Participant portraits

Interpretative findings of the study are reported through examination of the personal stories of each participant. Van Manen (1997), cited in (Groenewald, 2004), explained, “[Phenomena] have something to say to us – this is common knowledge among poets and painters. Therefore, poets and painters are born phenomenologists. Or rather, we are all born phenomenologists; the poets and painters among us, however, understand very well their task of sharing, by means of word and image, their insights with others – an artfulness that is also laboriously practised by the professional phenomenologist.”

As the emphasis of this study is to report the lived experience of educators, I am mindful that, in education, this is always collaborative, whether between colleagues, between student and teacher, or moving beyond academia to the public. Humans are always engaged in some form of meaning-making activity. Consequently, it is important to locate the results in the context of demographic data (Braun and Clarke, 2020). Phenomenology is the theoretical landscape that foregrounds IPA, and different scholars defend different approaches – while IPA reports on the core experience of those studied, it is also subjective (Zahavi, 2019; Harris, 2011). Readers may judge the results from their own circumstances or situations, and the use of participant

portraits is intended to enrich the data and to advance transferability (Klein, 2012). Participant portraits were therefore “...inherently representational...” to give an indication of demographics, place of work and career stage (Bruhn and Jimenez, 2020).

According to Ellis, Adams and Bochner (2010), the construction of stories makes “witnessing” possible, which can allow the researcher to suspend preconceptions, arguably aligning with a phenomenological approach. Accordingly, participants’ attitudes towards public engagement activity are briefly reported in the portrait, which describes facets of their identity construction. This situates the sample to convey the rich complexity of participants while acknowledging sensitivity to context, thereby reflecting on the limitations of the stories told (Elliott, Fischer and Rennie, 1999). To build these stories, I commenced by constructing cameos in my research journal notes during interviews and built this into the start of each participant’s story as a means to draw the reader into the world of the sense-making of the phenomenon being investigated (Pitard, 2015; Eatough and Smith, 2008).

Gender and academic hierarchies are indicated through the literature review and data collection as key considerations relating to the main research questions (Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019; Lahiri-Roy, Belford and Sum, 2021). This is contextualised through each portrait using an anthropological lens (Hughes, Pennington and Makris, 2012; Warwick, McCray and Palmer, 2021). Themes are reported in [Section 4.3](#) through an analysis of emergent and inductive themes revealed in interviews, which are grouped according to political, social and cultural influences within the context of the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2020; Braun and Clarke, 2006). The findings are drawn together in the following sections to present a layered account of multiple voices derived from the data (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). The following table summarises the key demographic and career characteristics of participants.

Table 13: Key characteristics of participants.

Respondent ID	Gender*	Career stage	Institutional ID**	Discipline***
Alpha K	M	Late	Post-92	UOA7
Beta A	M	Mid	Post-92	UOA10
Delta I	M	Mid	Post-92	UOA8
Epsilon M	F	Mid	1960s	UOA12
Eta B	M	Early	Ancient	UOA8
Gamma S	F	Mid	Ancient	UOA11
Iota C	F	Early	Ancient	UOA9
Theta A	M	Mid	R&E	UOA10
Zeta E	M	Mid	Post-92	UOA7

* This column indicates the social construct of participants' gender:

F identifies as a woman; M identifies as a man.

** This column indicates the HEI classification (Chapter two, Table 4).

*** This column indicates discipline within REF (STEM Panel B)

Nine descriptive profiles of participants interviewed are presented in the following sections (Saldaña, 2021). Participant names are anonymised to maintain confidentiality (BERA, 2018; Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Pseudonyms are presented in the form of the Greek alphabet, which were chosen as much of the research was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. These names reflect the naming schedule given to virus variants (Callaway, 2021). The order of names – *alpha* through to *iota* – runs in order of interviews approved by participants rather than in order of interviews conducted, which aims to minimise identification and stigma through nomenclature, perceived hierarchical or sequential ordering – for example through numbering (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018; Lapadat, 2017).

Alpha K

Alpha K is a senior research fellow at a post-92 HEI who has worked extensively in Scotland and in the USA. He is the teaching leader at the scientific research institute and is involved in a mix of teaching, research and commercial work. He identifies the split as 20% of his time on research and 80% on teaching and the management of teaching. He is modestly self-deprecating when it comes to discussing the links between R/T/Pe activity. He says, “I don’t do engagement,” and that he’s “too old” and leaves it to others. Freely admitting that he does not “do” social media, he is, however, happy to get people excited about science at the coalface of a school programme or

village hall outreach. He has done a lot of this kind of work in the past but does it less now. He values academic autonomy, which he notes can be encumbered by funding, institutional contracts and policy. His ethos *for the love of science* is infectious – not insidious in a cloying way. He shies away from a corporate identity within his HEI.

Beta A

Beta A is a senior lecturer at a post-92 HEI. His academic background was punctuated by a spell in the services sector. His teaching work expands across a wide reach of undergraduate programmes and tends to focus on applied rather than pure theory. His teaching work takes up 60% of his working week with the rest split between admin and research activity. He would like to reduce his marking time. He describes himself as teaching-focused and authentic assessment-averse. Beta A comes from an area of Scotland recognised as one of the most deprived areas in Europe and he recognises the challenges that he faced on his path to academia, which are also experienced by many of the students at his current HEI. His public engagement work focuses on schools for the promotion of his academic discipline. This passion is undoubtedly founded in his passion for his academic discipline.

Delta I

Delta I is a senior lecturer at a post-92 HEI. Prior to entering academia, he worked in industry, and he is very aware of the damaging effects of post-industrialisation on Scotland's natural environment. Consequently, this has helped him to take on the role as employability champion at his university to promote the opportunities for students working in scientific disciplines to make a difference in this sector. His work is balanced at 50% teaching and 50% research, some of which is linked to industry through the formation of KTPs. His public engagement work is diverse, from Twitter to university open days, working with industry, working in schools and taking part in showcase competitions. He thrives on the diversity of some engagement opportunities, from the unpredictable amusement of throwing paper planes on a trajectory to fingerpainting or explaining how things work. He admits that "science isn't perfect", which is the part where the learning begins.

Epsilon M

Epsilon M is a lecturer at a redbrick 1960s HEI. Since the pandemic, her role has shifted from teaching and research to a wider engagement remit. She has family, students, colleagues and research. Lockdown has made it harder to juggle all the balls in her life, but she has managed to metamorphose into a different role to keep going and this approach is working for now. She points out that the pandemic tripled her teaching load, meaning that her research work has taken a back seat, but she accepts that this is par for the course given the pressures of her commitments. She champions the role of women in STEM and enjoys engagement activities and creating connections with others. She has witnessed the remarkable ways in which students changed and adapted their approaches to learning during the pandemic. However, she is concerned about the effects on their mental health and hopes that the integration of R/T/Pe could be used as a means for recovery from the legacy of this period of time.

Eta B

Eta B is a lecturer at an ancient HEI. He recently moved from an early-career research post in the USA and now conducts research at his Scottish HEI. His work involves undergraduate and postgraduate teaching, research and administration of these tasks, which includes grant writing. He sees administration as a fundamental aspect of engagement, as, without funding, there is no money to pay for impact activities. He arrived in Scotland just before the COVID-19 lockdown and has not been able to take part in any public engagement activity to date, so his work outside teaching has primarily focused on research. He has an unequivocal understanding that research informs teaching and vice versa. His awareness of academic precarity underlined by Brexit and limited funding pots is similarly matter of fact. This has not affected his passion for curiosity in his academic discipline and his desire to nurture the same curiosity in his student cohorts.

Gamma S

Gamma S is a senior research fellow at an ancient HEI. Her teaching load includes a variety of interdisciplinary undergraduate cohorts, although the bulk of her work focuses on research. She does not make a dichotomy between research and teaching, describing herself as an academic, not a lecturer. Moreover, she is starting to identify

as a multidisciplinary academic. Her conception of public engagement pinpoints events, outreach, project work, webinars, podcasts and publications as ways in which academics can integrate research and public engagement. She has worked in several HEIs in Scotland since completing her PhD in the mid-2010s and recognises that there are marked institutional differences in terms of teaching loads and access to research funding.

Iota C

Iota C is a lecturer at an ancient HEI. Her previous academic roles have been in EU HEIs prior to her becoming a research fellow in Scotland. She has been passionate about public engagement since being a post-doctoral researcher and, in times before the pandemic, she was involved in various initiatives such as science festivals, schools work and outreach to marginalised communities. She finds that she does not work to contracted hours as her teaching load is over-burdened – to keep up with her research, she thus puts in additional hours. She recognises that gendered issues within her department affect this load, particularly when it comes to the administration of academic tasks, which she takes on by default. Despite this, she is passionate about developing research skills for her undergraduate cohorts and this naturally links to public engagement. However, her excitement for outreach work is tempered by the knowledge that it may have to take a secondary position to her research work as the demands and pressures of her job continue to increase.

Theta A

Theta A is employed as a lecturer and researcher at a post-92 HEI. He teaches STEM Panel B on two undergraduate programmes. As a teaching practitioner he has reflected on his practice using a blog site and this has morphed into a repository where he shares some of his research role publicly. When he moved to his current lecturing role, he had no research work as his post-92 HEI is “...not really big enough to have a huge amount of research going on”. However, he was able to seek out a research portfolio by working on a part-time basis for another HEI, which has now integrated with his current role, in which he conducts related research work as a sub-contractor. He is particularly aware of how he integrates his research and teaching work, and this is reflected in his approach to CPD. He feels strongly that this is “...part of my own development...I wouldn't want to feel that I was doing it just to meet a requirement.”

Zeta E

Zeta E started out his career in an ancient HEI and, after some time spent in North America working on research projects, returned to Europe. He secured a lecturing position at a post-92 HEI and is passionate about his vocation: "...being a good pedagogue, I believe is really, really important." Despite being an award-winning lecturer and maintaining a passion for public engagement, he feels blocked and thwarted by the research and career progression track at his current HEI: "I'm at 50 now and I'm still a junior lecturer and it sucks. But I believe I am still an academic." Zeta E's beleaguered position has been maintained partly because of his family commitments, which he accepts: "...we just either have teaching or research contracts and that's it." He brings the fundamentals of research into his work but cannot integrate this into his teaching: "...there's no structure at [post-92] HEI to marry up research and teaching together – from a lecturer's point of view it doesn't work."

4.3 Themes derived from research questions

4.3.1 Common themes

In the following table common themes from interviews categorised within cultural, political and social values of HE are outlined (Punch and Oancea, 2014). As BERA (2018) makes clear, it is the ethical duty of educational researchers to negotiate, adapt and be sensitive to these values. This enables critical perspectives to be formulated outside the classroom, which is not a comfortable or easy process. Drawing on the work of Freire (2014), this can be postured as a *pedagogy of discomfort* (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015; Lahiri-Roy, Belford and Sum, 2021). This term accepts that subjectivity cannot be assembled in isolation, despite the intractability of these interactions, which Hernández *et al.* (2010) liken to a "Gordian knot". Heidegger described this as a "situated freedom", recognising the positioning of humans as social beings who cannot be divested from the circumstances of day-to-day life interpreted through their *lifeworld* (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Zahavi, 2018). Such freedom is not absolute, which underlines the necessity of the researcher being aware of this interdependence and the consequently overlapping narratives that may arise (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019).

Table 14: Main themes, sub themes and nodes from stage 1 interviews (Punch and Oancea, 2014; NVivo, 2018)

Social	
Lecturer attributes	Academic precarity; autonomy; buzz from teaching; demoralised by contracts; demoralised by COVID-19; REF metrics.
Undergraduate social interaction	Co-create curriculum; creativity; introversion; keen beans; link with postgrads; research-readiness; resilience in COVID-19.
COVID-19	Lack of lab time during covid; pivot pedagogy; remote research.
Gender	Departmental differences; impact of COVID-19 caring responsibilities; intersectionality.
Cultural	
Public engagement	Institutional; individualised outside the university; online; social media; PEPs.
HEI culture	Elite culture; impact agenda; pre- and post-92 differences; UK EU and USA approaches.
Scottish identity	Civic identity; humour; self-deprecation; sense of place and place-making.
Triple nexus	Definitions of public engagement; scholarly activity; impact agenda; “messy” aspects of science.
Vocation	Teaching practice; CoPs; creative projects; SoTL; datawalking; use of third spaces.
Industrialisation	Employability; environment; food and drink; forestry; KTPs.
Political	
Public engagement	Gender; race; social mobility.
Funding	Equipment in labs; impact agenda; REF; neoliberalism; middle management.
Research intensity of HEI	Research funding; hierarchies; access to PEPs.
Brexit	Brain-drain; EU nationals lost; EU funding lost.

Initial themes derived from descriptive data were shared with all stage 1 interview participants for feedback and member checking prior to second stage interviews taking place (Mertens, 2020). All six respondents who agreed to a second stage interview generally agreed with the representation of the themes: "...it covers a lot of the points; I'd say a lot of the important points" (Eta B); "There's nothing that I wouldn't resonate with" (Gamma S). In some cases, participants betrayed a sense of *ennui* or weary expectation, that the results would be as reported: "Nothing surprising" (Alpha K). In other cases, a sense of despondency emerged: "...lots of the other things that were mentioned have been issues for a while and they're just kind of ongoing issues, and I'm not entirely sure if they'll be resolved any time soon" (Theta A).

4.3.2. Cross-cutting themes derived from research questions

The first area of inquiry looks at the participants' experiences of the triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015) while considering issues of personal, institutional and disciplinary identity in STEM disciplines (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017).

R1: How do STEM Panel B disciplines in Scottish HE make integrative links between public engagement, research and teaching at undergraduate level?

The second question is concerned with the extension of von Humboldt's theory, which links teaching and research as interdependent activities (Yau, 2019) to the triple nexus as described by Stevenson and McArthur (2015). This question seeks to understand the views of lecturers in terms of its practical applications and whether there are recommendations that could improve practice to instantiate the triple nexus.

R2: Does this activity align to Humboldtian ideals, and how is knowledge generated accordingly?

From these questions, data was arranged thematically to synthesise cross-cutting themes. Pure phenomenology privileges the voice or individual experience of a person studied, whereas IPA takes a more analytical approach, which subjectively synthesises individual experience, or experiences of a phenomena within a studied group (Ryan and Bernard, 2016). Themes from both stages of interviews are outlined in the following tables:

Table 15: Overview of themes covered in first stage interviews.

Participant	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Alpha K		✓		✓	
Beta A		✓		✓	
Delta I	✓	✓		✓	✓
Epsilon M		✓	✓		
Eta B	✓	✓			
Gamma S		✓	✓		✓
Iota C	✓	✓	✓		✓
Theta A		✓	✓	✓	
Zeta A		✓	✓	✓	

Table 16: Overview of themes covered in second stage interviews.

Participant	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
Alpha K	✓	✓	✓		✓
Beta A		✓			✓
Delta I	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Eta B		✓			✓
Gamma S			✓		✓
Theta A	✓	✓	✓		✓

Themes

T1: The R/T/Pe triple nexus

T2: Supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness

T3: Using digital spaces to support public engagement activity

T4: Hierarchies and institutional identity

T5: Reflections on practice and recommendations

4.4 Qualitative data derived from research questions

4.4.1 How do the linkages between research, teaching and public engagement affect the lecturer's experience and practice?

The diagram below gives an indication of the positioning of respondents in terms of their perceptions of their role within the triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). This data was derived from a combination of interview data analysis and word clouds generated from interviews using NVivo 12 to assist understanding (NVivo, 2018).

Academics who identified their activity as balanced between research and teaching, teaching and public engagement or research and public engagement are indicated between the two elements on the outside of the dotted line. Three respondents are within the dotted line, indicating that their perception of activity is closer to the triple nexus. In the centre, two respondents are indicated as balanced in their views of the links between research, teaching and public engagement. These respondents are also identified as ECRs, which indicates a difference from the findings reported by Girkontaitė, Benneworth and Muhonen (2020).

Figure 14: Positioning study participants on the R/T/Pe triple nexus.

Research-prioritised perspectives

In general, interviews revealed that research-intensive approaches were considered archaic, as Gamma S explains: “...both my parents were involved in the academic world, and I think their roles were more defined, and certainly the use of research was maybe a bit more exclusive or something that was very much you know, people did research, and they were really those kind of elevated academics.” Gamma S sees her role as an all-round academic less exclusively and much of her research is centred on

user engagement with practical interventions to support public health. She recounted research-informed engagement, which is driven by the researcher, rather than publicly engaged research (Selin *et al.*, 2017). She defines public engagement as “...going out and speaking to people and saying, what do you think of this? And how does it feel whenever you're sort of trying to use this app?”.

Alpha K is a late-career academic who identifies first as a research scientist then a lecturer, with his working space covering a “...broad range of responsibilities”. Although he identifies primarily as a researcher, this does not reflect the balance of his workload. He describes the unity between his teaching and research and articulates the essence and origin of the unity between teaching and research expressed by Wilhelm von Humboldt (Healey and Jenkins, 2009). He is passionate about research work and enjoys the “buzz” he gets out of teaching but finds that his time is not balanced between research and teaching, with about 35% of his time devoted to managerial duties: “I spend about 20% of my time doing research, the rest involved in teaching, either managing like programme leader stuff, subject network stuff, college stuff.” He was openly cautious about public engagement when we first spoke, but in his second interview he revealed that he is less circumspect: “...I'm actually quite enthused about public engagement at the moment.”

Similarly, Zeta E is an established academic and a self-confessed positivist who participates in research: “I do fundamental research, I'm the editor of the journal of [anon] and I'm very much an academic.” Driven and excited by measurable changes over time in technology and maths, he is bemused that qualitative research can make a valid and useful analysis of the human condition because he believes the human condition is essentially flawed. His view of research-prioritised perspectives betrays frustration: “There's far too much emphasis on the UK on research and, you know, and progressing, you know, towards positions based on research alone when they might be the worst pedagogue in the whole world, and many of them are because they live in ivory towers and they're so autistic that they can't communicate.” In common with the views of most interviewed, he has a cynical view of the REF as an exercise in box-ticking and performativity (Spence, 2018): “...it's all nice and hunky and dory and to write the right language down... Blah blah blah, you know, put it in our professional reviews, what have you done for public engagement, tick this box.”

Teaching-prioritised perspectives

On the other hand, Theta A resolutely stated that, "...my teaching identity comes first...". When it comes to describing his role, he explained the way he rationalises the "balancing" of teaching and research and how "...a lot of the stuff that I do in the research is also kind of basically straight-fed into the teaching that I'm doing just now." His duty to link and "evidence" his teaching and research as a lecturer is clear, even if he does not primarily identify as a researcher:

...one of the things that is encouraged and focused upon is, you know, from an undergrad and if you're teaching at degree level essentially that you should be engaged with research, either as a researcher or keeping track of what is going on, and that is...part of our [HEI] framework.

His balance of teaching and research follows von Humboldtian principals, but he admits that he has not "...actually heard of that phrase teaching and research nexus..." (Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014). He locates public engagement within the nexus: "...both teaching and research in their way are public engagement activities...", which concurs with the findings of McKinley *et al.* (2020). Foremost, he "...really enjoys the teaching aspect..." and adeptly links his research in industry to inform his teaching and design of modules, echoing the instrumental nature of RIT explained by Joseph-Richard *et al.* (2021).

Beta A stated that he is "...teaching on three days out of the five". As teaching is prioritised, it has a detrimental effect on departmental research: "...the focus is on research. The university wants more research because that's where the money comes from. But when we've got so much teaching, the research is going to get hit. If we get more good [researchers] in the group, we'd all have less teaching, we could all do more research and get more money in." Added to this frustration, he has little scope to conduct personal research: "So, the triple [nexus] is definitely not a triple for me because most of my time is either spent in the teaching or teaching support related activities." Furthermore, he sees little motivation to go the extra mile to bring in research money. He feels that the REF funding mechanisms will never directly impact his work as a practitioner: "Whether or not I as an academic will ever see any of the funds which the university gets from my role in that submission is dubious. It will

probably be lost in that centralised administration. It's not teaching, it's not research, it's a kind of a commercial thing."

Public engagement-prioritised perspectives

Some lecturers focused on engagement as a primary aspect of their role. Epsilon M noted that "...engage[ment] has now become my primary aspect." She clarified, "...by engaging, I don't necessarily mean activities for the public, it's also engaging with teachers on how to develop things with charities, on how to work together. So, I view that with industry as well, to bring back to help benefit our students and our research." In part, she underlines the institutional aspects of engagement in terms of awareness raising or student recruitment to a university, aligning with the findings of Watermeyer and Lewis (2015), who describe this approach to engagement as "promiscuous". Not all lecturers succumb to this view. On the other hand, Alpha K described himself as "idealistic" about the university recruitment aspect of engagement: "I don't see it as recruitment, I see it **could** be recruitment but it's not why we do it... We don't go into schools to encourage people to come to [HEI], we go in to get them excited about science."

Many respondents felt strongly that promotion of the public understanding of science should centre on the promotion of STEM disciplines: "most of my public engagement is with schools, and it's about promotion of [STEM Panel B discipline] in general..." (Beta A). These activities can involve improving scientific literacy in schools or widening access to groups currently underrepresented in STEM (Kerr, 2021). Eta B described how "...public engagement would be for me really like addressing the general public, going to schools, doing something at the Science Centre". He describes engagement as a "bolt-on" supplemental to teaching and research (the core functions of academic practice), which underlines the need to re-examine approaches to public engagement with young people so that activity is not just a "one-off" (Archer *et al.*, 2021). Delta I recalled, "I've personally done engagement through the [engagement/performance STEM initiative]. I've went down to schools in [anon] to do their student fayres that have got job prospects. The university has also held open days, and it was when we were [STEM Panel B Discipline], and it was open to the public...it was aimed at kids, but adults could come in and do things as well."

A wide range of public engagement activity emerged from those interviewed. Epsilon M outlined a formal approach: "...[her]...role is out-facing at the moment. There's the inward teaching aspect, but [she feels] very outward facing in terms of the people that [she talks] to on a day-to-day basis." Some events are formally organised but in informal settings such as science festivals. Planning and preparation are important for "...specific events...it's very tailored" (Iota C). Theta A gave an example of an activity:

As part of the Science Festival, the school kids came and, we had an area marked out and we got them to walk and try to divine the water, and we knew there was a pipe underneath. So, we knew in advance that there was a pipe underneath the area that we've marked out, and they were asked to walk through the spaces.

Less formal events include night classes – "Twelve adults sipping wine and listening to my presentation" (Iota C); science-focused gameshows – "...it's good fun, and it forces you to think about your science different, because kids will ask you anything" (Delta I); and informal talks: "...just doing my own thing...and not have it linked to the university at all" (Alpha K).

Some public engagement had a profound effect on the motivation and emotions of the scientists. Iota C reflected that, "I did one outreach, which was maybe the most rewarding thing I've done in my life, was going to HMP [anon]...[and] engaging with the learners in that prison." This type of community outreach has implications for the enhancement of the prison curriculum, which Illingworth (2020) found could lead to the introduction of additional resources such as science libraries and family learning programmes in prisons. Public engagement takes energy and courage too – Delta I stated that, "I hate public speaking, but it's my job. And when I go to parties, I'm the one that's hiding...but it's part of my job. I have to be enthusiastic. I have to be open; I have to be a little bit of an extrovert to get the science out there." Zeta E concurred. Despite identifying as an extrovert, he stated that, "I'm a rare extrovert. Well, I'm not a rare extrovert, but I'm in the minority...introverts are dominant. And so, this whole idea of public engagement, particularly for that sort of real introvert, is scary and anxiety producing, because you're meant to be up on the stage and entertaining kids. And

you're meant to be going to science festivals and going 'oh, look at this flame' and 'look at this thing to pop' and so on, and that's hugely anxiety causing."

Research/teaching nexus perspective

Some participants (mainly ECRs) felt comfortable around the conceptualisation of the teaching/research nexus (Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014). Eta B is immersed, to the extent that the links become unconscious: "I do not sit down and say, okay, that fits to the principle...I think you do it, in a way you do it automatically." Theta A described the balance between the two aspects: "I really enjoy the teaching aspect of it, but I also enjoy getting stuck into a complex problem within my research role. So, I definitely see myself as a bit of both." Gamma S recommended that "...potentially it would be useful to have some sort of framework that matches [the nexus], with students being aware of the use of research within the teaching. Because even if it's being used, they're maybe not aware of it or they're not aware how to use it themselves...[because] students are not exposed to research before they come to university."

Gamma S describes herself as an academic, noting the "blurred lines" between teaching and research. However, she still views public engagement as a separate activity: "I think it's just more about being an academic now and contributing to the academic community, whether that's through research or teaching or maybe something else. Like we do other things too, with the public engagement that's a completely different thing, we'll maybe do events." In contrast, Zeta E expressed anger that the nexus cannot be achieved in practical terms: "There's a hell of a lot of bullshit surrounding all this nexus stuff. It's been introduced to us at [post-92 HEI], but practically on the ground it doesn't work, because we just either have teaching contracts or research contracts and that's it. And there's no structure at [post-92 HEI] to marry up research and teaching together from a lecturer's point of view, so it doesn't work." Similarly, Beta A described the situation at his post-92 HEI: "... at that institution I'm at and with the students I've got, it doesn't quite work, because for the most part there's still quite a gap between the end of Honours year at this institution and actually starting a proper research project, which is appropriate for the international research community."

Zeta E and Alpha K noted that, increasingly, recruitment strategies in post-92 HEIs tend to look to hire staff specialising either in lecturing or research, which can act as a barrier to achieving unity between teaching and research. This issue has also become a point of interest in the EU: “One discussion that is going on in [the EU] about should there be professors that do research only and no teaching. So, in [the EU] they, let’s say they call it the Humboldtscher principle. So, from Humboldt” (Eta B). Unity between teaching and research is a principle that most respondents work to but find hard to achieve in practical terms: “I don’t balance it. I think, certainly when I started it, that kind of expectation was there, that you would be involved in the research, teaching, and if you look at our activity plan there was a bit about outreach, so it was expected as part of our job...when I had more time, before things were landed on my plate and I took more things on, then there was a better balance” (Delta I).

The driving force affecting lecturers’ ability to make time to balance teaching and research is funding and this tends to highlight the bifurcation between tier 1 and 2 and tier 3 and 4 HEIs (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). Gamma S drew a comparison between permanent and temporary contracts as influencing factors: “I think there are different priorities. I think it relates a lot to money and how much money an institution has to spend on doing research and then doing teaching, and the balance between that with different members of staff. So, permanent members of staff will probably do both throughout their career. And then if there’s a project that’s been funded, a researcher will be brought in predominantly to do the research and to cover the main data collection analysis, and all that sort of stuff for the project. So, I think if an institution is successful in getting funding and a lot of funding, then they’re much more able to recruit temporary staff on a contract basis to do research projects.” This view is resigned and accepts that funding matters are out of her hands, a view shared by most respondents. As Theta A pointed out, lecturers who are constrained are forced to squeeze their working patterns to achieve that balance: “...it’s been the flexibility to kind of have more time for teaching, at one point, and then less time for research and then another side. Because depending on the institution that you’re at your flexibility may be limited by contract structure.”

Triple nexus – balanced perspective between R/T/Pe

Given that the balance between research and teaching is sometimes hard to achieve for academics in practice, the triple nexus is harder still, as Iota C explained: “I know that they usually describe it jokingly, but you do 50% research, 50% teaching and 50% admin. It’s a funny joke, but it’s also very quickly not funny anymore.” Despite this systemic barrier, all the respondents described a greater facilitation and ease with which they accessed the nexus, suggesting that the “culture change” has solidified in institutions (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021). This was summed up by Gamma S: “the more established and the bigger universities definitely have more sort of research teaching, public engagement ethos just embedded throughout with all staff, because they’re able to facilitate it. And they’ve got the admin staff definitely to support the academic staff, and the smaller universities, you know, I think they probably struggle a little bit more.” This suggests that PEPs are key to enabling this culture change, but none of the respondents working at post-92 HEIs reported operating within this type of structure.

The experience of academics working in post-92 HEIs tended to be thwarted by “boundary blocks” (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021). The primary block identified by Zeta E is economic capital:

A lot of public engagement people have taken me for granted and used and abused me. I over-subscribed to it initially in the early days because I wanted to get on and make links and network, but it hasn’t paid back for me. And also [sighs] what good is it? What good is it to me? There’s no incentive for me to do it anymore, you know. It’s supposedly meant to make me a better practitioner. I’d like some money, you know [laughter]. I’d like to be paid for it; you know.

Most of the post-92 respondents conduct some form of public engagement activity that is not part of an institutional incentive, either voluntarily or as a side interest (Gani *et al.*, 2024). Alpha K takes a pragmatic approach to sourcing funds and capacity (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016): “I had an idea when I was on holiday and I was at a design museum and I saw this thing there, which it was in the design museum because it

looked beautiful. But what it is, is a kind of molecular biology kit for the people, and I came back home, and I looked it up, very affordable etc. Now at the same time, I got contacted by [anon] High School looking to do this thing. So yeah, so I've kind of put together a wee plan to get the equipment with some money I'll get from somewhere and go out to the schools and do that.”

As Watermeyer and Rowe (2021) explained, when public engagement is an unquantified expectation within a job contract, this represents a problem for those academics who struggle to access either economic or academic capital. In general, the role of PEPs is considered non-academic within the professional services division of an HEI. This perception is problematic for Epsilon M, who described her shift in focus to public engagement, which has been detrimental to her research: “I wanted to keep [research] going, but I no longer view it as a core bit of my role, which is maybe sad in some aspects.” This corresponds with the assertion of Watermeyer and Rowe (2021) that “fault lines” exist between departments viewed as academic and non-academic. This highlights an equity gap whereby scientific authority is seemingly diluted when the conflicting demands of the triple nexus bring forth an *othering* of this expertise (Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019).

4.4.2 Are there similarities and differences in institutional identity in relation to the demands of teaching, research and public engagement?

Schlesinger, Selfe and Munro (2015) posit that the void between lecturers on stable contracts versus short-term persists, highlighting the precarity of academia, which Jennifer Platt first observed fifty years ago. Alpha K referenced his early career in the USA, describing an approach to manage the balance between teaching and research, which is autonomous: “...this was taught to me very early in my career as a scientist, you have to see yourself as being essentially self-employed. So, although you’re employed by the college or a university, you have to attract money in to pay your salary and for the work you want to do. So, when you get into a position, you’re either teaching, you get salary, you get funding associated with your teaching, you're bringing in research projects, which pays for some of your time, you're doing commercial work, which pays for some of your time.” This echoes the *American Dream* – that opportunities for individual prosperity are achieved through individual hard work.

Alpha K asserted that research activity is adversely affected by short-term contracts at his current institution: “I see a big move to a new [current post-92 HEI] to lots of part-time teaching. So, they’re not attracting professional scientists who work full time as scientists and then do the teaching, they’ve got people coming in for three or four hours a week, just give a quick lecture, go home again.” This is problematic, as McKenzie *et al.* (2018) predict “...divisions created within universities not along the lines of discipline expertise, but along activity”. There is less potential in post-92 HEIs to break free from this. Accordingly, Zeta E identifies primarily as a researcher but disclosed that this is not aligned to his contracted role: “I believe I’m an academic. I don’t believe I have a role that’s academic because of the lack, the inability of [post-92 HEI] to have a proper academic structure in promotional positions.”

In the context of public impact, the trend towards portfolio work is described by Carter (2020) in startling terms as a compulsory and serious “game” where academics “...must assemble a portfolio that demonstrates the impact, i.e., the social recognition, of their research”. This is problematic, particularly when the ability to assemble such evidence is negatively impacted by the funding, status and research intensity of a university. Aligning with the views of Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) and Papatsiba and Cohen (2020), Gamma S agrees that HEIs identified as upper tier 1 or 2 – Oxbridge and other ancient HEIs – are able to attract more funding to develop the teaching/research/engagement nexus, whereas “...the smaller universities, or maybe the less established ones, will struggle to get funding...” This has led her to seek greater security and work away from post-92 HEIs: “...I think with a more established university, the name is well known and it's just easier.” The security gained through longitudinal funding enables upper-tier HEIs to continuously build a portfolio of research, activating synergy between R/T/Pe, according to Gamma S:

The more established and the bigger universities definitely have more sort of research, teaching, public engagement ethos just embedded throughout with all staff, because they’re able to facilitate it. And they’ve got the admin staff definitely to support the academic staff, and the smaller universities, you know, I think they probably struggle a little bit more.

This is the experience of Beta A. He would like to deliver a final-year module to give students the option to deliver the module as an outreach project within schools. He sees the benefits of real-world research and the promotion of STEM in schools, but a systemic barrier exists: “I think if I was in a bigger institution with more than five members of staff, I may be able to offer that as a final-year module. I couldn’t offer it as a final module just now because I don’t have enough staff in order to have options.” Delta I is aware his time has changed as his teaching duties increased: “When I started, and when I had more time, before things were landed on my plate and I took more things on, then there was a better balance” between the demands of research and teaching. Beta A reported similar: “there’s that sort of kind of balance which needs to be kind of struck. And of course, you know, if I was really doing my job with engagement stuff and getting students to be really enthusiastic about [STEM Panel B], then ideally, they would go to a bigger, older university than the one that they’re at.”

Delta I has only ever experienced working at a post-92 HEI. His perceptions of institutional identity reveal that upper-tier HEIs link organisational identity to power and position at the risk of compromising teaching (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018): “I think the bigger Russell Group universities maintain their research and...they’ve got a mystique about them that they’re old, they’re traditional. But we’ve had students come from [ancient HEI] to [post-92 HEI], because of the lack of teaching support that they get.” Perceptions of the triple nexus for academics based at upper-tier, or pre-92, HEIs reveal a more tailored arrangement to support this aspect of practice. This is in line with the findings of Papatsiba and Cohen (2019) and Watermeyer and Rowe (2021), who note the superior ability of upper tier HEIs to leverage funds and professional services staff to support the triple nexus.

Iota C said of her ancient HEI that: “It’s very tailored...when it comes to analysing or evaluating public outreach...they give you ideas of ways on how you can evaluate the effectiveness of your outreach.” This is now the main function for Epsilon M, who supports her colleagues in STEM by “...facilitating or creating activities or discussing ways that we can engage kind of outwith our institution.” She also acknowledges that, where previously public engagement may have been regarded as a “bolt-on”, it is now more embedded: “I did a lot of public engagement previously, but I didn’t see that as

a main part of my role. I saw that as a kind of added value, whereas now it is a big part.”

Eta B lectures at an ancient HEI. He suggests that the triple nexus has no relationship to public engagement, which is a “bolt-on” completely divested from teaching: “I think my role as a teacher is not really a role of public engagement... Public engagement would be for me really like addressing the general public, going to schools, doing something at the Science Centre” (Eta B). Eta B’s perceptions underline the performativity of the impact agenda (Kenny, 2017): “...without the grant proposals we get nowhere. So, that takes a lot of time and I think that is what I do with research. Connected to this is of course also getting engaged with for example companies. Because, in order to get an impact for your research, you have to have a connection to the real world basically.”

In line with Baird and Elliott (2018), Beta A suggested that leverage of money by central administration in his post-92 HEI is out of his control, which represents a potential barrier to the triple nexus: “None of my submissions were world-leading, they were very much just okay. Whether or not I as an academic will ever see the funds which the university gets from my role in that submission is dubious. It will probably be lost in that centralised administration, because if you’re applying for a research grant, let’s say I need £100,000 for a particular piece of research. I need £100,000, I’m going to need to apply for £200,000 because the university will top slice 50% of that for centralised services.”

The issue of funding engagement activity is undoubtedly a barrier to the four lecturers at post-92 HEIs. All admitted that, often, public engagement is undertaken voluntarily with no central support for delivery. Alpha K expressed some cynicism, noting that his post-92 HEI “...do[es] really like to control their image on social media”. This obliquely suggests that it is a greater concern than funding PEPs. Zeta E has become so disillusioned that he no longer engages in mainstream outreach. He has developed a “... [side identity STEM outreach] effectively a trademark now in its own right, and I’ve taken on my Twitter feed and Facebook feed and everything, I’ve taken off the reference to [post-92 HEI] on it.” The findings indicate that public engagement work is under-supported and under-valued at post-92 HEIs, which has implications for the

triple nexus, meaning that impact is lost and public engagement fails to be measured at institutional level (Lo Presti and Marino, 2019).

4.4.3 Can Von Humboldtian ideals link research and teaching with public engagement?

The ECRs interviewed appeared most at ease with the concept of the teaching/research nexus (Brennan *et al.*, 2019). Pedagogical development is supported for Iota C, enrolled in a postgraduate academic practice certificate. This has been helpful in developing her practice as an educator and informing her perceptions of the teaching/research nexus: “It comes naturally obviously, the research we do in [STEM Panel B] we find most fascinating ourselves, so I think it comes naturally to try and when we need to find an example for something to illustrate it or to make it more inspiring to the students, to look in the pool of our own research.” Similarly, Eta B is unequivocal about the linkages between research and teaching: “I would identify primarily as a researcher, but I think as a researcher it’s also our duty in a way to teach...because you have to train the next generation of scientists.”

Although most respondents could give examples of the triple nexus in practice at postgraduate level, none of those interviewed were able to conceptualise the triple nexus at undergraduate level. The primary barrier was identified as lying with the research readiness of school leavers (McKenzie *et al.*, 2018). Practical tasks contribute towards research readiness, according to Iota C: “I guess that’s what they practise in the labs, right, where they do without Covid, ideally practical tasks and run experiments and take their own data, and that’s where their research skills are being developed.” However, Beta A pointed out that: “...many of the undergraduates have still got a year or two of growing up to do, especially sometimes you’ve got, you know, seventeen-year-olds straight in. So, they’re still in many cases relatively young, relatively immature, and still not got into good study habits, which you would have hoped they’d learned from school.” This can extend into the Honours year: “...they are not research-ready [laughter]. Actually, I don’t know if they are research ready after they finish their third year” (Eta B).

In general, respondents agreed that the skills required for research-readiness are not embedded at school, underlining the need to develop STEM activities in school that feed curiosity. Epsilon M sees that students have "...the creativity and the curiosity [...] from day one. I think the other things that come with formal research need to be developed like everything else." Research-readiness is arguably a state of being and Theta A is aware of his duty to develop this so that undergraduates can be supported: "...developing skills for research are part coming out of school but there's not a lot of (pause)...I wouldn't regard them as research-ready shall we say. But I... [want to support this], and we've talked about that within our programme design, we term it as scaffolding." In line with the findings of Kaasila *et al.* (2021), Theta A is supportive of the central role that RIT plays in developing students' readiness to enter working life. Given that research-readiness is underdeveloped in most undergraduate cohorts, this needs to be acknowledged and planned for to improve the links between R/T/Pe in STEM (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

4.4.4 Does this form of scholarly practice hold relevance for the creation of knowledge and re-configuration of teaching in the post-pandemic university?

The COVID-19 pandemic expedited alternative approaches to teaching and learning and in some cases used publicly available research to augment teaching practice. Theta A recalled his use of real-time COVID-19 infection data from open sources on Tableau Public (a free platform to explore and share data visualisations online) for undergraduate disease modelling lectures: "...it gives a little bit more colour to what you're doing. And the pandemic definitely assisted in adding colour to the modelling that I was doing." This highlights the dynamic potential of the triple nexus to enhance approaches to teaching and learning in applied science: "...we were at that point in the middle of a global pandemic, the [students] actually found a Lotka-Volterra model more in tune with what they were covering." However, this is harder to implement in pure science disciplines. For example, Beta A highlighted that, in some ancient HEIs, modules contain "...a lot more kind of pure stuff. They've got a little bit of [applied science], but an awful lot of string theory and graph theory and group theory." Adapting pure science theories is not straightforward: "It's very easy to see how history is told in many different ways, but it is pretty difficult in a very pure discipline" (Beta A).

The pivot in approaches to teaching and learning brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic has undoubtedly re-configured knowledge creation in HE (Crawford *et al.*, 2020). Notably, for some respondents, this pivot did not represent a significant change from the status quo. The teaching space occupied by Alpha K was predominantly digital before the pandemic and his HEI has historically made use of networked learning spaces because of the far-reaching locations of its campuses. Despite his “...worry about the students being just stuck in their house on a computer”, he observed that, after the lockdown eased, the pressure on physical spaces in his HEI sometimes lessened: “I mean we teach like this now, I mean that’s probably how we are going to teach in the future, we won’t go back...it’s more convenient as well, and uses less classrooms in the college.” The existence of a digital divide is still a barrier to delivery of teaching and learning, which Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth (2019) note is a barrier to student participation. Gamma S echoed this, reflecting that her own internet connection is unstable, affecting her ability to teach in real time: “it’s just not possible to sit in front of a computer and hope that your internet works...it was the only way of being able to [teach] because we had to do it online, we couldn’t do it in the classroom [I ended up] making videos, little videos.”

The possibilities for knowledge creation to be brought outside the university walls have led to some instances of public engagement for the participants, serendipitously feeding into the triple nexus. For example, Alpha K’s use of third spaces to deliver public seminars is a culture change catalysed by the pandemic (Schwartzman, 2020). Previously, seminars were “...held at the institute and we tried various VC things to expand it, but since COVID we actually just do them online and it’s fantastic. So, I think that’s something that we’ll just keep on doing.” The use of OERS to mimic experimental design during the pandemic has reinforced their utility as a simple educational device with applications for practical lab work in microscopy, chemical analysis and physics, according to Iota C, Delta I and Alpha K (Nordmann *et al.*, 2020). This supports a model for open practice to feed into an open research culture (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Theta A described the tenets of the open research agenda from his perspective: “I think that there is a move towards more...open-source teaching and research. Certainly, from the research side of things, it’s being pushed a lot by the journals that we’re submitting to, and therefore the universities need to embrace it because otherwise you won’t get published in journals.”

Publication through a variety of media supports routes to public engagement via blogs, tweets and forums, potentially widening access to university research, according to some of those interviewed. However, it is recognised that public engagement with research is limited within peer-reviewed journals. As Delta I observed, “having open access journal articles is great, but you write open access journal articles for an academic, you don’t write that for policymakers or for members of the public where your impact will come from. So, if I had more time, I would do more articles on LinkedIn or something, that would try to get more layman’s text.” Arguably, the advent of altmetrics paves a way to quantify this type of impact (Weingart and Guenther, 2016; Jünger and Fähnrich, 2019), but Theta A highlighted the nuances of public engagement within open-source data: “There are some notable academics who do develop packages as part of a research project, and you can submit kind of short report paper type things to specific journals on them. And I think maybe that’s how the academics are quantifying them, but I don’t know if they’re quantifying them as public engagement.”

Alpha K, Iota C and Delta I all mentioned using open-source digital alternatives for lab work with undergraduates during the pandemic. Alpha K explained his use of OERs as follows: “So, instead of having practicals based on lab, on benchwork, I’ve designed some practicals to look at protein structures using online tools, usually from other universities to be honest. Some of them I did develop myself, but these are open access, available to the entire community.” A new way of working is already happening through the open education movement (Weller, 2018): “anybody can read something that’s open access and there’s this perception that people aren’t smart enough to read it, and that’s totally not true, you know. Those things that are suitable for public consumption, that’s how researchers learn how to be researchers” (Gamma S). In relation to teaching and learning materials, Theta A is aware that his HEI is moving “...towards more open-source or publicly available kind of teaching materials”. In practice, Theta A has not been involved with the creation of OERs, but his research work has led him to contribute to open-source code using and sharing on open platforms such as GitHub:

...the other thing that I've done, kind of counts as public engagement, is very niche because I work with open-source software all the time...I use R mostly rather than Python, but with both packages they have add-ons. I was working with someone else's add-on package, and it didn't do what I wanted it to do [and] I wrote some code to deal with it. And they used it, and they amalgamated it into their add-on package, so that now everyone else that uses that add-on package has the behaviour that we might have expected previously. And that's the sort of thing that from a data science coding point of view, that...is another form of public engagement that doesn't get us anything but helps the open-source community.

Theta A pointed out that this type of contribution “doesn't get us anything”, implying that this has public impact but no institutionally recognised value. Public engagement initiatives are all too often linked to the impact agenda, which has been shown to be problematic when impact is directly linked to funding incentives. These can be hard to measure and provoke unintended effects such as malpractice and corruption (Baird and Elliott, 2018). I asked Theta A if he could see a way that this aspect of *missed impact* could be somehow afforded a value by his institution: “...it would be very difficult for them (post-92 HEI) to kind of take it into the public engagement machine so to speak, because it's still very technical.”

Epsilon M takes a broader view on the ways in which public engagement can be quantified as “...anything that you can show that you've added value, and you can answer not just from a university perspective is always really, really positive. I always ask students, you know, what do you think will make you stand out?” In practice, Epsilon M is aware that the triple nexus supports undergraduate employability skills: “I think anything that can add value, and public engagement is probably a really good one because a lot of students are really enthusiastic, really excited about sharing or have other skills to share, you know, not necessarily standing in front of people, but maybe you know, editing a really great video or being able to create a fantastic worksheet, you know, or advising somebody on career opportunities. I think it takes so many forms, so I think there's always something that you can contribute and that can add that adds value when people are looking at employability skills.”

The effect of COVID-19 highlighted the resilience of students, according to Epsilon M: “I would say definitely with public engagement and outreach, the pandemic has obviously stopped the very traditional way of doing things. Going into schools, being at a science fair. We’ve had to look at different ways of doing it and I have found that the students have been absolutely amazing at changing things and adapting.” In contrast, lecturers may be less resilient than students: “We survived the pandemic, but we’ve had to change our teaching style and I think that teaching style is going to be with us for a while, and I think that’s fine for new academics coming in because that’s what they’re used to. I think people like me who’ve done it for seven years and longer are going to find that’s the struggle, trying to keep up with the demand of what the next generation want as they come through” (Delta I).

4.5 Autoethnographic findings

As Sloan and Bowe (2014) have stated, “Having isolated phenomenal themes, one re-writes the theme while interpreting the meaning of the phenomenon or lived experience.” After the stage 1 interviews were completed, I used autoethnography to reflect on the findings generated and interpret the meaning derived to share with interview participants. Using the themes derived from research questions, autoethnographic writing contributed towards an understanding of cultural norms from the lived experience of those interviewed (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010).

Table 17: Overview of cross-cutting themes interpreted through autoethnography.

Theme	
T1	Letter from America: a song – understanding core experiences of the triple nexus through identity and culture.
T2	The Lab of Curiosity and The Messy Scientist: two stories – supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness.
T3	Time to get Woke!: memes – using digital spaces to support public engagement.
T4	The Pedagogue’s Sonnet: a poem – hierarchies and institutional identity.
T5	Finding my no: a poem – reflections on practice and recommendations.

Themes

T1: The R/T/Pe triple nexus

T2: Supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness

T3: Using digital spaces to support public engagement activity

T4: Hierarchies and institutional identity

T5: Reflections on practice and recommendations

4.5.1 Letter from America – T1 understanding core experiences of the triple nexus through identity and culture

The triple nexus linkages frequently overlap, but they are hard to quantify for all those interviewed, which reveals the ways that the “impact agenda” has insidiously progressed to disenfranchise the role of the educator (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018). Alpha K observed the combative landscape associated with funding experienced by his colleagues: “...it does all come down to funding. But I’m okay for funding, so I don’t mind. I’m not scrambling for money really.” Added to this, the neoliberal superstructure of the REF, a type of academic league table, incentivises research, and the reporting of impact case studies is directly linked to funding mechanisms (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Marques and Powell, 2019). Alpha K has a sardonic view of performativity within the nexus: “I don’t always feel the need to record the impact of things [laughter]. Sometimes I think you should just do something to interest people.”

Lecturers experienced identity loss when it came to submitting REF-returnable research: “It’s not teaching, it’s not research, it’s a kind of commercial thing” (Beta A). There is considerable pressure, “...formal pressure that you must bring in the funding or else” (Epsilon M). For Gamma S, her previous academic role was constricted and limited by this pressure:

In one job it just really was a struggle to get funding. It was just sort of a constant cycle of trying, doing funding applications, trying to get funding, trying to do projects. There was almost too many plates spinning to be able to focus on any one thing, you know, with enough, it’s like there just wasn’t enough hours in the day to do everything that was needed and to keep things moving. And so, that is one reason why I moved to one of the bigger universities.

Funding is constrained by policy and HEI governance: “There’s a mixture of lack of funding for STEM subjects, lack of industry to help focus Scottish Government, or UK government...and it comes down to universities’ budgets and how they want to spend their money” (Delta I). Discussion with Alpha K highlighted the pressures on academic funding in Scotland, compared to the more expansive open funding opportunities that he experienced when working in America, which aligned with the experience of Eta B:

Here I am independent, and I don’t have a supervisor who provides the funding basically. In the US...there was a bit more room to do research that would have benefit in the long term...these long-term plans that might generate impact later on, which could be much greater, but there is just nobody funding this kind of thing.

Beta A agreed: “If you want to get anywhere in terms of research, then you’re doing it in your own time. Unless you get research funding.” Given that four respondents pinpointed the funding mechanisms in the USA, I wanted to interpret this in the context of the *American Dream*, whereby America is symbolic of an exciting cultural otherness and a place where dreams can be made into reality (Elliot, 2018). Zeta E notes, “...all the things that I see in America resonate greatest with me, because they have a much better attitude. A much better attitude, and I know I’d get on very well, but I think I’ve

probably left it too late in my life to do that now. In a healthy department in some middle-ranking American university, with a supportive boss and head of department and everything, I know I'd do very well in that environment, yeah. That's where I'd thrive best." I wanted to explore the *American Dream* as *The Scottish Dream* and how this could support the triple nexus. My first interaction with Alpha K sparked me to think about the *American Dream* and how this may or may not fit into Scottish cultural identity in the twenty-first century. My reflection on our first interview finished with a line from The Proclaimers' 1987 song, *Letter from America*, which explores the Scottish diaspora:

*I wonder my blood will you ever return
To help us kick the life back to a dying mutual friend...?*

(Proclaimers, 1987)

In Scotland, many post-92 HEIs are located in third-tier cities (cities which have been impacted by socio-cultural change because of de-industrialisation) and STEM is foundational to scholarly, business and public activity in third-tier cities (Brabazon, 2019). Delta I observes of his work in a third-tier city that, "I've got KTP projects, so they're a mixture of research and industrial engagement...there is an industrial team, and there's a KTP associate who's employed to do that job...it's not so much research as commercial, but we get research outputs from it, so we get manuscripts, we get papers, and we get some sort of scientific knowledge as well." Brabazon (2019) suggests that these cities can ably pivot from an industrial economy to a knowledge economy, forming the premise for my song, an interpretation of *Letter from America*, which co-locates areas of deindustrialisation in Scotland alongside the North American diaspora (Leith and Sim, 2020).

The original song was a chart hit and arguably blazed a trail for Scottish popular music artists to openly flaunt their cultural identity. The Proclaimers were reportedly told to tone down their regional accents on the release of the record (Leith and Sim, 2020), underlining the persistent deference that still abounds within Scottish cultural identity (Alpha K, Delta I and Gamma M). The lines "...will you ever return, To help us kick the

life back to a dying mutual friend...” appeal to the Scottish cultural diaspora “...across the ocean...” and reflect this very Scottish cultural problem. The second verse of my interpretation references Professor Sir David MacMillan of Bellshill, South Lanarkshire, Scotland. Professor MacMillan left Scotland in the mid-1990s to pursue a career in the USA “...across the ocean...”, which led to him being jointly awarded the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 2021. In the spirit of comedic deference typical of Scotland, Professor MacMillan bet \$1,000 that his award was a prank, soon to find out that this was not the case. MacMillan, a keen football fan, announced on BBC Radio Scotland’s football show *Off the Ball* that he would donate the entire £405,000 prize money to underprivileged students in Scotland (Kramer, 2022).

Deference as a form of Scottish cultural identity proliferates and this was recognised by all in the study, including the respondents not brought up in Scotland, who have a civic identity as *New Scots* (Arnott and Ozga, 2016). My interpretation explores these facets of identity construction in *The Scottish Dream*. The song re-purposes *Letter from America* (Proclaimers, 1987) to a modern-day interpretation that imagines a scientist reflecting on the challenges between providing outreach and securing research funding. The lyrics link people and places in the song to represent the modern-day challenges and opportunities for STEM based on the interview findings. The original song charts the depopulation of the Highlands associated with the times of the Highland Clearances and draws parallels with the economic migration and depression of the Central Belt of Scotland in the 1970s and 1980s (Leith and Sim, 2020). Drawing on this, I used songwriting as a means of dialogic communication with respondents to explore how the concept of the science brain-drain affects Scotland.

The Nobel Prize has worldwide recognition and is noted for the consequent efforts of the Sir Alfred Nobel Foundation to support the popularisation of science. Furthermore, Hargittai (2022) observed that Professor MacMillan’s 2022 award “...is uplifting [as] chemistry in its classical sense is still capable of discoveries that merit Nobel Prizes”. The majority of previous awardees were in applied fields (biochemistry, physiology or medicine). Beta A noted the difficulties for science communication in pure disciplines, lamenting, “I would find it quite difficult to talk to a general audience and make my research that interesting or excitable.” For Theta A, “...those ideas that could maybe bring in research money or add something to a class can be very difficult” for those

who work in pure, rather than applied, research, making the triple nexus a challenge. However, Zeta E asserted that a teaching-led approach to the triple nexus builds skills that assisted him to develop a way to explain pure science concepts perhaps more abstract than applied science:

80% of my students at my first demonstration understand what I'm trying to show them, and I'd say, by the end of a module, 95–98% do roughly, I'm guessing. So, it builds up from very basic fundamentals, and just I think...most people know already what I'm going to tell them, most people know. Everyone has it in them in their intuition usually, I just have to enable them. I'm a facilitator, which enables them to grasp in some sort of language, whether that language is English or maths, or some sort of schematic diagram, to realise and accept consciously what they already know intuitively. I believe that most people know already what I'm about to teach them.

Letter from America makes references to the Highland Clearances of the 1800s (Leith and Sim, 2020). Historically, the cultural norms of Scotland were oppressed following the Act of Proscription in 1746, which saw the prohibition of Highland dress and outlawed the Gàidhlig language. This reflects Scottish identity. In modern times, historical oppression has informed Scottish identity and culture, amplified through comedic deference (Zhang and Pearce, 2020). Delta I joked that, “I’ve been slightly unhinged this week, just babbling to each other, or singing songs.” He claims that this is characteristic of his cultural upbringing: “...in the west of Scotland, we do tend to have quite a dry sense of humour, and I think that ties in with the identity.” He went on to describe his use of “gallows humour” as an antidote in times of stress: “so you know how your jokes or you think you know how your jokes are going to land, but sometimes [my colleague] manages to surprise me with some of his really bad jokes...when you’ve got everything landing on your plate, you’ve got to laugh otherwise pretty much I think you’d be sitting on your desk every single day just not wallowing, but I think just wanting to bang your head off the wall.”

I placed verses from the original song alongside an adapted version of the song that explores the twenty-first-century cultural identity of Scottish STEM academics. The

opening verse mentions two well-known Scottish scientists who rose to fame in the period of the Scottish Enlightenment. Significantly, in this era, a surge took place in a distinctly Scottish educational identity, which is still evident over 250 years later (Arnott and Ozga, 2016; Ozga, 2020; Leith and Sim, 2020). A closer connection between science and society reportedly emerged during the period (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018) and the opening verse acknowledges the public outreach work of two renowned Scottish scientists who willingly and openly engaged with the public during this time: John Anderson (1726–1796) and James Clerk Maxwell (1831–1879).

John Anderson 1726–1796

James Clerk Maxwell 1831–1891

Figure 15: John Anderson and James Clerk Maxwell. Both photographs unknown author, licensed under CC BY-NC.

Both these men reached out to share their scientific findings within the public domain using novel techniques such as performance and poetry. John Anderson was a physicist, who founded Anderson’s Institute (the forerunner to the University of Strathclyde). His identity as a science explainer and public communicator of science – *Jolly Jack Phosphorus* – was built through his enthusiasm for letting off fireworks and explosives in demonstrations performed in night classes delivered to the public in Glasgow. Some scientists were dismissive of his methods and he was reportedly

marginalised (Kidd, 2017). However, he left money to build Anderson's Institute, which was noted for its open and inclusive welcome to Scottish women, who were able to attend classes there as early as 1796.

Alpha K likened James Clerk Maxwell to "...Scotland's version of Einstein". Maxwell formalised the relationship between electricity and magnetism, which he communicated through the medium of poetry (Illingworth, 2019). Maxwell wrote eloquently and persuasively on matters of science communication, political barriers within his academic field and personal reflections on his work. Merging poetry into science communication is a dialogic method enabling creative communication between scientists and non-scientists, potentially enabling diverse methods to enact a two-way dialogue (Illingworth, 2020). The development of the song lyrics from interview dialogue with Alpha K was received well: "...we are encouraged to do [a] kind of self-evaluation of our practice and things. That's a very formal process. We have forms to fill in, which isn't that creative. So, yeah, I mean I liked [your song] ...scientists are quite artistic in some senses."

The first verse of my song is haunted and plaintive and, [in the live version](#), I adopt a minor key to sing them. The lyrics aim to build momentum to a major key to disclose the lived experience of STEM academics today and how they juggle expectations to find funding, carry out research and engage with the public. The final verses explore locations within Scotland. The places named and chosen for highlighting in my song are identified through interviews as satellite locations close to de-industrialised, third-tier cities that have suffered from the socio-economic effects of the loss of the manufacturing and chemical industries in Scotland (Brabazon, 2019; Leith and Sim, 2020). It highlights the Polmadie Burn, a sickly, yellow-coloured stream that flows into the River Clyde in Glasgow. This waterway is one of the most polluted in Europe, maintaining high levels of toxicity as a direct result of historic environmental pollution from the J. and J. White chemical factory (García-Lamarca and Gray, 2021; Sim *et al.*, 2018). The polluting effects of industry on the River Clyde, for example, were highlighted by Delta I, who described his use of real-life research to support the triple nexus with undergraduate students: "[The Clyde] ...has just been a dumping ground for everything from shipbuilding to dye manufacturing...the further back in time you go you identify pollution down here caused by something sixty to seventy years ago. Students get the experience of a real-life project, whilst doing their education."

The Scottish Dream (2023)

**When you go, will you send back
a letter from America?**

**Take a look at the research
from Maxwell to Anderson...**

Broke off from the lab bench

the other day

*I spend my time, looking for
funding streams to flow my way...*

But is it pointless? Or is it fruitless?

When I've barely time,

for making slime,

And outreach anyway?

Chorus

Across the ocean, in the ivy league

It's quite a stun, Our Davie's won

The Nobel Prize I'm all intrigued.

We should have held you,

we should have told you

But you know our sense of timing

we always wait too long...

Shawfield; Steventon; Polmadie; Bellshill no more...

Letter from America (1987)

**When you go, will you send back
a letter from America?**

**Take a look up the rail track
from Miami to Canada...**

Well broke off from work

the other day

*Spent the evening thinking about
all the blood that flowed away...*

*Across the ocean to the second
chance,*

I wonder how it got on

when it reached the promised land?

Chorus

Look at the ocean, try hard to imagine

The way you felt the day you sailed

from Wester Ross to Nova Scotia.

We should have held you,

we should have told you

But you know our sense of timing

we always wait too long...

Bathgate, Linwood; Methil; Irvine no more...

4.5.2 The Lab of Curiosity – T2 supporting undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness

Meeting Eta B was a real lightbulb moment for me. They recounted a description of the teaching/research nexus with perfect ease and fluency, despite English being their second language. However, this was Eta B's state of being, not a buzzword (Bensaude, 2014; Wall, 2018) – which underlines the parity between research and teaching that von Humboldt aimed to achieve with his treatise on the Internal and External Organisation of the Higher Scientific Institutions in Berlin (von Humboldt, 1810). Even more appealing, Eta B describes this parity by using a buzzword that does exactly what it says on the tin – “the Humboldtscher principle”.

Autoethnographic reflection, 2021

The dark and uncertain times in the funding landscape precipitated by Brexit meant that, as Iota C and Eta B pointed out, it is **Game Over** in the UK when the funding runs out for an academic in a STEM Panel B discipline (Crawford *et al.*, 2020). There is little scope to allow curiosity in practical lab work in the UK, according to Eta B, which is different from the situation in Germany, the crucible of Humboldtian ideals. This is a reflection of the problematised nature of the teaching/research nexus in the UK (McKinley *et al.*, 2020). Building on these phenomena and using imaginative variation (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019), I constructed a story following Eta B's interview that draws on Lewis Carroll's children's novel *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* (Frick and Brodin, 2019). This allegory instantiates what Leigh and Bailey (2013) term as *embodiment*, which may have useful outcomes for reflective practice in education.

In the original story, seven-year-old Alice boldly follows a white rabbit down a hole and enters a mystical fantasy world after she makes an ill-considered decision to drink an unknown drink labelled “drink me” and then eat an unknown cake labelled “eat me”. The results are unexpected. While transmorphing, Alice cries with despair at first, and then swims away on her sea of tears to a mystical land. This echoes the shifting parameters of academic identity (Frick and Brodin, 2019; McCune, 2019). As Alice enters Wonderland, she finds it “Curiouser and curiouser...”. Significantly, this novel plays with the notions of logic through an illogical construction of literary nonsense to

present an alternative or flipped reality. Similarly, the tumultuous challenges brought about by COVID-19 (Crawford *et al.*, 2020; Schwartzman, 2020) have challenged lecturers to flip their classrooms to adapt to the unknown and infuse a sense of curiosity within their teaching practice (Erbil, 2020). Elements of *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* are retained in the re-told version to enhance the allegorical nuances of the original story using similar words and images.

The Lab of Curiosity: a story

Gingerly, Alice knocked on the door of the Lab of Curiosity. No one was in. Once or twice, she had peeped in, but felt that it was not the place for a girl who wore a crinoline dress and pinafore. But it was too late – as she lingered at the threshold, behold, the white rabbit raced past her, and she knew she had to follow him.

As the lab door opened, Alice was sucked into a vortex... Down, down, down. The white rabbit was still in sight and hurrying her along the way to a tall, dark hall, at the entrance to the main lab. In an instant, the rabbit was gone through a tiny door that locked behind him. The lab bench ahead of Alice had been pre-arranged in an orderly fashion. To the left of the bench was a secure cabinet labelled *curious chemicals for catalytic change*. There lay within two vials labelled with beautiful writing.

Brexit brain-drain (shrinking catalyst)

Puzzling proposals (growth catalyst)

Figure 16: Image from autoethnographic artefact. A story - Brexit brain-drain and puzzling proposals. [This photo](#) by unknown author is licensed under [CC BY-NC](#).

Alice stood at the edge of the bench. She knew she had to get into the Lab of Curiosity but was unsure how. “Well, if I use puzzling proposals,” said Alice, “and if it makes me grow larger, I can reach the key; and if I use Brexit brain-drain and it makes me grow smaller, I can creep under the door; so, either way I'll get into the Lab of Curiosity, and I don't care which happens!” With that, Alice boldly grasped both vials and turned towards the lab bench.

Fin.

The story echoes some of the challenges faced by women in STEM (McKinnon and O'Connell, 2020): “Once or twice, she had peeped in...” the lab, but felt a strong sense of imposter syndrome (Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021). This reflects conversations with Iota C: “I am very in favour of women in STEM, probably marked by my own experience... [as a student] ...I didn't have a single, not one, woman lecturer, not even a supervisor, you know when you do small group supervisions or in the lab, there was no one. There was absolutely not a single woman ahead of me in any role, way, shape, or form involved.” Worryingly, Iota C is aware that access for women in STEM is under threat: “...there's much bigger systemic problems that cause this lack. So, there's no amount we can do to go to high schools and try and inspire women to persist with [STEM Panel B] if the system afterwards is hostile or not encouraging.” However, Epsilon M is a mid-career academic who sees a longitudinal change coming: “I do feel that the only way we are going to be able to challenge these attitudes...is when we reach that tipping point where there just are enough women, so it doesn't become an anomaly.”

Epsilon M shares the story of her move from industry in STEM Panel B to academia, which was precipitated by a complete loss of agency within her role in industry: “I thought that I had the best role in the world, but toward the end changes in the organisation, changes in managers, it was actually gender-based.” Similarly, in the story, Alice's loss of agency is represented by her dress. The structure of the crinoline dress Alice wore in John Tenniel's illustrations was a fashion current to the time of the book, though her apron hints at practicality. The Lab of Curiosity is told through a gender-based lens to share the lived experience of women scientists, who, like Alice in her dress, are limited by expectations of gender norms: “I started with wanting to

develop my research more, Covid has made that kind of impossible, if I'm honest. But it's given me the opportunity maybe not to be stressed about that as much, because there was really not much I could do. I was having to home-school two kids in primary school, there was triple teaching load, there was not time really to do anything else" (Epsilon M).

Creativity, according to Frick and Brodin (2019), is a mute phenomenon in doctoral education. Accordingly, I set out to discover whether creative writing in autoethnography could be used as a process to interpret and extend my thinking on the phenomena isolated from interviews with the research participants (Starr, 2014). Literary techniques such as imagery and alliteration were used to develop the aesthetic quality of the interpretation of common phenomena amongst respondents (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010), including *Curious Chemicals of Catalytic Change* and *Brexit Brain Drain*. Brexit was mentioned by all but one respondent: "...in the UK especially because of Brexit there are less people coming...this could be a serious issue" (Eta B); "I'm absolutely gutted about Brexit. We have less access perhaps to the European funding, and recruitment has been absolutely a nightmare. We need special funding now if we want to attract students from Europe, because they're classed as immigrants" (Iota C). All those interviewed agreed that Brexit has contributed to academic precarity, particularly Eta B, who is at the start of his career: "it's extreme uncertainty because you don't know will there be a position anywhere."

The story ends with a cliffhanger – the intention to draw the reader in – but, in contrast, the academics interviewed do not feel as bold as Alice, who jumped into the unknown. The white rabbit represents funding streams, which are hard to reach, as Delta I, Gamma S and Beta A agree. The set-up of the orderly lab bench mimics the constraints of a teaching programme where students are set up not to fail (Delta I and Eta B), but this does not reflect real-life lab conditions: "we never have the perfect control experiment" (Iota C). Eta B explained that Scottish undergraduates at his HEI are given very little chance to make mistakes, which constricts their autonomy or agency to conduct research. This contrasts with his previous experience at an HEI in the EU. He is concerned that undergraduates in his discipline are not research-ready (McKenzie *et al.*, 2018): "The thing is so you learn from your mistakes, and in a way it's that everything is organised, at least with us and I think it is similar in other places,

there is no real place to fail. And everything's organised in a way that it is also not easy to fail" (Eta B). Academic identity can be torn between fitting within these constraints and a wish to "slip under the door", to the Lab of Curiosity which echoes the assertion that academics can fall into "depressive complicity" whilst trying to meet multiple managerial measures to quantify academic quality (Burrows, 2012). Delta I explained: "As long as we meet the 85% pass target for each module...if you're in red you've got to explain why your students are failing. They don't [consider] that it could be the cohort that had a particular problem...it's just why are these students not passing? So, it gets demoralising, you can put in as much effort as you can to help your students, but nobody's recognising it at all."

4.5.3 The Messy Scientist – T2 Vygotsky's theory in action

The second story I wrote interprets the ways in which agency, curiosity and independence can be used to support research-mindedness in undergraduates using vignette analysis (Pitard, 2015). Cultural norms are illuminated in the story of *The Messy Scientist* – a scientist who does not have an orderly lab bench and is not constrained by a need *not* to make mistakes. The messy scientist deals with real-world problems and integrates R/T/Pe: "When they get to see real-life science, and it's messy, and it doesn't work and there's a lot of non-results, it's quite good. It helps build up their resilience a little bit for when they go to the workplace, but also it helps them potentially when they go into their PhD that stuff goes wrong all the time with a PhD" (Delta I) (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). The story references the Polmadie Burn, one of the most polluted waterways in Europe (García-Lamarca and Gray, 2021; Sim *et al.*, 2018). This obliquely references Delta I, who explained his use of real-life research to support undergraduate teaching and learning looking at pollution on the River Clyde (Crow, Rawcliffe and Harris, 2019; Tight, 2016).

The Messy Scientist – A vignette

As the lab bench digital stop clock concludes its allotted time, the audience is listlessly impressed by the expected outcome of the experiment at hand. Even a hydrogen pop test experiment has lost its *je ne sais quoi* for these world-weary undergrads who sat through the standard school STEM engagement programmes. But, after all, if it hadn't been for that STEM stand-up in schools project parachuting into the soft underbelly of

the primary school in a post-industrial SIMD deprived area, would the same fifty pairs of eyes be staring back at me now?

The messy scientist relishes the hitherto unknowns and acknowledges that failure is part of success. Whether that is because they worked at the coalface of industry before they joined academia or because they have seen their students grow through engagement with KTP projects is up for debate. What shines through is their curiosity and acceptance of the unknown. They get that these undergrads need life skills when they leave the cossetted confines of academia. Resilience is right up there, top of the list.

But how resilient is the messy scientist? In lab conditions, all the world is a stage, and they are merely a player on it, but at home their personality is retiring – they can be downright shy and shrink to the corners of remarkability. This unremarkable status is maintained in their teaching appraisal reviews – provided, that is, that 85% of the fifty pairs of eyes pass their modules. There's no room for messy results or qualitative attainment as the funding rug will be pulled from under their feet if they fail to ensure that this result is achieved in a living lab populated by messy, complicated human beings who don't dance to the tune of neoliberalism.

Messy science and messy learning bring the experiential to the experiment. Throw in a bit of real-life research and you've explained why you'll not be going swimming in the Polmadie Burn* on the River Clyde or using the rope swing slung across the branches of the trees alongside the burn, which seems more deadly than a game of chicken on the M74. Wicked problems like these, where pure science meets social science, have no set answer, no right or wrong, and many different viewpoints. This is where the science gets messy, and the curiosity of knowledge creation unfolds.¹

The vignette builds a picture of a scientist formerly employed in industry who now works in academia, which is primarily informed through the core experiences of those

¹ In 2021, the Daily Record reported the danger of the situation and noted that children had erected a rope swing adjacent to the toxic burn - Williams, C. and Easton, K. (2021) 'Burn flowing 'toxic soup' into River Clyde 'glows green' with cancer-causing chemical', The Daily Record, 22 January 2021. Available at: <https://www.dailyrecord.co.uk/news/scottish-news/burn-flowing-toxic-soup-river-23366825> (Accessed: 17 March 2023).

respondents who worked in industry prior to academia (Delta I, Beta A, Alpha K and Epsilon M) (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). The opening line in *The Messy Scientist* uses assonance – “stop clock concludes...listlessly impressed...” as a literary device to slow the rhythm and mood of the vignette. The words suggest an audience that is not engaged, while alliteration describes the “parachuting” of “...standard school STEM...” activity from academia to the public domain (Chubb, Fouché and Sadeh Kengah, 2021). Orritt and Powell (2020) posit that scientists can promote engagement by using language more creatively: “I think that science is really creative though, just people need to find that” (Gamma S). Using *eidetic variation* to interpret the findings of the interviews, the opening paragraph underlines the importance of knowing your audience when it comes to public engagement (Davies, 2020). Theta A agrees: “...it’s difficult, because both teaching and research in their way are public engagement activities, but it’s often depending on which part...what the audience is, or the type of public engagement. Because a lot of the time as academics and as researchers and teachers, we could be better at working with a wider audience.”

The findings show there are strong links between industry and academia in HEIs located in third-tier cities (Brabazon, 2019), and these are often met through KTPs. According to Delta I: “I’ve had students doing their Honours project and their Master’s project on the KTPs that we’ve been involved in. So, they get the experience of a real-life project, whilst doing their education.” On the other hand, Gamma S sees public engagement with a wider view than its commercial aspect. Of a school project, she said: “I developed a programme for primary schools and early secondary...the idea was that you spend a couple of weeks during your science class, going out and investigating and using what’s available in your local area...encouraging that research-mindedness from a very early age, which I think is really important and I don’t just think it’s important for students that are planning to come to university.”

Beta A and Delta I work at post-92 HEIs in de-industrialised areas of Scotland that attract students from “...very low SIMD 20 schools...” (Beta A). Funding in these HEIs is often geared towards a teaching-intensive approach and Delta I sees this as advantageous to helping students develop skills and align to the triple nexus: “[In] the analytical lab that I’ve been talking about with all the equipment, expensive equipment, our students get to use that on a week-to-week basis, they actually get the hands-on

experience of how they work. They get to see how it works in real person; they get to use them. At [ancient HEI], they see videos of it in a lab, and there's like seventy or eighty folks in a lab and there's just a demonstrator showing how it works. That's not going to help them when they go for a job as a lab technician." None of the respondents attached to an upper-tier HEI had a background in industry and they did not discuss how KTPs can link to the triple nexus. This suggests that ancient or pre-92 HEIs continue to derive the majority of research funding from UK research councils, rather than KTPs, as Hewitt-Dundas (2012) has pointed out.

Resilience is highlighted in the story, and this is an important aspect of academic identity that is bolstered by public engagement and real-life research activity for most respondents (Gani *et al.*, 2024). This has been particularly important during the pandemic: "I don't know if I feel great after every lecture I give online, but certainly [after] lab work, or field work [I do]" (Alpha K). Delta I thrives on the buzz of public engagement: "I like doing it and I like trying to show off what I do and get people interested." However, public engagement forces academics unwillingly out of their comfort zones: "Some outreach stuff, I'm not that keen on it [laughter]" (Alpha K). Zeta E's idiosyncratic humour and energy is the anchor of his public-facing arsenal, which has made him an award-winning scientist for public engagement and teaching. However, he gives me the impression that his love for public engagement is forced at times, sardonically commenting that, "...you're meant to be going to science festivals and going 'oh, look at this flame' and 'look at this thing to pop' and so on, and that's hugely anxiety causing."

The story describes a "living lab populated by messy, complicated, human beings", underlining the tensions between pure science and the social understandings of human-ness (Knoblauch, 2021). Beta A is resolute – pure science *cannot* engage broader audiences: "As for kind of research-led public engagement, there's none from me at all. I would find it quite difficult to talk to a general audience and make my research that interesting or excitable." Beta A feels that the same applies to students: "If I made an outreach module for the final year, I'd have a whole bunch of students going, 'No, I can't do that. I can't go out to schools, and I can't present, and I can't talk to people about [STEM Panel B]." Eta B highlights curiosity as a way to scaffold learning and teaching in pure disciplines. He cited an instance from a materials

science module where “...the student was really interested in it...why is it so interesting? Why is it better than the other one? ... I think **that’s what I want**, is that the student asks the question – why is this happening?” Similarly, as Alice enters Wonderland, she finds it “Curiouser and curiouser...” and the Lab of Curiosity aims to build on the notion that unexpected results and the autonomy to make mistakes is an essential aspect of the theory of proximal learning that Vygotsky preponed and this can support a deeper engagement with research (Shvarts and Bakker, 2019). Nonetheless, developing research-readiness through curiosity and allowing room to make mistakes at undergraduate level is not easy. Middle managers tell lecturers: “I want to see pass rates; I want to see progression rates” (Beta A), so undergraduates are cossetted to “...meet the 85% pass target for each module” (Delta I).

4.5.4 Time to get woke!: T3 Memes – using digital spaces to support public engagement

Meme is a term that originates from ancient Greek but was formalised by evolutionary biologist Richard Dawkins, who coined the term from the Greek *mimeme* as a way of describing a unit of cultural information spread by imitation, similar to genetics (Beskow, Kumar and Carley, 2020; Iloh, 2021). Dawkins argued that cultural transmission creates a pathway to evolution thorough imitation, variation, selection and retention. This connects to constructs of identity in terms of adaptation and self-enhancement, which is appealing to a qualitative researcher in terms of the ways in which memes can aid dialogic rapport building (Gregg, Sedikides and Gebauer, 2011). Ironically, Dawkins, who is a “visible scientist”, is recognised for his achievements in the public communication of science but has also been critiqued for his default to the deficit model of science communication (Weingart and Guenther, 2016). He has “...rarely reflected on the diversity of publics of science, and even less on the diversity of communication to those publics” (Trench, 2008). Meme transfer as an action that modifies and re-shapes culture, as opposed to the transfer of meme images, arguably supports socio-cultural creativity in digital spaces. Consequently, memes were used to interpret some interview findings.

In this meme image, my intention was to create an image that combined humour with a critique on Richard Dawkins to amplify the findings of the interview with Zeta E (Beskow, Kumar and Carley, 2020). The image of Dawkins is grey and monotone,

contrasting against a cultural parody of the advertising slogan “Get Coke” in the second image (Donnelly, 2009). Zeta E described the moment when they become “woke” or “awoke”: “The word has been hijacked by the right-wing kind of media in the past year. Woke is someone who’s socially aware. Aware of social justice and...well, they are awake, they have been awoken. They are awake.” This aligns with contemporary debates in STEM, which centre on inclusivity, intersectionality and equity (Weingart, Joubert and Connaway, 2021; Canfield *et al.*, 2020; Selin *et al.*, 2017).

This Photo by Unknown is licensed under CC BY-SA. Image created in canva by Lucy Beattie.

Figure 17: Meme image "Diversity drought? Get Woke!" from interview with Zeta E.

Digital spaces and social media have significant potential for academics to reach a broader audience (Jarreau *et al.*, 2019). They are disruptive, not constrained by peer review, and can transmit information in real time (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019). Social media spaces are democratic – access is not restricted or hidden behind a paywall, which supports routes to open science (Pownall *et al.*, 2021). However, the majority of respondents felt unsure about using social media for personal engagement: Theta A has an academic blog, but is “...not active on social media, or YouTube”.

Alpha K is “...not on Twitter and I’m not even on Facebook...[sighs]...maybe if somebody kind of talked me through it a bit, I guess I’m a bit wary of it... [I could do] with a bit of guidance”. Similarly, Iota C keeps her social media strictly professional: “on Twitter I’m more of a grey mass, I’m really very reluctant to be too much in the public domain. So, mostly it’s probably just likes and re-tweets, but I think any genuine content that is from me must be absolutely minimal.” Institutional tweeting was found to be functional and bland. For example, Beta A runs his “[research] group’s Twitter account, which will just be, you know, hope your Higher grades are good, looking forward to meeting you for the group, all that sort of thing”.

Two respondents reported being more active in their contributions to social media. Epsilon M has grown more confident: “...in terms of my Twitter feed, it did start off as very work-related...[now]...it has descended to I think a personal account of how I view the world and things that are I guess increasingly important to me.” Although she described the personalisation of her social media as a *descent*, this conflicts with the findings of Jarreau *et al.* (2019). They posit that scientists who engage with social media on a personal level are seen as more approachable or trustworthy. Exposure on social media can also build metrics related to academic profiling, which is a form of data capitalism, according to Weingart and Guenther (2016). Altimetric is used as a measure of public visibility in digital spaces such as Twitter, as an alternative form of reputation indicator. Only one respondent was aware of this: “On our [academic] profile it lists how many times something’s been cited or mentioned on Twitter or social media. So, when I was going for promotion (*and I won’t shout this too loudly*) I was tweeting about my research from like my first publication, when I was doing my PhD. I was tweeting about it and then trying to use hashtags, so that other people would pick up on it and re-tweet it. So, that sounds exactly like alternative metrics” (Delta I).

Third spaces have positive implications for the promotion of STEM. Epsilon M is embracing this approach with the undergraduates she works with: “...[by]...getting the students to sit and conduct mini-interviews with staff and ask them about their research, we are hoping to kind of share that more widely on YouTube, and I think students want to do Instagram, and perhaps TikToks.” She also noted that, “...a really positive outcome for me from Twitter has been getting to know other people and other

charities who have the same interests as I do, around diversity and inclusivity, around public engagement.” As Clark (2020) asserts, Twitter hashtags can be adeptly used to curate similar bodies of knowledge with a memetic effect. In the following example, the meme was created using an open-source image representing a female scientist. The slogan uses a well-known phrase, “Girls Just Wanna Have Fun”, adapted to “Girls Just Wanna Have **Funding for their scientific research**”, which is a slogan curated from Twitter posts that support #WomenInSTEM (Erskine, 2021). The lettering is in pink, a colour typically stereotyped and associated with girls.

Figure 18: Meme image "Girls just wanna have funding for their scientific research" from interviews with Epsilon M and Iota C.

Funding for women in STEM is harder to access, according to Iota C: “I think there's still a lot to be done. I'm part of the [anon], the inclusion group for equity in STEM, and there we did look a little bit at grant success for women in STEM fields. And I think it's still harder for women to get the larger grants or to get the same...yeah, the higher the grant value when it comes to £1 million, £1.5 million, then there's a steep drop in the

likelihood for women to win these grants.” This is something that Epsilon M is aware of too: “I feel that I've been actually very supported, and I know that there are other women who don't feel the same way in academia.” Epsilon M reflects with pathos on her “luck” that she has been a visible scientist: “I've been kind of lucky that the institutions that I've been in have obviously valued and promoted women.”

Given that, “There are not a lot of generally visible role models, especially in STEM subjects and STEM Panel B” (Epsilon M), the meme is a simple statement that shines light on the visibility of women scientists who struggle to get funding for their research.

However, Bleijenbergh, van Engen and Vinkenburg (2012) question the notion of the “ideal academic” and how this relates to being a woman. The assumption that an ideal academic attracts funding and delivers research output does not always fit with the gendered obligations of family life, whether male or female. The interview with Beta A reveals that he recognises the historic contribution of female academics to his discipline: “[There was a] time in the world where women got more of an opportunity to showcase that they actually were as good as men, you know, or better. Because previously, it was the men that went to university, it was the men that got the learning. But again, we can't be seen to say, oh we're going to study this subject because it was pushed by a female academic. We're studying the subjects that the staff here have the expertise in, and we're studying the subjects which we think that the students need to know about.” However, he does not reveal an understanding or empathy as to why this still needs to be so visible in contemporary times. Iota C, a mentor for women in STEM, is quietly hopeful for continued support for women in her department: “[I supported a student to start] ...a get-together over lunchtime. Head of School very supportive, even paid for some sandwiches and tea and coffee. We were very proud to even have like nearly half attendants were women, and we were very inclusive”. This is a small step, but it was her hope to go further in 2023: “I'm currently organising the Conference for Undergraduate Women in [STEM Panel B], which we will be hosting at [ancient HEI]. And there we're aiming to have a panel that touches on not just being a woman in [STEM Panel B], because people have so many more identities, you could be a lesbian woman in [STEM Panel B]. You could be a mixed ethnicity, lesbian woman in [STEM Panel B], and all these intersections of our identities play a very strong role in how we fit in and how we

perceive ourselves as physicists.”

4.5.5 The Pedagogue’s Sonnet: T4 a poem – hierarchies and institutional identity

Nineteenth-century French philosopher Auguste Comte mapped out the doctrine of positivism, which highlighted a bifurcation between knowledge transfer and knowledge production. However, the deindustrialisation of education since these times has resulted in a shift in knowledge production, which Knoblauch (2021) denotes as a dissolution of boundaries whereby science can no longer be regarded as a closed field or sub-system. This has the potential to reform the constitution and leadership of HE institutions, particularly with regard to the relationship between science and society in STEM (Weingart, Joubert and Connaway, 2021; Knoblauch, 2021). However, this shift remains at odds with the positivist technical rationality that foregrounds HE management, meaning that funding allocations are typically linked to analysis of performance metrics (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Spence, 2018; Cohen, 2021; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019).

Shelley’s sonnet *Ozymandias* resonates with the discussion with Zeta E, which centres on the similarities between the power of the two traditional pillars of the university – research and teaching (Brennan *et al.*, 2019; Collini, 2012). He postulates that a re-configuration of these traditional bounds for post-92 HEIs “doesn’t fit into that pattern...we should stop aspiring to be like Glasgow or Edinburgh, you know, or Oxford or Cambridge, we need to find our own niche” (Reid and Gardner, 2020). All the interviews revealed the pedagogical struggles of academics in Scotland. Furthermore, a split, or schism, was revealed in the types of institutions that promoted research or allowed academic autonomy to foster research-mindedness in their lecturing staff. Delta I recounted the experience of a colleague, which led to his return to a post-92 HEI: “[He] had to have his teaching component, he had to have his research component, but [because of] the pressures to keep the research money whilst still maintaining a high level of teaching to make sure that the teaching numbers were up, with lack of support, he went to [post-92 HEI] after that and he seems to be back to enjoying his job.”

Shelley's poem is a mainstay of traditional English literature teaching in schools and Carter (2020) describes his poetic works as a link between creative imagination and the scaffolding of new knowledge. She goes further to suggest that "...making use of cultural artefacts provides an ethical, moral and aesthetical approach to neoliberalism" (ibid., 2020). The allegorical description given of a traveller from "...an antique land..." describes a solid stone statue, "Ozymandias, King of Kings", which has crumbled and changed over time, leaving a "half sunk...shattered visage" on the ground beside two pillars described as "...vast and trunkless legs of stone..." (Shelley, 2014). The sonnet depicts the fragility of the human condition, which is exemplified through the transience of the imagery of the broken statute of Ozymandias. The poem suggests that power and pride can succumb to change and be transformed over time through external and environmental pressures such as weather. This forms a backdrop to reflect upon the nature of the university and its organisation beyond the traditional model of scholarship, which rests upon two pillars or "...legs of stone..." – research and teaching. Contemporary universities are challenged to incorporate a third mission, representing its social and economic contribution to communities and people outside academia and challenging traditional HE models (Reid and Gardner, 2020; Knoblauch, 2021; Collini, 2012).

Identity conflict is voiced within the findings of the study. Iota C "...want[s] to pierce that academic bubble of only ever speaking to [STEM Panel B] about other [STEM Panel B] and to only speak about science to other academics", pinpointing public engagement as an antidote to this: "it's just so nice to speak to other people about what we do and the importance of science" (Gani *et al.*, 2024). The deep vulnerabilities exposed by the experiences of lecturers who are torn between the vocational demands of teaching appear in opposition to the constraints of funding regimes and neoliberal rhetoric espoused by middle management. Six of nine participants interviewed discussed REF and how it impacted their experience: "I deeply dislike the REF, it was originally kind of for measuring how good your research is" but now is "not necessarily [if you] do good research, but [if you] get a good REF score" (Alpha K). These experiences are congruent with Kenny (2017), who outlines the disempowerment experienced by academics when working towards REF submissions.

REF appears to foster a disconnect between research and teaching in some lower-tier HEIs: "...there [is] an assumption that focuses on getting that teaching excellence going...So, there was pressure to get things in, but not that the institution thought that it was going to compete with the top REF institutions" (Epsilon M). REF is driven by performativity, which is problematic and highlights the commodification of this approach to scholarship (Wilkinson and Wilkinson, 2020): "I had my name put forward for the past two REFs, which is another huge issue...because I had publications that were like three and four stars, could have brought in a lot of money and bought out my time, but of course that wasn't done...[a] huge bone of contention, probably one of my biggest...it's all nice and hunky and dory and to write the right language down...blah blah blah...what have you done for public engagement, tick this box" (Zeta E). This indicates that the triple nexus is at risk when it comes to REF reporting.

The following poem is presented as a caricature of Shelley's work. Although it is true to the form of a sonnet in terms of its length – fourteen lines with rhyming couplets – this is immaterial, as Illingworth (2020) points out that the purpose of scholarly communication through poetry lies more heavily with the process than the product. The poem uses certain literary techniques such as alliteration and imagery to enhance what Amoroso (2021) describes as "literary artfulness" to write in an aesthetically compelling way, without necessarily having the skills of a seasoned poet or writer (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Drawing on the parallels of the Scottish Enlightenment (Swanson and Akdağ, 2018) and Scottish HE policy (Arnott and Ozga, 2016), the narrative is partly presented in Scots language and idiom.

The Pedagogue's Sonnet

I met a being in a VLE

Who said: "Two aspects of my self lie here

Betwixt devotion and precarity,

On a desk, a shattered paradigm exists, whose bounds,

And stifled breaths, made slim by high command,

Tell of its making through neoliberalism,

Which yet survives, counted on league tables",

The hand that ordinales, and creates a schism:

"They ca' me REF, King o' Kings:

Keek at yer wirk, big man, and despair!"

Nothing beside remains, save the desire

Of colossal freedom, and research to share,

A lonely lectern, my attire.

Notes

- VLE – *virtual learning environment*

- Keek – *Scots, to look*

- Wirk – *Scots, work*

- *Big Man* – *An idiomatic Glaswegian phrase that can describe someone who is perceived to be older or bigger: it can be used informally amongst male friends, and jokingly may not always imply a greater stature.*

The value of this work may appear at first glance merely an aesthetic portrayal of the human condition and social circumstances, yet it is hoped that it may present findings and analysis in a way that can be shared as a means of teaching leadership concepts in education as well as highlighting the key themes and findings of research interviews (Golsteijn and Wright, 2013; Callahan and Rosser, 2016; Braun and Clarke, 2006). Significantly, the harm caused by neoliberal management fosters anxiety and dissociation amongst some of those interviewed, strengthening the case for embedding the “I am” of embodied inquiry in educational research (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020; Wheaton, 2020). Exploring the embodied, personal aspects of research prompted discussion from participants concerning the interpretation of interview data through poetry: “...the poem is very different, and I thought it was a really personal kind of research output. So, I thought that was really nice” (Gamma S).

The Pedagogue’s Sonnet communicates the personal struggles of lecturers who were interviewed: “Someone in my position who teaches at HE and does fundamental scholarly research, I should really be on the scale of, you know, junior lecturer, senior lecturer, reader, assistant professor, you know, full professor and so on, and the dean. That scale, which I’ve never got on, and I’m at fifty now and I’m still a junior lecturer, and it sucks” (Zeta E). This conveys the apprehensive precarity of the role of pedagogues, whose research capacity is dictated by middle management and neoliberal funding mechanisms such as REF (Kinchin and Francis, 2016; Kenny, 2017). The poem offers a counter to the bleak outlook for lecturers, which aligns with the assertion that, “...the richness of life is lost in the process [of assigning numbers to the qualitative features of education]” (Baird and Elliott, 2018). This provoked a reaction from one participant, who agreed that the essence of the poem captured their feeling of trepidation around submission of REF returns: “Your [poem about] REF thing where [it talks about the big man] – ‘I’m going to look at everything you’ve ever done’, it was like yep, that’s...and that trepidation of well what’s actually going to happen with that?” (Beta A).

Two participants remarked on the novel approach to qualitative inquiry and felt positive towards its cultural positioning and relevance to identity in Scottish culture (Leith and Sim, 2020): “I enjoyed that it was written with, you know, the kind of more colloquial Scots language. And yeah, because it was just very different to what I’ve kind of seen previously, in terms of that sort of thing. So, I haven’t previously seen anyone use that

kind of language in reflection, and I don't think I would use that type of language in reflection, but it was very effective from a reading perspective and getting me then to think about what was in the sonnet. So, no, I think because it was very novel for me, I'd never seen anything like that before" (Theta A). New approaches to dialogue were instantiated by sharing and reflecting these methods with respondents: "...as soon as I got to the bit about the big man, I could hear myself in a Glasgow accent just saying it. I was like, God, it does sound like a west Scotsman doing it. It's not something I've come across before, but reading it I enjoyed it, and I could see things in it that does tie up with everything that I've been going through. I suppose everybody else has been doing it. I enjoyed it, and I have started since you sent that, I've started looking at autoethnographic [methods]" (Delta I).

4.5.6 Finding my "no": T5 a poem – reflections on practice and recommendations

Poetry as a method of qualitative inquiry largely remained informal within the domain of anthropological studies in the mid-twentieth century (Klein, 2012), but its use is now more common, and it has been noted that it can offer a stimulating insight into educational research and leadership studies (Callahan and Rosser, 2016). This poem fortifies the findings of the interviews as poetic portraits (Dixson, Chapman and Hill, 2016; Muccio, Reybold and Jidd, 2015). The use of literary devices in the following poem (Muccio, Reybold and Jidd, 2015) such as *enjambment* (where the meaning "runs over" or "steps over" from one poetic line to the next) adds surprise to the lines and draws the reader to understand themes that interjoin and arise from a single sentence – "Finding my no". This was inspired by an autoethnographic reflection I wrote after interviewing Iota C:

When I interviewed Iota C I felt distressed. It was clearly visible as the video stream came online that she was suffering from physical ill health. Her matter-of-fact stoicism about her medical condition put me at ease to some extent. But I really did not want to pressure her as it became clear that her workload (which she jokingly described as being 150% of her contracted hours) is immense.

She is an early-career researcher and whilst her shoulders are wide and strong to take on this burden, her role is precarious (Kinchin and Francis,

2016; Wheaton, 2020). She wants to find her “no”. No to unrealistic contractual demands; no to devising a system to measure the impact of public engagement; no to additional tax burdens for EU academics post-Brexit; no to gendered rhetoric that has no tangible outcomes for change – “...there are examples of peers or colleagues who are male and are very similar to me, who didn’t have to do the same things that I did.”

Finding my “no” – a poem

Finding
out. Re-searching,
searching the half-lit ivory tower.
Intersections contrast like chiaroscuro,
depending on your lens.

Finding my
real me. Beyond the walls,
of the convivial community.
Mutinous mycelium,
that spreads like a dangerous idea.

Finding my no
way out. Set on a track
measured by metrics.
Reaching in from outside,
authentically anchored.

Poetry as a process transforms narrative to provoke, engage and stimulate the reader, which Muccio, Reybold and Jidd (2015) denote as a "...sensuous, intellectual anchor". The use of the word *anchor* in the poem captures the ways in which academics link into their own identity, or side identity, to augment real-life research with public engagement (Garcia-Sancho, 2015). Zeta E has become disaffected by his HEI's lack of support for his research and public outreach and now runs a personal science communication channel: "[It has] ...a trademark now in its own right...on my Twitter feed and Facebook feed and everything...I've taken off the reference to [post-92 HEI] on it." The poem *Finding my "no"* illustrates three key themes relating to practice identified in interviews:

- (i) Balancing the R/T/Pe triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

The poem explores the nuanced and ill-lit conceptions and imagery of the *ivory tower* (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015), which draws on an artistic description of intersectionality (Canfield *et al.*, 2020) as *chiaroscuro* (in Italian *light-dark*, this word is used in art history to describe clear tonal contrasts, suggesting the density and volume of an artistic image). Very little synergy is apparent between a career track and the balance of the triple nexus, according to Beta A: "[It] is generally measured on three things. It's your teaching, it's your research and it's your corporate contribution. So, all the things that you do for the university and for the wider academic community. You really need to be either utterly outstanding in one of those three areas or well above expectations in two of those areas to get any chance for promotion."

When asked about the nuanced conceptions of balancing the triple nexus, Delta I is resolute: "I don't balance it". For Iota C, it is "...a big shock to the system". Eta B sees "...public engagement as an add-on", while Gamma S integrates public engagement into her practice: "A lot of my research involves the public, so there is an element of public engagement through my research, and then I obviously develop some outputs too, like it might be I've been doing little one-minute videos to provide updates on research, and just infographics and stuff like that." On the other hand, Alpha K, who originally stated that "I don't do engagement" re-gained his appetite for engagement when it came to our second interview: "[I'm] quite enthused about public engagement at the moment, because I had an idea when I was on holiday...so I've kind of put

together a wee plan to get the equipment with some money I'll get from somewhere and go out to the schools and do that."

- (ii) Academic identity (Guidetti, Viotti and Converso, 2019; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021(a); Wheaton, 2020).

The description of a "convivial community" points to the reported dysfunctionality of the academic community and draws on the notion of the university as a "mushroom factory" (Wheaton, 2020). Alpha K is suspicious: "[Collegiate is] a word a lot of people use these days...it's a word I've seen kind of creep in the last five years or so." Justifiably, the triple nexus presents a chance to develop a CoP, which feeds into a scientific identity that can start at an early age. As Beta A explained, in schools outreach he does "...a mini workshop in maths, one in chemistry, one in physics. And because they're with like-minded other pupils, you know, like, yeah, it's fine to like physics, it's fine to like maths. There are other, if you like, geeky kids like me." This encapsulates an understanding that the mainstreaming of the public understanding of science at an early age is more than marketing or promotion of science, but becomes multi-directional, which can help to permeate the gaps between science and society (Trench, 2008). This aligns with the views of Delta I, who sees collegiate as "...two things, there's how I get on, and how the staff get on with each other, and building up a work environment. But there's also the students and how well they get on with each other, and then their links with us."

Identity is pressured and precarious. Zeta E sees that senior management expectations have a serious impact on his mental health: "...it's old-school: 'soldier on boy, sit up straight. Soldier on, I did it you know, I survived the war, we'll get through this', that's the kind of Brexit kind of old-school kind of British stiff upper lip view...these are the sort of things that lead to nervous breakdowns and so on, you know, with huge work stress and so on." Standing up to these pressures is the foundation of *Finding my "No"*. The poem references "mutinous mycelium", suggesting an underground network of mushroom roots driven by subversion in times of tension.

By using third spaces or social media, scientists can circumvent academic convention to bridge the gap between the real world and academia. However, dismantling the

ivory tower in this way is sometimes thwarted by institutional policy. For example, Alpha K described his experience when he did a “*couple*” of tweets – “I got my kind of fingers rapped because I hadn’t passed it through my [HEI].” Despite this, Delta I recognises that creativity and his personality are fundamental to engagement on social media (Jarreau *et al.*, 2019): “I need to get my tweets to be more engaging...it’s that creativity...[that] could help science outreach...my in-built personality, is very matter-of-fact...But I know that’s not how the big bad world looks like.” This suggests that identity formation is fundamental to practice whereby the triple nexus can be nurtured using various approaches to public engagement.

- (iii) Problematic approaches to measuring public impact (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2020; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021(a))

The concept of “reaching in from the outside” is drawn from the interview with Iota C. She remarks that public outreach rarely measures longitudinal impact: “We all love these stories but they’re like little gold nuggets that we very rarely get to indulge in actually hearing years after that something we did that it had an impact on someone else. It’s the dream, but unfortunately, it’s not very often so gratifying to do outreach.” Beta A notes the challenge and highlighted that much of his impact may be missed or lost: “The difficulty with those things is it’s hard to measure, you know, you can go out to a bunch of different schools portraying the wonders of [STEM Panel B], and you might just be setting loads of young kids up to study [STEM Panel B], which is great, but not necessarily at your institution...you can never measure it, but you’ve got the pride of getting that buzz about your subject, but you also know that you’re trying to pull them towards your institution at the same time. So, there’s that sort of kind of balance which needs to be kind of struck...if I was really doing my job with engagement stuff and getting students to be really enthusiastic about [STEM Panel B], then ideally, they would go to a bigger, older university than the one that they’re at to study.”

Gamma S sees the role of PEPs as fundamental to this “when it comes to analysing or evaluating public outreach”. This is well supported at her ancient HEI: “there are possibilities to do courses with the professionals at [ancient HEI], the outreach professionals, and then they give you like ideas of ways on how you can evaluate the effectiveness of your outreach. Like little feedback boxes or little games where the kids

do something fun, but you are learning whether they took away the right message or learned something from it.” However, for academics interviewed at post-92 HEIs, there are no PEPs to support methods to measure impact: “I don’t think there’s been any training on how to measure impact. We know how to measure journal articles, it’s a four-star or a three-star publication, and that’s great. How do you measure the impact? How do you know that my policy document has been read by certain people and it’s been taken up? There’s nothing really to measure that. I mean, you could say a journal’s been cited fifty-five times and that’s great, but there’s nothing for that for impact as far as I’m aware” (Delta I).

4.6 Summary of findings

These findings are foregrounded by the frictions and challenges that lecturers experience in their day-to-day practice. Conflicting demands on lecturers and an ever-increasing pressure from neoliberalism to achieve results within their own research profiles leads to dissonance in their abilities to implement the R/T/Pe triple nexus in their teaching (Weingart, Joubert and Connaway, 2021; Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021). Structural barriers include policy, HEI hierarchy, employment contracts and funding (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). Whereas perceptual barriers include lack of support from institutions, organisational reactivity, capacity and capability (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Obermeister, 2020). Interviews revealed that either teaching- or research-prioritised perspectives are common in all HEIs, whilst a balanced view was taken by ECRs in Ancient or pre-92 HEIs. The next chapter will discuss these findings and make recommendations to improve the balance of the R/T/Pe triple nexus in STEM.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Discussion

A key finding from interviews showed that participants place different weight to research and teaching as the core “commodities” of lecturing work (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021). This is understandable as it is likely that the participants’ experience of their professional world is often aligned to the vision of their institution, which may be identified as high or low research-intensive (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). Using the concept of the “triple nexus” of R/T/Pe proposed by Stevenson and McArthur (2015), the study explored the lived experience of STEM Panel B lecturers in Scotland and finds out if knowledge is in crisis, as Brew (1999) suggested over two decades ago. Given the pressures of the massification and funding constraints in HE, McKinley *et al.* (2020) suggest that a shift has taken place moving academics away from von Humboldtian principles. In the following section I discuss the implications of this, before moving on to the discussion of vocation, open practice and the humanist aspects of the triple nexus. Recommendations focus on lecturers’ experiences of the triple nexus and how this can improve teaching and learning in STEM disciplines.

5.2 Moving from brain-drain to brain gain

It is clear from interviews that an unwritten institutional hierarchy is alive and well within the working world of all the lecturers interviewed (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018). Universities are dichotomised as traditional, where scholarly practice is prioritised and research is the focus of practice, which aligns to the university model founded by Cardinal Newman; or as non-traditional, often more teaching-focused with little time or focus for research. In many cases research is explicitly linked to institutionally-led knowledge transfer initiatives in business or real-life research, which mostly aligns with the von Humboldtian model, but less so focused on co-creation with members of the public outside of academia (Collini, 2012). There is appetite amongst participants to engage with the public, and to maintain unity between teaching and research, but it is not always easy.

5.2.1 Fitting von Humboldt into the triple nexus

The principal foundations of universities in Scotland sit within the traditional pillars of research and teaching, yet Hazelkorn and Gibson (2018) have asserted that the von Humboldtian approach is more hands-on and public-facing than the traditional “disembodied” ethos espoused by followers of Cardinal Newman. However, tension exists where public engagement is added to these traditional pillars of the university (Collini, 2012). Academia is facing funding pressures and, since the Stern Review of the REF in 2016 (Great Britain Department for Business, 2016), funding has been explicitly linked to impact and impact statements. This can force academics into producing impact statements focused on short-term goals linked to funding objectives, endangering the impact measurement of long-term outcomes (Ma, 2020).

Iota C is despondent about short-termism: “...we very rarely get to indulge in actually hearing years after that something we did had an impact on someone else. It’s the dream, but, unfortunately, it’s not very often so gratifying to do outreach.” This indicates that academics cannot dare to dream or to indulge in their longitudinal impact as educators. Beta A expressed his frustration at being institutionally disempowered: “The university is happy for outreach if they can see the advantage of it from a university point of view.” This ultimately links to the unhealthy aspects of the commodification of impact and its managerial constraints (Kenny, 2017). Was it the intention of von Humboldt to arrange the university into a neat machine organised along managerial precepts? It is unlikely. His 1854 treatise attacked the role of the state and he categorically stated that any state interference should be “condemned” (von Humboldt, 1854). Zeta E is critical of their post-92 HEI in this respect, and he implies that while middle management claim that the nexus is foundational to teaching work, in practice that does not happen.

This problematises the organisation of institutions that claim to maintain the unity of teaching and research, because state interference, in the form of the REF, has now pushed some academics to leave the bounds of their institutions to embrace that unity in private practice or consultancy (Wheaton, 2020). This is very much echoed in the experience of Zeta E, who mentioned that they had put their name forward for two REF reviews and published in a number of four-star journals, yet, despite this, the research capacity of their post-92 employer was too limited to take the application

further. Consequently, Zeta E decided to step back from public engagement activities citing stress: “I wanted to make the world a better place, but the reality was it was an extra stress with time and family and doing things on Saturday morning at science festivals and evening classes and things, which posed a stress on when you have family and kids.”

5.2.2 Hierarchical differences in HEIs

All the respondents had a clear understanding that there is still an unspoken hierarchy amongst HEIs, which naturally directs the course of an individual’s career. Aligning with the findings of Papatsiba and Cohen (2019), this study found that respondents were well aware that research time was mainly supported or protected within job contracts with ancient or pre-1992 HEIs, but rarely in post-92 HEIs. Some respondents chose to move jobs from a post-92 HEI to another university because of “a triple teaching load” (Epsilon M) or a desire to follow a research path that could not be supported sufficiently at a post-92 HEI (Alpha K, Beta A, Gamma S). Despite this reported lack of institutional protection of lecturers’ workloads, all HEIs lecturers were expected to work towards REF-returnable research to advance their careers. Zeta E and Alpha K, both late-career researchers, felt no pressure to bow to this expectation.

Neoliberalism is an arbitrary, “tick-box” approach, as Collini (2012) points out. Some universities are now starting to push back against this. In 2023, the University of Utrecht made a clear statement that they had decided to cease participation in global league tables issued by the Times Higher Education World University Ranking: “...collaboration and openness of scientific research [are] more important...[than]...too much emphasis on scoring and competition” (NL Times, 2023). This highlights a step-change in institutional rhetoric. The statement is firm in its intention to move away from league tables, but clearly values public engagement, open practices and open science, which has promising implications for open research (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). This echoes the imperative from Nosek cited in Cohen (2019), who calls for “...a research environment in which ‘the process, content, and outcomes of research are openly accessible by default’”. The impact of open approaches on the triple nexus will be examined further in [Section 5.4](#).

The REF reports and managerial constraints of HEIs prompted 75% of the lecturers interviewed in this study to reject organised institutional public engagement in favour of non-formal settings. For example, in a village hall, night class or online settings, where no expectations, performativity or outcomes are monitored by the university (Alpha K, Iota C and Zeta E). The freedom of this sort of activity is an antidote of sorts (Gani *et al.*, 2024) to the commodification of the triple nexus, and it is often performed for the “love” of science or mathematics, with no explicit professional recognition or reward (Alpha K, Beta A, Delta I). Contrast this to situations where academics are pressured by their institutions to deliver public engagement activity for no extra reward or contract time. This was the experience of all whom I interviewed at some point or other during their careers and is most relevant to lecturers working at post-92 HEIs. There is very little infrastructure to allow unstructured research, which can lead to what Alpha K frames as a “brain-drain” resulting from talented scientists leaving the lecturing talent pool to seek more research-expansive opportunities at upper-tier HEIs (Cohen, 2021).

Papatsiba and Cohen (2019) critique institutional hierarchies and call for reform, but it is evident that this is embedded in the infrastructure of post-92 HEIs where academics “...don’t really have that proper academic hierarchy that you do at most established universities” (Zeta E). This lack of infrastructure to support research prompted Gamma S to leave her post-92 employment and move to an ancient HEI, which put primacy on research over teaching. She felt that this was beneficial and allowed her to grow her research interests. In their review of the Science and Technology Facilities Council – “Pathways to excellence in public engagement” – Holliman *et al.* (2018) made nine recommendations to add rigour, consistency and transparency of impact measures with potential to be rolled out to all UKRI research councils.

These included practical observations, noting that “engagement approaches beyond outreach require different skills, mindsets, planning and time commitments” (Holliman *et al.*, 2018). In line with this recommendation, the findings from the interviews show that lecturers need the capacity (HEI support, timetabling and funding) and the capability (worldview, skills and CPD) to reach the triple nexus. Alpha K agreed with this and was quick to mention that links between research and teaching should be in unity, without danger of either taking precedence (McKinley *et al.*, 2020). On the other

hand, in this study, the capability to foster the triple nexus is most developed in ECRs and lecturers who have received formal training in the form of CPD or a postgraduate certificate in academic practice to support science communication or publicly engaged research within their practice (Eta B, Iota C and Gamma S) (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). The common experience of all these interviews suggests that improvements can be made to support a “pluralistic” academic identity. This is essential to bringing about longitudinal change to implement the triple nexus (Sandmann and Jones, 2019; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

5.2.3 Different approaches to public engagement with pure and applied science

The study explored the range of public engagement approaches ranging from small village halls to Nobel Prize winners (Hargittai, 2022; Strategies, 2020). From the themes uncovered in interviews, all agreed that curiosity is best fostered when there is space and time to think, although this space and time was not always afforded to lecturers within their contracts. The stifling of expository thought through managerialism is cited by Spence (2018) as a barrier to broad and critical thought, and this coalesces with the thoughts of Deta I and Theta A, who lament that there is little space for “blue sky thinking”. Accordingly, Spence (2018) argues that this undermines the intellectual ideals of von Humboldt, and in practice the capacity to make space for critical thought within the undergraduate STEM curriculum is also challenging (Alpha K, Zeta E).

However, Alpha K, Delta I, Epsilon M and Gamma S cited case examples that illustrate how this works in practice, when linked to applied science and implemented in discrete projects. The challenges of linking teaching, research and public engagement in pure, rather than applied, science is outlined by Theta A: “...a lot of the maths I was teaching was not really pure maths because it’s not getting far enough down the technicalities to be only pure.” The definition of “pure” maths or science could be subject to philosophical interpretation. American physicist Ernest Lynton described it as “blind tyranny”, denoting a blinkered adherence in universities, regarding pure science as the optimal form of research (Sandmann and Jones, 2019). This draws attention to the *noesis* of this phenomenon – how it is experienced. The perceptions of some

participants suggest that applied science is viewed as more optimal for public consumption than pure science (Hains-Wesson and Young, 2016).

There is undoubtedly room to discuss the ways in which academia frames pure and applied science. Reflecting on my interview with Beta A, I recalled the realisation that, despite my knee-jerk avoidance of pure mathematical concepts at school, my education in later life has brought me some understanding of the pure maths that underpins applied maths in everyday life:

When I was training as a forest school educator, we learned about the Fibonacci sequence and how it is replicated in nature in pinecones and leaves. So that tells me there must be something natural about mathematical reality in day-to-day life.

Beattie (2021)

How can the links between teaching and research be improved when it comes to pure research in science or mathematics? For some STEM Panel B disciplines, it is easier to achieve tangible routes to public engagement, whereby public impact can be directly linked to an outcome that affects humans (Gamma S), but it is widely recognised that it is much harder to demonstrate public impact in pure science research (Hargittai, 2022). Gamma S described a computing research project culminating in a “large exhibition” at the National Gallery or National Library of Scotland, which links scientific research with art as a form of science communication. Not all lecturers interviewed are flexible to this approach.

Beta A is wary because of his experiences in research: “...you'll often get [professionals] in mathematical circles looking down on applied mathematics.” They are resistant: “...as for research-led public engagement, there's none from me at all.” When reflecting on the use of autoethnography as a research method in STEM, Beta A cannot envisage departmental support from his HEI to make any links between the social sciences or the arts within their discipline: “I can imagine my head of division, being a professor of physics, would look at it and go, ‘What on earth are you doing? Where are the facts? Where is the evidence-based stuff? You're spending too much time talking to social scientists, Beta A’.”

Returning to thinking time, Gamma S uses physical activity to help: “I try to get out for a walk every morning and then lunchtime, and that would be when I would do a lot of my thinking about ideas.” This has extended to her research into sedentary behaviour. During the pandemic, “one strategy that we’d like organisations to encourage, might be that you meet up with a colleague to go for a walk to have your meeting, even when you’re working at home or, you know, you’re on the phone or you have thinking time and you go away and do something that is movement-based to think.” Similarly, for Theta A, “when I’m away from my desk or, you know, exercising, it tends to be I’m able to solve problems. So, like I’ll have a problem that I need to solve obviously, and almost kind of sub-consciously I’ll be thinking about it without actually thinking about it. And I find that often those ideas will come when I’m out for a run or out for a bike ride or something like that, or just a dog walk.”

5.2.4 Do lecturers dare to dream?

The study interprets qualitative interviews to expose perceptions of participants’ lost opportunities for pure research using autoethnography. Following the first round of interviews, I wrote a song that I shared with participants – *The Scottish Dream*, which re-imagines The Proclaimers’ (1987) song *Letter from America* – through the eyes of respondents. Alpha K, Delta I, Iota C and Beta A all identified the impact of Brexit upon the Scottish brain-drain. This song delves into themes of emigration of people and talent, as well as structural, cultural and institutional barriers particular to the Scottish mindset highlighted by respondents (Leith and Sim, 2020). Delta I describes it as “West of Scotland deference”, and Alpha K avoids putting himself out there using social media: “[I’m] shy about it.” On contractual demands, Iota C reflected that, “I’ve not found a way to say no or really argue that much.” These statements highlight the cultural and social dimensions of the lecturers’ experiences, which are conveyed in the song, *The Scottish Dream* (Punch and Oancea, 2014).

The interviews revealed that the research climate in Scotland is somewhat different to interviewees experiences in mainland Europe (Iota C, Eta B), and the USA is cited as markedly different by four respondents (Alpha K, Delta I, Eta B, Iota C). All the respondents agreed in their second stage interviews that a Brexit brain-drain has

precipitated a crisis in STEM, pointing to negative effects on the economy in Scotland, underpinned by technology, forestry, food and drink. In this respect, Eta B mentions the science behind the Scotch whisky industry for example. Iota C is stark in her assessment of the future of academic institutions in Scotland: “We have less access perhaps to the European funding, and recruitment has been absolutely a nightmare. We need special funding now if we want to attract students from Europe, because they’re classed as immigrants.” The re-classification of EU students as immigrants is a loaded concept. In addition, Scottish policy for education is devolved to the Scottish Government, but immigration policy is reserved to Westminster, which is problematic, according to Pietka-Nykaza, Leith and Clark (2020), because there can be a disconnect in policy objectives. This is significant as international students make up a significant portion of income for Scottish HEIs (Kemp and Lawton, 2013).

The Scottish Dream updates the original song *Letter from America* and playfully re-imagines the song through the story of a hero of the Scottish brain-drain. The hero of the song is chemist Professor Sir David MacMillan, winner of the 2021 Nobel Prize for lifelong research in pure chemistry. Hailing from Bellshill, in the deindustrialised central belt of Scotland, I shared the song with Professor MacMillan, or “our Davie”, the main character of the song. His response was favourable to the “unique” and creative approach to the research. The lyrics evoke a cultural resonance with the historical “brain-drain”, which Mycock (cited in Leith and Sim, 2020) asserts is based on an historic Scottish cultural “victim mentality”. *The Scottish Dream* re-imagines the cultural meanings from a loss of industry in places such as Bellshill and other locations in central Scotland to portray a new interpretation of “Scottish quotidian life” (McGregor and Christie, 2021). The song echoes a sense of regret that The Proclaimers (1987) draw upon: “We should have held you, we should have told you, but you know our sense of timing, we always wait too long.”

David MacMillan chose to announce his win to Scotland in a very public space – on a Saturday afternoon football show, “Off the Ball”, on BBC Radio Scotland. He told listeners that the sum of his winnings would be donated in full to support young people in STEM to enhance the equality of access to undergraduate science education in Scotland (Kramer, 2022). This is a brain-drain success story that needs to be told, and it underlines the importance of the Nobel Prize as an institution for public engagement

with science. Although it is not a distinct measure of public impact, it is a public recognition of the longitudinal impact of a scientist and their work on society (Hargittai, 2022; Dörfler and Stierand, 2020). However, it is clear from literature and from the interviews that there is little provision to measure individual impact in the medium term, and REF2021 has accentuated this, as impact scores can no longer be transferred if a lecturer moves job or changes their institution (Baird and Elliott, 2018) unless the longitudinal impact of a scientist leads them to world-leading recognition in the form of, for example, the Nobel Prize for a lifetime achievement. This is congruent with the views of Beta A. Beta A observed that lecturers rarely receive university promotion or recognition for balanced achievements in the triple nexus. He feels that there is an institutional expectation that success equates with being outstanding in public engagement, research or teaching.

Returning to Iota C's statement that, "it's not very often so gratifying to do outreach", it is useful to look at types of research project that could improve undergraduate teaching and perpetuate longitudinal impact. Literature reveals scope for longer-term TIR at undergraduate level, according to Smith (2017), who illustrates his example of the "studio projects" in architectural design. Although architectural design is inherently a more creative process than engineering or pure science, the principles Smith has outlined suggest that an understanding of the cyclical aspects of TIR could build longer term outcomes for STEM disciplines. For example, Delta I highlighted the cyclical aspects of a research cycle conducted over a period of years in his teaching work while monitoring pollution levels on the River Clyde in Glasgow. There is undoubtedly a research gap when it comes to understanding how co-production of research questions generated through public engagement could be instantiated within cyclical research in STEM. This could have applied functions for STEM Panel B disciplines in climate and environmental studies (Mabon and Crawford, 2020).

A similar example cited by Alpha K relates to fieldwork undertaken at the same site over a number of years in the north of Scotland. The research location is in a real-life context, and the results, according to Alpha K, inform a cyclical process of research. This suggests that Vygotsky's zone of proximal development in teaching underpins practical tasks to develop research skills and to evolve the concept of student-as-producer, (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). Furthermore, this extends von

Humboldt's theory to situate public-as-co-producer within the triple nexus (Mabon and Crawford, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

5.2.5 The triple nexus improves STEM teaching

From the lecturer's point of view, there can be little doubt that the triple nexus brings significant improvements to STEM teaching, as Stevenson and McArthur (2015) assert. Dialogue is an essential part of this. It cannot be ignored, and dialogical approaches link to the concepts of knowledge creation discussed by Brew (2010) and Healey, Flint and Harrington (2014) in relation to re-creation of the undergraduate curriculum. Particularly where KTP projects are involved, real-life research, aligned with Vygotsky's theory on teaching and learning, can be easily integrated (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). However, from the outset, the KTP model favours knowledge transfer, rather than knowledge exchange, and this is a crucial difference as science communicators move away from the deficit (Metcalfe, 2019).

Epsilon M found that co-creation with her students led to more opportunities for public engagement through student co-creation and knowledge exchange during the pandemic. The agility of the student response to adapt highlighted by Epsilon M illustrates the positive disruption of the pandemic, where "pivot pedagogy" relied on the ingenuity of both students and lecturers (Nordmann *et al.*, 2020). As Havemann and Roberts (2021) have discussed, the "pivot" underlines the possibilities for student/teacher porosity and co-creation using open education, which aligns with the theory of student-as-producer outlined by Freire (1970 cited in Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020).

The claim by McKinley *et al.* (2020) that von Humboldtian ideals are stifled, and that academics may struggle to identify a nexus within their workload, was perceived to be true, according to all those interviewed. Some lecturers interviewed had never even heard of the phrase, but most had a strong conceptualisation of the idea and how it should work in practice. It is far more nuanced and difficult to classify when it comes to pure science as Brew (2010) observed, alternative approaches to scholarship are best conceptualised as an academic CoP. It is harder to conceptualise when public

engagement is thrown into the mix, and it is often regarded by lecturers as a “bolt-on” (Alpha K, Eta B). Although an emerging CoP in Scotland has been established by ScotPEN which has promising results to support the triple nexus (Archer *et al.*, 2021; NCCPE, 2021b).

An alternative approach to academic research from the USA which is growing in Scotland uses vertically integrated projects (VIPs) as a framework to integrate across disciplines and university departments. VIPs reportedly lend themselves well to the undergraduate curriculum but they were not mentioned by any of the respondents in this study suggesting that more needs to be understood about their potential to involve public engagement (Strachan *et al.*, 2019). The challenges of the VIP approach can centre on the lack of opportunity for institutional engagement and an individual’s promotion and acceptance, which echoes the observations of Gani *et al.* (2024) and is reflected in the responses of those interviewed.

Beta A noted that, “...promotion is generally measured on three things. It’s your teaching, it’s your research and it’s your corporate contribution.” Similarly, Delta I did not include public engagement as a facet of their academic practice worthy of promotion: “...you don’t put that kind of thing on your application form when you go for promotion...it wouldn’t be recognised I don’t think.” There is accord amongst 40% of respondents that an American-style approach allows for a longer tenure track (Eta B), a greater level of autonomy (Alpha K), and departmental, rather than institutional, support for independent research: “...in America they have a much better attitude” (Zeta E).

5.3 The “H” factor: vocation, dedication or placation?

This study set out to determine how lecturers support undergraduate learners to develop research-mindedness in the context of the triple nexus in STEM (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Results from qualitative interviews suggest that respondents’ academic identity, and how they instantiate that within their practice, underpins their approach to the interlinking aspects of R/T/Pe. In common for all, academic identity is intrinsically linked to a perception of academic freedom, and the majority of those interviewed revealed that there is little freedom within the edifice of neoliberal

managerialism and metrics (Spence, 2018). Examples where respondents felt their academic agency was limited, or where they met barriers, included career path or tenure track (Eta B), promotion opportunities (Beta A and Delta I), HEI student recruitment expectations (Alpha K), and fulfilment of individual research interests (Epsilon M, Gamma S).

Von Humboldt (1810) made it clear in his treatise that research and teaching should be conducted in unity and the 1988 Bologna Process cemented this, making an explicit call to European HEIs to measure their quality and success by interlinking research with teaching (Geschwind and Broström, 2015). One major concern today is that funding decisions often rest on measures of “impact”, adding to the two fundamental pillars of the university (Collini, 2012). There are few formalised measures of how this embeds within teaching practice (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). As well as raising queries around the ethical dimensions of impact metrics, this calls into question the managerialism of such a measure – a concern for all interviewed in the study (Boliver, Powell and Moreira, 2018).

5.3.1 Measuring individual performance

In the 1960s, citation indexes were developed as a legitimate means of tracing the history of ideas by linking academic papers through citations (Garfield 1955 cited in Burrows, 2012). Nonetheless, linking impact metrics to this affects the ability to attract funding and inevitably impacts individual academic identity: “there is money in the game, there are jobs to be captured, and there are professional identities at stake” (Weingart and Guenther, 2016). In more recent times, the “H-index” has been used to quantify the impact of an individual rather than the history of ideas. The H-index was devised by physicist Jorge E. Hirsch in the mid-2000s. It used algorithms to balance the number of papers published versus citations made from a given academic’s publications as a measure of individual “quality” or “success”.

Measures of “success” have fed into the wider picture of REF returns and university league tables, which Baird and Elliott (2018) liken to a “football transfer window”. Positivist metrics developed to measure an individual’s success, such as the H-index, were at the time received more favourably by scientists than social scientists, which

underlines the disciplinary favour scientific disciplines give to positivism. Burrows (2012) have argued that these systems of individual evaluation can have a cumulative effect, leading individuals to experience feelings of cynicism. Aligning with the findings from this study, Collini (2012) predicted a knowledge production problem brought about by individuals distancing themselves from HEIs. Given the imperative that Brew (1999) issued a quarter of a century ago that knowledge production is in danger of being in crisis, educators cannot ignore this.

One example of this type of knowledge production crisis is noted by Collini (2012). He observes that academics are less likely to write or contribute to student textbooks because of the increased focus on success being measured by the publication of high-impact papers in academic journals. This was true for all the respondents in this study – none reported that they wrote for textbooks, except for Theta A, who mentioned that he contributes to open-source textbooks. This illuminates an interesting avenue for further research because open-source publishing is a democratic “un-paywall” method of publishing ([Section 6.1](#)). Open publishing of academic textbooks is arguably a form of public engagement meriting more attention. This has been shown to have a positive effect on students’ access to learning materials, particularly in the USA, where students are expected to buy the majority of their books (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). In addition, open-source publishing of textbooks is dynamic and current as information is assessed and amended by contributors on an ongoing basis.

5.3.2 The “H” factor

In the following section, I consider the “H” factor, a re-imagined spin-off of the H-index. “H” is a factor of humanist principles that informs the norms and values relating to an educator’s academic identity (Burdick and Sandlin, 2015; Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018). When success is judged on whether lecturers modify, persuade or influence perceptions and behaviours, there is a fundamental tension. Some respondents acknowledged this situation with resolute acceptance. Delta I, for example, confided that, when looking for a promotion, they ensured that their social media profile amplified their research outputs, influencing their impact metrics. However, this approach can be problematic, particularly where academics reportedly over-claim measures of impact (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016). From the interviews undertaken,

career stage is an influence on an individual's attitude towards agency. This was apparent from the responses of Alpha K, Zeta E and Epsilon M (all late-career academics). Their responses reveal a sense of ennui when it comes to the funding mechanisms aligned to the links between R/T/Pe, and they refer to work they "used to do", but no longer undertake (Alpha K).

Resilience is justifiably important to maintain individual academic identity, but this comes down to the respondents' understanding of what is important or necessary for the public, which can be political, institutional, and also individual (Punch and Oancea, 2014). According to Burdick and Sandlin (2015), "Civic values centred on the public good do not always coincide with private values, or with the values of the discipline or profession concerned." In this sense, institutional expectations for an individual to attract research grants also stifle the nexus because of the timelines involved: "If you're writing a research grant to try and get in £200,000, that's a month of your time trying to put that thing together. That's not just an afternoon's work. And of course, if you're used to doing it and if you've done plenty of them it's easy to write the next one. If you've got 5% research time, then no chance" (Beta A).

This suggests a need to reform reporting mechanisms for grant funding in universities. Baird and Elliott (2018) highlight that the shift from RAE to REF has meant that time spent on reporting targets increased, and, with "imposed evaluation systems, professionals have active disincentives from thinking for themselves about how to improve things". This concurs with the views of respondents, who reported very little time for strategic thought because of high teacher loads, except during the quieter summer months. Delta I shared his strategy for resilience: "if I need time to think or to do something, then I just take myself away from the computer, away from work and just spend time thinking." This shows that Delta I is assured in his approach to finding time for wellbeing at work (Scottish Government, 2023). However, this is only one aspect of wellbeing. Eardley, Banister and Fletcher (2020) discuss eudaimonic wellbeing, underlining that self-improvement and self-fulfilment are most fundamental to pursuing lasting happiness and wellbeing. Few instances in this study indicated that the lecturers I spoke to experience this on a day-to-day basis.

5.3.3 Mutinous mycelium, developing networks outside the university

Lecturers experienced a sense of wellbeing from public engagement beyond the walls of the university, which helped respondents to fortify their resilience and academic identity (Gani *et al.*, 2024). All the respondents (except Eta B) reported that they found great pleasure when relating stories where they (as an individual) had brought research to a wider public. Often this outreach would be informal, not necessarily funded through a grant application, nor did it influence student recruitment numbers or publishing metrics (Burrows, 2012). For example, when sharing a story on her current research on an electron microscope, Iota C was joyful. She volunteered to teach night classes for prisoners through a prison outreach scheme, funded by the Royal Society. She reported that it was “the most rewarding thing I’ve done in my life, going to HMP [anon]”. Similarly, when Alpha K took his science show on the road to village halls “for the love of science” he did not link it to his impact scores or professional profile. Zeta E told me that this aspect of his work is now hidden – he pulled back after his HEI expected him to deliver activities with no protected time or financial reward. This underlines the devaluation of public engagement activities, a common experience for many respondents in this study (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021(a)).

Iota C revealed the precarity of her individual fulfilment within the triple nexus, reporting that it was not always achieved when teaching undergraduates at an HEI. Teaching is under-valourised, and Iota C mentioned occasions where teaching was not remunerated or done on a voluntary basis within her university: “I was involved in undergraduate teaching at the start of my contract, which I continued as a volunteering activity during my fellowship.” This is also true for Delta I, who suggested that funding cuts are targeted at his discipline: “[STEM Panel B Discipline] schools [are] an easy target, I would suggest for cuts. So, I’ve always got my CV up to date [*laughter*], it’s always ready to go just in case these things...because a programme has to bring in a certain number of [undergraduate] students for it to be viable.” These, and other experiences divulged by respondents, underline the strong link between academic capitalism, academic precarity and pedagogic frailty, which ultimately has a negative effect on the quality and quantity of new scientists coming into the profession, according to Alpha K and Eta B (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Burrows, 2012; Kinchin and Francis, 2016).

It is clear that resilience is fundamental to maintaining academic identity and this is vital to ensuring that the triple nexus can flourish (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Academic identity arguably sits at different places on the triple nexus – late-stage career academics tended to maintain the view that research should take primacy over teaching, while mid-stage researchers are less inclined to think this way, and ECRs take a much more balanced view of the triple nexus (Fig. 14). Even if they do not set out to design their undergraduate teaching according to the triple nexus, the interviews with ECRs reveal common cultural understandings and expectations that illustrate an active understanding and teaching approach in support of the nexus (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Gamma S explains that this module is optional for her undergraduate computing students, yet it is vital to broaden their understanding of their research, which underlines the need to embed public engagement as a mandatory module in STEM degrees.

5.3.4 Communication or popularisation?

This thesis argues that communication is directly linked to humanism in educational theory, or the “H-factor”. This is likely something that cannot be quantified in league tables because communication is inherently humanist as a qualitative aspect of educational theory and practice (Freire, 2014). Instances described by respondents reveal the humanity of public engagement, echoing a “science populariser” element of their work without the “conjuring” aspect that has historically linked science communication to money-making or academic capitalism (da Rocha Goncalves, 2020; Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). However, these instances mainly reveal an easy synergy between teaching and public engagement, and, when it comes to undergraduate teaching, this does not reveal an easy fit for the triple nexus because of the problematic measurements of research excellence that Alpha K criticises: “It is not necessarily about good research, it’s just about a good REF score.”

Resolving this tension is difficult. How can a scientist’s own evaluation of what is best for society’s wellbeing indicate what the public need, and how can this be scored as research of high impact and good quality that can be integrated into undergraduate teaching and learning? At this juncture, humanist principles can risk being

paternalistic, or even hegemonic (Gani *et al.*, 2024). It is apparent from the experiences of all those interviewed that the multiple goals of the impact “edifice” (Burrows, 2012) raise concerns of political tensions between these different aims, often be linked to career stage, because, to advance their career, academics are expected to fit within the constraints of institutional hierarchies and academic capitalism (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019).

This also raises the question of due process – especially regarding the model of communication and valuable facets of communication. A major challenge with the broader goal of “informing the public” concerns the so-called deficit model, where the public is viewed as the “other” (Empson, 2012), with meagre knowledge of science, remedied by scientists’ uni-directional communication (Gani *et al.*, 2024). As Dooley (2017) has observed, when scientists step outside the ivory tower of their work, they should not be afraid to be human or to use emotion to communicate science. This suggests that, conversely, inside the ivory tower, academics may feel dehumanised (Wheaton, 2020).

Respondents reported a sense of trepidation or fear around the completion of impact statements when tick-box efficiency takes primacy over effectiveness (Zeta E, Beta A, Delta I) (Chubb and Watermeyer, 2016). Engaging with socio-economic and socio-cultural topics within science can therefore help STEM Panel B academics become involved with new topics by developing an aspect of inspirational practice as with, for example, the role of women in STEM (Iota C, Epsilon M) (Social Sciences Group, 2017). During the COVID-19 pandemic, Theta A used daily COVID-19 briefings on infection rates to exemplify mathematical modelling to undergraduate students, which he found to be a serendipitous aspect of pivot pedagogy (Havemann and Roberts, 2021). In addition, science communication, as a form of scholarly practice, worked well for both Delta I and Alpha K when leading undergraduate field trips to monitor sites for ground pollution and environmental indicators (Jünger and Fähnrich, 2020).

However, these examples are all rooted within applied methods in STEM Panel B disciplines. Beta A, Theta A and Delta I all expressed frustration when it came to demonstrating public impact or explaining pure scientific theory or concepts in a way that was tangible and accessible to a broad audience. Theta A linked this to the nature

of his current post-92 HEI, which indicates an institutional difference to the ancient HEI where he previously worked (Cohen, 2021): "...a lot of the maths I am teaching [is] not really pure maths...it's...underpinning bits of applied maths, so lots of calculus for instance...even though that was what my undergrad and my PhD were in, that's just not what I've found myself doing in a research role when I've moved to [post-92 HEI]." However, Delta I, at a post-92 HEI, can't see a way to widen the impact of his research in pure science because he does not have enough time protected within his contract.

5.3.5 Fostering research-readiness in undergraduates

Phenomenological findings from the study suggest that teaching in HE is being dehumanised and there is very little space or time to bring the triple nexus into an undergraduate setting because of relentless academic pressure for student retention, results and impact scores (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Burrows, 2012; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). There is a need for HEI management, curriculum developers and their (potential) funders to reflect on these challenges if the triple nexus is to be nurtured at undergraduate level. In applied science, there are good examples where this can work well, particularly where fieldwork and co-operative learning can engage with the public, feeding into Vygotsky's theory of proximal learning (Erbil, 2020). However, for pure science disciplines, this is not so easy, particularly when it is apparent that many undergraduates are not research-ready (Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). Eta B thinks that Scotland is behind in this respect and is scathing in his approximation of the development of research-readiness in the UK compared to other parts of Europe.

In part, this delay in research-readiness could be about the age and stage of undergraduates. Gamma S believes that, even by third year, university work can be challenging because, "I think students are not exposed to research before they come to university." In Scotland, the school-leaving age is generally 17, which means that many undergraduates come to HE a year earlier than many of their counterparts (Kemp and Lawton, 2013). Zeta E pointed out that the human brain is not fully developed until the age of 25 and relates this to his experience of university: "For me it was later [than 25]. For me it was 30 to 32." He outlines the precarity of a situation where lecturers are trying to bring out research-readiness as well as teach. Zeta E

cites the stress this can bring to teaching practice. It is evident that, to grow the H-factor, HEI management and academic developers need to build resilience in staff and students if they are to support the triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Epsilon M notes that resilience and willingness to adapt of her undergraduate student cohort feeds into their impact on local communities, in turn building resilience, “*they are probably our best ambassadors*”. She also reflects, however, that, during the pandemic, this did not come without a toll on the mental health of staff and students. Long-term strategies to build student resilience to support research-readiness in undergraduates is vital, according to Delta I:

“When they get to see real-life science, and it’s messy, and it doesn’t work and there’s a lot of non-results, it’s quite good. It helps build up their resilience a little bit for when they go to the workplace, but also it helps them potentially when they go into their PhD that stuff goes wrong all the time with a PhD.”

5.4 Open scholarship in the post-pandemic university

The future of tertiary education has undoubtedly been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic as an emergency situation changed systems and practice for educators all over the world (Anderson, 2020; Cochrane *et al.*, 2020; Fuller *et al.*, 2021; Schwartzman, 2020). The concept of “pivot pedagogy” was born, representing an opportunity for scholars already embedding OEPs into their day-to-day work to invite others to join the open education community (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020). As practice for public engagement has evolved over the last two decades, the goals and objectives of HEIs have evolved to develop systemic support for PEPs (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021(a)). Given that some of the respondents in this study have seen public engagement policies in the past as an institutional “bolt-on” (Alpha K and Eta B), the possibilities and potential for open scholarship to formalise approaches to research should be explored further (VITAE, 2013a).

If public engagement is to become a third mission for universities, how can this integrate into open practice? The civic movement supports this approach and calls have come from policy and government about the role of the university in local and

national communities in Scotland in this respect (Arnott and Ozga, 2016; Boland, 2014). However, support for open scholarship is still an emerging field of interest, and there is little direction in policy to recognise and reward HEIs to develop open scholarship practices (Farrow *et al.*, 2020; Havemann and Roberts, 2021). The notion that the pandemic pivot to OEPs was a temporary “workaround” was reportedly widely accepted, according to those interviewed – with the exception of those who worked in digitally distributed campuses prior to the pandemic (Havemann and Roberts, 2021; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). The following section considers the impact of open scholarship on the triple nexus, and how this may or may not enable the triple nexus to flourish (Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

5.4.1 Opening up digital spaces

Pivot pedagogy during the pandemic was a common experience for all those who were interviewed but it was met with mixed feelings. Reflecting on the use of digital spaces to replace practical lab work, Delta I was resolute: “I don’t want it to be part of the new teaching model, but it’s what’s going to happen.” Delta I implies that this change will implement long-term curriculum changes, and Alpha K was more comfortable with this. He had worked using digital technology to teach at distributed campuses using OEPs. Similarly, Theta A embraced the use of digital spaces and blogging to foster open knowledge creation using web2 to support his teaching and learning (Yau, 2019). He sees blogging as an open aspect of his scholarship that enhances knowledge creation when he shares his blog posts with students because he “*routinely*” learns things from students.

Digital spaces promote equity of access for undergraduates. Gamma S mentions the cost-of-living in an ancient HEI city as a barrier precluding some students from studying there: “...by having some digital spaces and doing some of your teaching online, it’s more inclusive and you’re opening up to a wider range of students.” This has implications for the widening access agenda (Riddell, Blackburn and Minty, 2019). Although the pandemic disrupted systems and approaches, the interviews suggested that students were resilient and accepting of the change (Epsilon M, Gamma S, Iota C, Zeta E). Boliver, Powell and Moreira (2018) acknowledge that HEI identity

influences approaches to widening access, and the testimonies of the respondents in the study indicate the truth of this, as noted by all respondents teaching at post-92 HEIs in formerly industrial (third-tier cities) (Brabazon, 2019). Those who worked for post-92 HEIs were more accustomed to a flexible approach to the delivery of teaching and learning, particularly in digitally distributed campuses. This affects mindset and willingness to engage with open-access, digital methods to support teaching and learning.

As Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth (2019) argue, the role of digital in universities has the potential to foreground social justice and increased participation, which is fundamental to the core values of praxis and public pedagogy (Freire, 2014; Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). Using autoethnography to reflect on the findings from the study, I uncovered a tension that exists in OEPs between openness and vulnerability:

...the other side of vulnerability reveals an openness or “unruly curiosity” (Pirrie and Fang, 2021) that enables potential for transformation. Vulnerability allows one to be responsive to unpredictability through openness, through sharing with others. This makes me wonder is it easier for academics to share these vulnerabilities in third spaces such as blogs, rather than amongst the formal confines of the academic community?

Beattie (2021): Autoethnographic reflection

Curiosity was a common theme uncovered in interviews. Gamma S spoke about some of the challenges she faced as an educator: “...having that open mind and exploring things, [undergraduates are] really scared of getting things wrong. So, I think potentially it would be useful to have some sort of framework that matches with the research nexus and it’s embedded throughout, with the students being aware of the use of research within the teaching.”

5.4.2 Open research cycles

One possible approach to embedding open practice within the triple nexus can be found within open research cycles (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Open research uses an open

and iterative approach to developing a research question that refines questions and methods by seeking feedback and experience using social networks and blogs. Blogs are classed as “grey literature”, and their use is embryonic in research methodologies, according to Adams, Smart and Huff (2017). This may have implications for formal ethical approval in research. However, my interviews found that some participants actively used blogging as part of their methodological development for their research interests. Open access journals also play an important part in this cycle and their public value is recognised by Gamma S: “Anybody can read something that’s open access and there’s this perception that people aren’t smart enough to read it, and that’s totally not true, you know” (Kelly, Sadeghieh and Adeli, 2014; Sandmann and Jones, 2019). She continued, “Those things that are suitable for public consumption, that’s how researchers learn how to be researchers, they read other papers, so why can’t someone who’s not paid to be a researcher do the same thing?”

The concepts of open research are embedded into Epsilon M’s teaching practice and she supports undergraduates, asking, “...the students to sit and conduct mini-interviews with staff and ask them about their research...[to] share that more widely on YouTube, and I think students want to do Instagram, and perhaps TikToks.” By allowing students to open up dialogue on research in a third space, they can engage in a neutral space that is not necessarily controlled by an HEI, allowing individual curiosity to evolve and space to develop research questions or themes (Farrow *et al.*, 2020; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). Democratisation of research is therefore an important aspect of open research with potential to fit well with the intentions of the triple nexus in an undergraduate teaching context. However, with this open curiosity, it must be acknowledged that there is vulnerability. If open research cycles are therefore to be used to support the triple nexus, it is essential that ethical guidelines are in place ([Section 5.4.4](#)).

An open approach to research, with students as co-producers, aligns to the approach first outlined by Healey and Jenkins (2009) in their call for reform. Yet, there is little evidence to suggest that, over the last fifteen years, HE policy has supported capacity and capability to promote this approach for those interviewed in the study. In Scotland, according to Britton, Schweisfurth and Slade (2018), the establishment of consensus policy-making is “...within Scotland’s DNA” (OECD, 2015 cited in Britton, Schweisfurth

and Slade, 2018), but there needs to be stronger provision in national policy to support this. This is echoed by the respondents in the study (SFC, 2019). According to McGregor and Christie (2021), participatory methods such as citizen assemblies within Scotland allow for “cognitive praxis”, which can advance innovative practice for wicked problems such as the twin crises of climate change and biodiversity loss. This illuminates an avenue for further research in this respect, arguably highlighting the need for open societies and scholarship, supporting the assertion of Roche *et al.* (2019) that:

Clear communication of scientific research is of paramount importance to evidence-based policy, open societies, and creating an informed public, but this communication must be tailored to different audiences and contexts. A great deal of work has been done to bring science to younger audiences through the use of dialogue and participatory approaches to public engagement, and while there is no longer a dependency on the deficit model of public engagement, more work that targets other groups is needed.

This is problematic, according to Beta A, who finds that his work mainly targets schools and young people, revealing a telling gap in the capacity of Beta A, who has had no formal science communication training for audiences other than schools. This lack of formal science communication training was common for many who were interviewed, except Iota C and Epsilon M, who had undergone specialist training in science communication, highlighting a route to develop capability and capacity for students and teachers to foster the triple nexus through formal science communication training and reach a wider variety of audiences (Thomson, 2023; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

5.4.3 Missing the impact of open practice?

According to Farrow *et al.* (2020), open practices in research can challenge assumptions about how to create and disperse new knowledge. This is an enticing approach within a public engagement dimension given the appeals made by Brew (1999) and Healey and Jenkins (2009), which challenged educators to open up ways

to re-configure knowledge creation through the teaching/research nexus. Farrow *et al.* (2020) defines open practice as a stage of the open research cycle that characteristically may improve the reach, impact and efficiency of a lecturer's work. Open practitioners often integrate open publishing into what they do through open access journals, blogging or social media, using social networks as a research resource for radical transparency (Farrelly, Suilleabháin and McCarthy, 2020; Johnston, MacNeill and Smyth, 2019; Weller, 2018). Each participant (except Eta B) described their use and experience of some open practices. However, they did not always see obvious links between public engagement and open practice.

For Alpha K, Theta A, Epsilon M and Gamma S, their approach to open practice is primarily through digital scholarship, whether using open education resources (OERs), blogging, social media or open-source coding. The definition of digital scholarship in the context of open practices is summed up by Weller (2011), who mentions the presumption that open approaches to scholarship may lack quality or be viewed as less "proper" than traditional scholarship. This is borne by the views of some respondents, who mention their use of open practice, but do not classify or report this as public engagement. In recent times, HEIs have gradually accepted open practices, particularly within the fields of massive open education online courses (MOOCs) and OERs (Weller, 2018). These approaches to scholarship fill a liminal space that is frequently occupied by HEIs – usually what Weller (2011) defines as "big OER". This can include examples such as the Open University's "Open Learn" platform, or Coursera, developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Meanwhile, "little OER" are typically produced through CoPs by open-source coders or teams.

The core experience of respondents' use of open practice indicates that this is not well defined within HEIs because the majority of HEIs still adhere to the worldview that institutional settings and physical spaces are necessary to act as a bridge between academia and the public (Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019). Alpha K distances himself from this interface: "I think that STEM and the publicity of STEM has kind of been taken over by the STEM team in [post-92 HEI] ...that kind of put me off a little I'd say from the public engagement stuff. I still do some local stuff, very local." Yet, despite this, Alpha K actively uses and contributes to "little OER" to support his teaching. Theta A, meanwhile, describes his use of open-source coding as follows: "I think that there is a

move towards more openly available kind of open-source teaching and research, [but]...it's still very technical.” These statements reveal the differences between lecturer perceptions of their HEIs and their associations with open practice. Findings from the study reveal a dimension of lecturer experience that intersects both institutional and third spaces within the open practice movement, yet there is reportedly little formal ratification of this approach within HEI policy (Weller, 2011; Farrow *et al.*, 2020; Havemann and Roberts, 2021).

Open access papers amplify public engagement and reach (BERA, 2018). Paywall-protected privilege means that many journal articles are not universally accessible. However, open access papers have been instrumental in reporting REF returns, according to Delta I: “We have submitted one of our papers to REF. We got it in I think just before the deadline. So, they’re in open access publications – we’re doing everything we can to make sure they’re REF returnable.” However, Marques *et al.* (2017) reinforce the notion that REF remains a complicated and laborious system, which only promotes “select” and best case studies that may not always have wider reach beyond the walls of the university. It can therefore be inferred that REF is at odds with “open” as it allows very little space or investment for new researcher development which is supported by the experience of Zeta E.

Carter (2020) has described academic freedom within the confines of neoliberalism is described derisively by Carter (2020) as “irony” and, in the context of the tensions between open research and the REF, it is clear that this is true for nearly half the respondents (Zeta E, Alpha K, Delta I and Beta A). Alpha K “deeply dislikes” REF and Beta A sees that, despite being submitted as a case study, the research grants gained will likely be “lost in that centralised administration”. There are even fewer impact case studies reporting on collaborative or transdisciplinary research and this is echoed in the findings from the interviews (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017; Boulding *et al.*, 2020).

The impact value of open practice can sometimes be lost, because the nature of impact is hard to measure, quantify or report on (Theta A, Gamma S). This is certainly true within STEM Panel B, as Theta A notes his use of open-source coding “...*kind of counts as public engagement*”.

This exemplifies a memetic aspect of open practice (Clark, 2020), which links to theories discussed by Weller (2011), who highlights the ways in which copyright law intersects with a “re-mix culture” within digital technologies. He predicted that some academics would fear “the imminent revolution, [and] the irrelevancy of higher education...” as a fatalistic consequence of open practice, but this is not the case for any of those interviewed in the study. On the contrary, most embrace open practice in both formalised and non-formalised settings. Theta A shared his experience of using and contributing to open textbooks: “We use a lot of open source, a lot of the textbooks that we use on my modules are openly available...and if you spot like a typo or you spot something, you can report that and fix it for them, and they’ll amalgamate that into the book.” This reveals the dynamic aspect of open practice, but also hints at problems or perception of problems that might be perceived by practitioners. Despite the benefits of open publishing, Chtena (2019) cited in Farrow *et al.* (2020), mentions the frictions associated with open text production, circulation and maintenance, which can conflict with traditional standards of copyright and ethical approval.

5.4.4 Ethical dimensions of open scholarship

Within STEM disciplines, Davies (2020) has highlighted the public communication of science as problematic, particularly when public engagement may be dichotomised as either “democratic” or “strategic” (Priest 2018, cited in Davies, 2020). This also links to issues of confidentiality in business and intellectual property (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012). The focus on the ethics of open science and open data has been particularly heightened by the pandemic (McCrea, 2021). During this time, public acceptance of and expectations for open engagement with science may have advanced towards open practice for STEM educators (Martini, 2020). To maintain and improve these practices, there is a need for policy to embed open practices at national, local and institutional level (Havemann and Roberts, 2021). This shift supports the call from Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon (2014) to desist at risk of “...ignoring or discounting places outside of the formally mandated engagement processes where publics do, or wish to, engage with science, technology and innovation” to accommodate public engagement at all stages of research cycles (Farrow *et al.*, 2020).

Despite this, continued expectations from impact assessment regimes such as the REF to demonstrate links between open access and public engagement with STEM keep ethical barriers in place in relation in research environments that require security or business sensitivity (REF, 2019; Haklay *et al.*, 2021; BERA, 2018). This is particularly an issue with research that handles personal data, health or social issues that may be sensitive in nature (Gamma S). As universities have been traditionally focused on teaching and research as their core mission, formalising the mission of public engagement illuminates gaps within the dimensions of ethics, trust and capacity, and there is a need to fortify these relationships to communicate the core values of openness and transparency within the triple nexus of STEM (Bensaude, 2014; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). One way of developing relationships and trust is to maintain a research cycle through “live briefing”, linking to student work at different stages of existing research projects already granted ethical approval (Gamma S).

This is a similar approach to the “studio projects” described by Smith (2017), situated as TIR. However, “live briefing” suggests a more dynamic and responsive approach than TIR, able to readily integrate public engagement at any stage of an open research cycle (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Gamma S is enthusiastic about open practice and defined open scholarship as a tool, within the broad confines of public engagement: “I guess it’s anything that’s out there in the open, you know. So, it could be an event, or it could be published work.” However, she was keen to point out that her definition of public engagement is not always accepted within frameworks or guidelines set out by her HEI: “...for some reason [this approach] doesn’t seem to be, you know, routinely or standardly perceived as public engagement.” Although McKinley *et al.* (2020) and Duncan, Manners and Miller (2017) discuss public engagement and impact in the context of teaching and research, they make little or no mention of open practices in this respect. McKinley *et al.* (2020) suggest that the macro-conditions of the REF are divisive to the teaching/research nexus, and their study found that public engagement occupies a mid-way position within the reported aspects of the teaching/research nexus. For the triple nexus to thrive, according to interviews within this study, it was found that public engagement within HEIs has an explicit expectation to be quantifiable, goal orientated and audience focused (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015; Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019).

This was a common experience for those respondents working in ancient HEIs where typically they work alongside PEPs to disseminate their research to wider audiences (NCCPE, 2021b). PEPs also support lecturers to deliver and report on impact case studies and there are some concerns that rewarding public engagement through funding for impact might prompt cynicism, endangering public engagement by becoming a “bolt-on” merely to achieve funding goals (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). The situation appears to be different for different HEIs and those working in lower-tier or post-92 HEIs, who report little to no support from PEPs to deliver their public engagement work (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). Theta A describes the public engagement department of his post-92 HEI as a dehumanised “machine” and it is clear from his experiences that most of his public engagement activity is driven by structured, one-off events such as science festivals or outreach days. Beta A is dismissive of PEPs: “So, they’re essentially kind of like the folks that are probably not either researching or teaching, but they might have in the past, and then they’re kind of given that remit...usually not in the post-92 institutions.”

When it comes to researching educational practice within the paradigm of public engagement, BERA (2018) guidelines state that the “norm” for educational research typically rests within a traditional model. Although they do specify that open access is seen as an effective way to support pathways to democracy within research practices,

Written contracts are considered the norm for funded or commissioned research. Such agreements should, wherever possible and especially in the case of publicly funded research, take into account the rights of the public within a democracy to have open access to the results of research.

(BERA, 2018)

Although this stipulates that research outputs should be open access, there is no mention of how this data is disseminated to appeal to a broader audience. Furthermore, no mention is made of the ways in which open scholarship and open research cycles may help educators to guide the formulation of research to develop the triple nexus of R/T/Pe within teaching practice. This reveals a gap where science

communication CPD and postgraduate teacher training may assist STEM lecturers to develop a more cohesive, publicly engaged approach to teaching and research with undergraduate cohorts in STEM (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Theta A is reluctant to believe that his post-92 HEI would classify open practices as public engagement: "...they don't realise it's quantifiable or reportable, or they might not count it as public engagement." This suggests that institutional structures for ethics are so tightly aligned to the norms of publicly funded research that there is little scope to shift from the contractual approach.

Although BERA (2018) ethical guidelines provide for open practice in section 68 (they stipulate the uses of Creative Commons licences) to support wider public access to research outputs, there is a sense of powerlessness amongst those interviewed when it comes to ethical processes that support routes to public engagement (Weller, 2011; Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Alpha K is blunt on this: "We have an internal ethics committee, and we have to do what they tell us." Often, the timescale of undergraduate programmes is not long enough to complete the ethical approval process (Alpha K, Epsilon M), which suggests a need to develop "live briefs" as part of an established research cycle (Gamma S), inviting undergraduates to participate in discrete aspects of research at any stage of the cycle (Farrow *et al.*, 2020)

Epsilon M stated, "...that creativity and the curiosity is probably there [in students] from day one". Similarly, Zeta E is confident in the abilities of undergraduates to be curious, and, as part of that, he sees his role as a facilitator to develop their approach to scholarship. Regarding work prospects for students, Delta I sees public relationship building as a way to improve employability prospects for students. He described his first-hand experience of this in his role as an employability champion for undergraduates. However, to integrate open practices for public engagement outside contractual or KTP agreements, HEI and Scottish Funding Council policy support needs to be in place (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). The recommendations of Beckman and Hensel (2009) state that, "Collaborative research projects may be designed by the faculty mentor, while individual projects are more likely to be student designed. In all cases, however, the role of the mentor and advisor is critical to the students' learning process so that they develop strong research skills and an understanding of ethics in research." This suggests that all disciplinary departments could benefit from an open

practice “engaged scholarship champion” to help build and grow the movement to support public engagement (Sandmann and Jones, 2019).

5.4.5 Recommendations

If public engagement is to be embedded as the third mission of the university alongside teaching and research (Collini, 2012), the purpose and paradigm of the university needs to be re-examined. Scholarship should not be incentivised by money, nor an arbitrary value that may be inferred by league tables or REF scores (Baird and Elliott, 2018; Havemann and Roberts, 2021). Brew (1999) has asserted that knowledge is in crisis, so there is no harm in pursuing public engagement outside an HEI as an antidote to higher education, but this should not come at the cost of a lecturer’s wellbeing, teaching load or individual research path (Gani *et al.*, 2024). Given the primacy of co-creation and wellbeing as foundations for Scottish social policy, this needs to be supported by HEI policies to protect time and funding, enabling lecturers to develop teaching practice and curriculums to support the triple nexus.

Within HEIs funding, policy and practice, and the quality and consistency for public engagement support will most likely be supported by PEPs (NCCPE, 2021b). Lack of access to PEPs is most marked in post-92 HEIs with little or no formal support for the triple nexus within STEM departments. This aligns with the findings of Watermeyer and Rowe (2021), who state that the role of PEPs is often undervalued and misunderstood. Support for public engagement in HEIs presents an opportunity for PEPs with STEM backgrounds (e.g. Epsilon M) to uniquely position their practice “to synergise so-called ‘hard’ knowledge with ‘soft’ practice” (Watermeyer and Rowe, 2021).

This study found a common understanding amongst lecturers that the timescale of undergraduate programmes is not long enough to develop undergraduate research skills within year one, sometimes not even by the final Honours year (McKenzie *et al.*, 2018). In addition, ethical approval, research grants and REF reporting are lengthy and laborious, so off-the-peg solutions may create better routes to develop discrete research projects that undergraduates can easily progress through broad-based research skills modules in the final year of school and the first year of university.

Possible routes may be through working on VIPs, or with existing CoPs such as ScotPEN (Archer *et al.*, 2021), to develop a loose framework for social learning or live briefs within already established research projects in STEM (Strachan *et al.*, 2019; Annala and Mäkinen, 2016; Metzger *et al.*, 2019; SFC, 2019).

A US-style contractual model for lecturers outlined by Alpha K could be used as a foundation to build contracts, enabling lecturers to be more dynamic in their implementation of the triple nexus (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). Despite high teaching loads, all respondents accepted the teaching/research nexus as fundamental to the fabric of the university (Collini, 2012). REF reporting requirements promote public engagement (REF, 2018), but there is scant opportunity to develop and extend von Humboldt's approach to the teaching/research nexus to a triple nexus in STEM. Stevenson and McArthur (2015) identified new pathways for academic developers to improve teaching in STEM, and institutional policies need to support and reward staff accordingly (Holliman *et al.*, 2018; Sandmann and Jones, 2019).

Equity of public access should be formalised with acceptance and guidance for open research cycles and publishing (Havemann and Roberts, 2021; Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Open access repositions the function of academic publishing, but the guidance in REF is nebulous: "We recognise that there is a range of practice in the sector, and it will be up to HEIs to determine what evidence to provide" (REF, 2018) This may leave room for misunderstanding, or a piecemeal approach between different HEIs (Papatsiba and Cohen, 2019). As such, open scholarship policies must be viewed as a fundamental part of public engagement within the triple nexus for STEM to advance the skills for undergraduates and support them to be research-ready within the public domain (Stilgoe, Lock and Wilsdon, 2014; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). One strategy to support this would involve ensuring mandatory, rather than elective, modules for STEM undergraduates in public outreach, science communication, OEP or research design to deepen public understanding of science (Davies, 2020; Kahan, 2015).

The commonality of experience in this study in relation to lecturers' understanding and engagement with the triple nexus suggests a general curiosity and desire to integrate this into undergraduate teaching. This suggests that a distinct CoP to develop and

grow this mode of scholarship as a triple nexus could build co-creation and reform contractual obligations for staff in universities (Strachan *et al.*, 2019; NCCPE, 2021b). Foundational to this, it should be recognised that time and space should be protected within lecturers' contracts to allow for "blue sky" thinking (Collini, 2012). With this in mind, HEIs should align with public sector policies for wellbeing and the "Right to Disconnect", which supports staff to integrate a one-hour period for wellbeing activities such as walking, cycling or physical activity (Scottish Government, 2023). If the mission of the university is to embrace public engagement as a core tenet of its existence, the human "H-factor" of this work should inform the direction of travel for curriculum reform (Collini, 2012).

Chapter 6: Conclusion

This chapter will provide a concise conclusion of the findings from the study and highlights the contribution of the thesis to understanding the ways in which university lecturers can make integrative links between T/R/Pe in STEM. The focus of the study has been on the experiences and perceptions of Scottish STEM Panel B HE lecturers teaching undergraduate student cohorts (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017). The research questions addressed focus on the interlinkages that exist between these aspects of scholarly practice, described as the triple nexus by Stevenson and McArthur (2015). The study sought to discover where these interlinkages may exist and where policy and practice could improve undergraduate teaching and learning outcomes in STEM (Healey and Jenkins, 2009).

6.1 Areas for further research

In light of the findings and existing literature within this study, it is clear that integrative links between R/T/Pe will improve outcomes for undergraduate teaching and learning while developing research-readiness (Healey, Flint and Harrington, 2014). Very few studies look at the situation in Scotland (McKinley *et al.*, 2020), and fewer still consider STEM disciplines, although some examine the social sciences (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). Using this lens, I wanted to illuminate the humanist aspects of pedagogy to make recommendations based on the interviews undertaken to determine whether “knowledge is in crisis” (Brew, 1999). Because this research was qualitative it is identified that an area of further research could be undertaken by looking at the phenomena of the triple nexus in STEM from a positivist viewpoint by examining the impact case studies within units of assessment in REF. This study disaggregated data by gender and drew focus upon the perceptions of women in STEM using a feminist lens (Mertens, 2020), but there was no focus on intersectionality which is identified as another area for further research (Canfield *et al.*, 2020).

Vygotsky is attributed to the foundation and development of the theory of student-as-producer, which informs Freire’s theory of critical pedagogy. This was found to be apparent in the approach to teaching and research for those participants who

developed long-term fieldwork projects with students in chemistry (Rayner, Smyth and Fotheringham, 2020). This has potential to be a case study which exemplifies the triple nexus to other disciplines which could be done effectively using R/T/Pe approaches to research. One finding to consider, which was not unveiled through interviews, is the impact of open research cycles in this respect (Farrow *et al.*, 2020). Although open practices, including OERs and open-source publishing, were touched upon by nearly all those interviewed, in most cases they did not view activities such as research using open-source coding or open publishing – this is an aspect of impact that has been missed in impact reporting (REF, 2019). None of the participants considered the use of open research cycles to link public engagement into their research practice. This is therefore identified as an area for further research (Farrow *et al.*, 2020).

6.2 Teaching from the heart – a charter for the embodied university

Building on the arguments for a compassionate university presented by Boyd and Grant (2019), the findings from this study show that, as Watermeyer and Rowe (2021) denote, if research and teaching are viewed as core “commodities” of the university, this must also apply to people in the context of public engagement policies and funding. Interviews with participants indicate that lecturers perceive a pressure to be performative (Baird and Elliott, 2018), while conflicting with their own passions and research identity as scientists. Given that Jarreau *et al.* (2019) pinpoints that scientists are often preoccupied with a focus on defending science, rather than building relationships, the study set out to see where positivist worldviews could intermingle with social science theory to gain a richer understanding of this phenomenon through reflexivity (Knoblauch, 2021). This foregrounds the importance of people and social interaction in this context, which is foundational to the humanist aspects of educational theory (Rowley, Fook and Glazzard, 2018). Wilhelm von Humboldt (1854) cites Aristotle to outline the importance of humanness within intellectual activity:

For that which peculiarly belongs to each by nature, is best and most pleasant to everyone; and consequently, to man, the life according to intellect (is most pleasant), if intellect especially constitutes Man. This life therefore is the most happy.

This quotation inculcates the way scholarship thrives within the dimensions of humanism, with happiness being the ultimate objective. Happiness and fulfilment were illuminated as issues of contention for lecturers in this study. Challenges from increased competitiveness, competing workload pressures and institutional demands endanger the triple nexus and add to a general sense of precarity (Wheaton, 2020; Sutton, 2017). This can be helped at local level by providing more access to CPD opportunities and developing modules in science communication for undergraduates and as part of a postgraduate certificate in academic practice (Davies, 2020; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). However, although these recommendations may improve approaches to learning and teaching, this does not address the structural challenges that lecturers reportedly face.

Policy findings from the study centre on the differences between institutional hierarchies when it comes to implementing public engagement into a university's mission. As Papatsiba and Cohen (2019) have found, this study has also found marked differences between the capabilities and capacities of lecturers working at pre- or post-92 HEIs in terms of their abilities to embed public engagement activity into their work. To remedy this, there should be a greater focus brought on the inequities between lecturers' contracts to find a balance in the triple nexus at all universities in Scotland (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

Given that Scotland ascribes to a policy for wellbeing as a nation (Eardley, Banister and Fletcher, 2020), policy for educators needs to implement support for eudaimonic wellbeing – fulfilment of purpose and self-being (Sutton, 2017). Given the precarity of the situation in post-92 HEIs, there is also evidence from this study showing that the lack of support within departmental structures to support lecturers with public engagement means that there will be a continued flow of professional scientists away from these types of HEI, compounding the added loss of talent and economic uncertainty brought about by Brexit (Leith and Sim, 2020).

Embodiment is explored within this study through the interaction of interpretative phenomenology and reflexivity using autoethnographic methods (Starr, 2014). As such, the study contributes novel findings towards this approach to data gathering and is identified as a suitable method to gather embodied, qualitative data through virtual

qualitative interviews in situations where face-to-face data gathering may not be possible (Leigh and Bailey, 2013). This approach can be used in a variety of circumstances including a lockdown in a public health crisis (Roberts, Pavlakis and Richards, 2021), if travel distances are too far, or if respondents to a study are unable to meet face-to-face with a researcher because of disability or sensitivity (King, Horrocks and Brooks, 2018).

The implications of the merger between scholarship and embodiment were hard to comprehend for some of the respondents. Some held a very positivist view and saw little space for social science to mix with scientific inquiry (Knoblauch, 2021). Others were open to this approach, particularly when they reflected upon autoethnographic findings within the study, the most effective being the poem, “The Pedagogue’s Sonnet”, which reinforces the use of autoethnography as a reflexive practice for educators (Olmos-López and Tusting, 2020; Hains-Wesson and Young, 2016).

The links between an embodied approach to R/T/Pe and compassion shed light on the policies for HE and indicate a need for a re-configuration of policy and funding to support the triple nexus, particularly in the STEM disciplines that appear to present very little data on impact cases (Duncan, Manners and Miller, 2017). This should be done at macro-level by addressing this in national and international policies to guard against breakdown in trust between HE and lecturers, policy-makers and civil society – without this, the triple nexus is in danger of being perfunctory or performative (Hazelkorn and Gibson, 2018).

6.3 Implications for STEM

The study unveiled difficulties when it comes to promoting public engagement with pure science (Hargittai, 2022). There is a substantial body of evidence to indicate that, over the last 20 years, science and the public communication of science has come to the forefront of practice (Trench, 2008; Weingart, Joubert and Connaway, 2021), but in this study examples of practice in pure science tended to be viewed as “bolt-ons” to research. This requires a culture change and indicates that, despite examples in current practice outlined in the literature, there is still a danger of public engagement initiatives being limited to one-off events, particularly within school settings (Archer *et*

al., 2021). This requires scientists and academic developers to be creative in their approaches to research in pure science disciplines, either by engaging with the public in creative ways or by reaching out to the public using third spaces (Jarreau *et al.*, 2019; Lubicz-Nawrocka, 2019).

Public engagement within HE should not be focused on “promiscuity” to increase recruitment in STEM or attract more students to sign up to certain HEIs (Watermeyer and Lewis, 2015). This is reflected in the views of the respondents in this study, who were demotivated by “tick-box” evaluations or events run as exercises in public relations. These sorts of initiatives are very audience-focused on one section of society and fail to recognise the benefits of public engagement with STEM and the ways these interacts with marginalised groups, such as indigenous communities, prisoners, older people or those with different abilities. This study did show that the lecturers who were interviewed (bar one) all found a great deal of pleasure and satisfaction in communicating their research in these types of settings outside the bounds of the ivory tower (Gani *et al.*, 2024). This calls for more research on the emic and etic dimensions of scientific research to be explored, particularly in relation to intersectionality and the ways this relates to teaching and research in STEM (Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021; Beals, Kidman and Funaki, 2019).

It is vital to develop public engagement programmes in STEM with schools to help to train the next generation of scientists and develop research-readiness, however, as contended by Healey and Jenkins (2009) and Joseph-Richard *et al.* (2021), this is underlined by the importance of developing skills for research-mindedness at an early age. This adds to knowledge concerning the teaching/research nexus and the educational theory of Vygotsky, who posited teaching methods to privilege the student-as-producer in inquiry-based learning (Lazonder and Harmsen, 2016). This can be assisted by developing links to improve skills for research in schools and in the first year of undergraduate study.

In Scotland, maturity of age has been identified as a potential factor that hampers research-readiness as many undergraduates leave school aged seventeen. A possible solution could involve in developing a first-year undergraduate training programme or a module that specifically focuses on science communication, public

outreach and academic skills to develop the “impact identity” of students (Menlove *et al.*, 2019). This ambassador approach to public engagement has been shown to develop stronger links between undergraduate and postgraduate cohorts and could develop routes for lecturers to integrate CPD in this area alongside undergraduate teaching to support the triple nexus in STEM (Stevenson and McArthur, 2015).

6.4 Personal development

Reflexivity forms a foundational aspect of teaching practice and weaves a thread throughout the findings of the study (Carr *et al.*, 2020). At the outset, I committed to writing on my positionality in the research and continued to do so as the research continued. Using a combination of IPA with autoethnographic methods, I reflected on the findings and shared these with the participants in the study (Dörfler and Stierand, 2020). Portraiture was used as a method within the methodology to record the “natural attitude” of the researcher and participants at a given moment in time (Eatough and Smith, 2008).

Although a single moment cannot define identity, as Bruhn and Jimenez (2020) rightly point out, identity is not static which determined the phenomenological aspects of participants’ experience, namely *noema* (what is experienced) and *noesis* (how it is experienced) (Hains-Wesson and Young, 2016). A significant finding of this study is illuminated within the methodology and its process to uncover the painterly aspects of autoethnography, using “imaginative variation” as a tool of phenomenology. There is scope for further research in this respect through collaborative autoethnography and writing groups (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019).

6.5 Summary

For public engagement initiatives to thrive, it is vital that universities modernise and extend the tenets of the R/T/Pe to embed public engagement as the third mission of the university (REF, 2018; Collini, 2012). While this is problematic in practice because of the multi-faceted demands on lecturers’ time and activity, it is essential that policy at macro- and micro- levels is put in place to support this to address issues of social justice and improve working conditions for lecturers (Wheaton, 2020; Caltagirone *et al.*, 2021).

This study asserts that the conceptualisation of the ivory tower is outdated, and the optimum way that meaningful links can be made between science and society should be through adoption of open research practices and better training for undergraduates and lecturers (Farrow *et al.*, 2020; Davies, 2020). This research contributes to evidence that calls for better definition of the teaching/research nexus and the ways that this interacts with public engagement (McKinley *et al.*, 2020; Joseph-Richard *et al.*, 2021; Stevenson and McArthur, 2015). If HE is to grow in line with recent policy suggestions to link impact assessment with funding, this cannot be at the cost of putting knowledge production in crisis (Brew, 1999; Baird and Elliott, 2018).

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Appendix A: Ethical approval and participant information forms

18/06/2021

Dear Lucy Beattie,

Your application 16437: Speaking from the heart - crossing the teaching research nexus, submission reference 13745, has been approved, with conditions, by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below; These can be discussed between the applicant and the supervisor and changes to improve the study overseen by the supervisor.**

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them. Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Title	Comment
Re. summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	The idea for the research study is very good, however in this iteration, it requires more thought in execution.
Re. I summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	the design and methodology has inbuilt bias inherent in its design. There appears to be an assumption that the teaching links to research will be different dependent on the type of institution, rather than on the experience training and quality of the staff.
Re. the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)	The rationale for the study remains very unclear, with various statements made that appear monolithic in relation to what is assumed to be going on in higher education.
Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule	The interview schedule while intended to be unstructured does require the researcher to gather data about the staff member, as comparisons underpin the rationale for the study. Therefore there needs to be more exploration and an acknowledgment that teaching underpinned by research while influenced by a university's history and culture is about what staff do when teaching, and how they using their own experience and attempt to deliver teaching that is underpinned by research, or that relies somewhat on technology. Finally there has to be an acknowledgment of the concept of attempting or acknowledging data saturation as a concept being achieved, which underpins this type of exploratory research to minimise the inherent assumptions and bias potential underpinning the existing design.
Please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:	The issue of protecting participant identity could do with a bit of clarification. Give the universities concerned are either ancient or post 92, is it clear that pseudonyms will be applied? How are participants' identities going to be protected, given that that subject- association and role have (perhaps remote, but nonetheless) some potential to point to individuals. Anonymising identities was mentioned but could be more explicit.

<p><i>The design and methodology has inbuilt bias inherent in its design. There appears to be an assumption that the teaching links to research will be different dependent on the type of institution, rather than on the experience training and quality of the staff.</i></p>	<p>Understood. The ethics application has not gone in depth and needs to be dealt with more thoroughly in the methodology chapter.</p> <p>However, IPA seems best method as comparative case study (CCS) methodology did not seem appropriate as the instances and acknowledgement of research-informed approaches at undergrad level seem fuzzy and unsubstantiated in Scotland. Therefore, difficult to construct a case/compare cases.</p> <p>However, literature indicates that teaching predominates research in Post92 HEIs and vice versa. Therefore as (Sloan and Bowe, 2014) point out the complexity of human lived experience needs to be elucidated as a phenomena of experience.</p> <p>The root of IPA stems from the philosophy identified by Husserl and refined by Heidegger (Sloan and Bowe, 2014; Farrow <i>et al.</i>, 2020) and further refined and re-defined as a methodology by subsequent theorists:</p> <p>Gadamer focused on the use of language to identify themes which highlights the use of language within interviews to guard against bias in IPA. Awareness of intersectionality and inclusivity in academic language eg. “master copy” “black list” “grey literature” (Khan, 2021).</p>
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	<p>Van Manen looked at the practical approach to IPA and how it can formatively influence the relation between being and practice (existentialism into vocation). He also suggested that the researcher should use comparable human experiences through “existentials”:</p> <p>Lived space: spatiality Lived body: corporeality Lived time: temporality Lived human relation: relationality</p> <p>This will guide the broad thematic analysis before distilling to sub-themes which emerge from interview data and coding.</p>
<p><i>The rationale for the study remains very unclear, with various statements made that appear monolithic in relation to what is assumed to be going on in higher education.</i></p>	<p>This is hard for me as I am not engrained into HE culture. What I see from literature is that there is a chasm between the Humboldtian philosophy of what makes a University i.e. inquiry driven, research-ready vs. the managerial constricts enforced through consumerist policy.</p> <p>How does this affect Scottish HE? Public perception/literature/policy suggests Scotland has a tradition of excellence in research stemming from the times of the Scottish enlightenment. This philosophy has bolstered its national approach to access to education for all, how does this play out in the 21st Century for</p>

	<p>Scottish undergrads, all of whom can apply for a fully funded place?</p> <p>What is the legacy of the Scottish enlightenment as we move into University 4.0 and the post-pandemic University? Are we moving towards Enlightenment 2.0? Or is it just neoliberal, marketized rhetoric to keep funders and policy makers happy?</p> <p>So, what is the relevance to this study now:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coming out of covid how can this be a changemaker - Understanding how Scottish undergrad teaching/research works and how they engage with public
<p><i>The interview schedule while intended to be unstructured does require the researcher to gather data about the staff member, as comparisons underpin the rationale for the study. Therefore there needs to be more exploration and an acknowledgment that teaching underpinned by research while influenced by a university's history and culture is about what staff do when teaching, and how they using their own experience and attempt to deliver teaching that is underpinned by research, or that relies somewhat on technology.</i></p>	<p>I think I need to move back from the presumption that there will be a split between HRI and LRI institutions. The exploration of individuals experience defines the concept of intentionality within phenomenology. Brentano highlights the need to be intentional about the understanding of the “aboutness” of lived experience (Harris, 2011).</p> <p>But how then do I justify a very purposive sample... i.e. Post 92 and Ancient unis only? Therefore the sample will be broad so that no direct comparison is made and bias is reduced.</p>

<p><i>Finally there has to be an acknowledgment of the concept of attempting or acknowledging data saturation as a concept being achieved, which underpins this type of exploratory research to minimise the inherent assumptions and bias potential underpinning the existing design.</i></p>	<p>A disadvantage to the design is the reliance on interview data (Farrow <i>et al.</i>, 2020). However, this is the reason that preliminary findings from stage 1 interviews would be shared to comment, reflection and feedback prior to stage 2 interviews. Given the timing of the study during the pandemic lockdowns this must be acknowledged as a limitation.</p> <p>There would be a case to adopt grounded theory as a method in tandem, but as it is a single student PhD project this would likely be unachievable within the timeframe of the study.</p>
<p><i>The issue of protecting participant identity could do with a bit of clarification. Give the universities concerned are either ancient or post 92, is it clear that pseudonyms will be applied? How are participants' identities going to be protected, given that that subject-association and role have (perhaps remote, but nonetheless) some potential to point to individuals. Anonymising identities was mentioned but could be more explicit.</i></p>	<p>Can make this clearer. Anonymising identities/subject matter/location.</p> <p>Some thought to be given to pseudonyms. Should it be participant 123 etc ABC or to humanise "Alfie" "Barbara" "Charles"?</p>

Risk Register

Risk assessment will be continuous throughout the study and will be supported within a defined framework for management i.e. monitored on a regular basis and actioned as appropriate.

Although major incidents are not expected if one were to occur this would be dealt with in an appropriate manner and reported to the lead supervisor (LS), Dr Stephanie Zihms, as a matter of urgency. Risks supported within a defined framework will be monitored and reviewed to see if further action is appropriate for unanticipated risks.

The management of risk will be regularly monitored by the principal investigator (PI), Lucy Beattie, to ensure that risk management is effective in the event of the risk profile changing. Any unexpected risks that do arise will be communicated to the lead supervisor, and strategies to manage the risk will be updated.

Issue	Likelihood of risk (low, medium or high)	Mitigating Action(s)	Recovery Plan
Conflict of interest	L	Any conflict of interest will be declared by PI.	Any such conflict of interest will be reported to the LS and noted within the results to ensure transparency.
Sustainable procurement and sustainability	L	Project will be delivered in line with the UWS sustainability plan .	Steps to mitigate will include reducing travel or using public transport where possible, using recycled consumables and limiting the use of plastic.

Health, Safety and Welfare	L	<p>The PI will take reasonable care for the health, safety, mental and physical welfare of themselves and others who may be affected by their acts or omissions.</p> <p>Travel will be according to UWS international travel policy and procedures. Suitable insurance will be taken out together with EIHC cards for EU medical cover.</p>	<p>All accidents, incidents and near misses will be immediately reported to the LS.</p> <p>International travel itineraries and check ins will be reported to the LS.</p>
PI unable to complete study due to force majeure or research participants becoming unwell.	M	<p>Given the current pandemic and associated self-isolation protocols there is a medium likelihood of the study being disrupted if the PI or a participant contracts COVID19 or is a close contact with someone who has contracted COVID19.</p>	<p>Report to LS and arrange alternative dates or additional participants recruited as required.</p> <p>In the event of any unanticipated events that could cause significant delay to the study an application to UWS will be made for extenuating circumstances (ECS).</p>
COVID-19	H	<p>The PI will ensure that any data gathering is in</p>	<p>Ensure data is gathered remotely</p>

		line with current Scottish Government guidelines for the control and prevention of COVID19.	where possible and if this is not possible ensure appropriate social distancing and biosecurity measures are undertaken.
Data Protection and Ethics	L	PI is aware of GDPR rules concerning data handling in line with UWS policy. All data will be gathered according to regulations set down by BERA .	Data will be gathered and held on a secure folder within the UWS MS Teams channel. Any back up files will be held on a password protected hard drive locked within a filing cabinet. Any breach of data will be reported immediately to the LS to ensure that breach is dealt within stated guidelines.
Financial management and monitoring	L	Any external costs such as training, resources and travel will be identified and applied for within the PGR budget.	Given the nature of the study which gathers data via digital means the financial risk is low. Any budgetary issues will be reported directly to the LS.

STEM lecturer or researcher?

Call for research participants to explore research, teaching and public engagement.

I'm looking to connect with participants in:

- ✓ Earth systems and environmental science
- ✓ Chemistry
- ✓ Physics
- ✓ Engineering
- ✓ Mathematics
- ✓ Computer science

My name is Lucy Beattie. I'm a PhD candidate at the UWS School of Education and Social Sciences based in Paisley, Scotland.

My study looks at the lived experience of lecturers who work in STEM panel B disciplines in Scottish HE with particular emphasis on the links they make between teaching, research and public engagement.

Participants are invited to be interviewed about their experiences in public engagement, research and teaching with undergraduate student cohorts.

Participants will be drawn from two Post-92 and two Ancient HE institutions in Scotland. Interviews will be strictly confidential and personal data and findings will be anonymised to ensure confidentiality.

Benefits of participation include a chance to explore and reflect on your scholarly practice to pinpoint how you develop links between teaching and research. There are no anticipated harms to taking part and the study has been granted ethical approval from the UWS ethics committee no 16437.

The expected time commitment will extend to an orientation call lasting no more than 30 minutes to discuss mutual expectations relating to the study. This will be followed up by two semi-structured interviews lasting approximately one hour each over a six month period.

Interviews will be conducted remotely or face-to-face according to participant preference and relevant COVID19 public health guidelines at the time. Data will be recorded, transcribed and stored securely for the duration of the study and used for no other purpose than to inform the research questions.

To join the study or for more information contact:

Lucy Beattie

PhD supervisors

Dr Stephanie Zihms

Dr Gordon Heggie

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

CONSENT FORM

PARTICIPATION IN THIS RESEARCH STUDY IS VOLUNTARY

I have read and understood the study information dated [DD/MM/YY], or it has been read to me. I have been able to ask questions about the study and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.	YES / NO
I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and understand that I can refuse to answer questions and that I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason.	YES / NO
I agree to interviews being audio recorded on MS Teams or mp4	YES / NO
I understand that the information I provide will be used for the purposes of this study and associated publications only and that all personal, identifying information will be anonymised.	YES / NO
I agree that my (anonymised) information can be quoted in research outputs.	YES / NO
I understand that any personal information that can identify me – such as my name, address, will be kept confidential and not shared with anyone other than the principal investigator Lucy Beattie.	YES / NO

Please retain a copy of this consent form and sign below:

Participant name:

Participant email address:

Signature: _____

Date _____

Who should I contact for more information about the research?

Lucy Beattie PhD Candidate

What if I have a complaint about the research?

If you have a complaint about the research, please contact my supervisors

Dr Stephanie Zihms

Dr Gordon Heggie

